

Numbers and Magic Squares Representations of Hardy-Ramanujan Number-1729

*On a Special Day:
137th Birth Anniversary of S. Ramanujan,
December 22, 2024 - National Mathematics Day
(<https://bit.ly/3yOMpl3>)*

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Abstract

*This paper brings representations of 1729, a famous **Hardy-Ramanujan number** in different ways. These representations are of **crazy-type, single digit, single letter, Selfie-type, running expressions, selfie fractions, equivalent fractions, Triangular, Fibonacci, fixed digits repetitions prime numbers patterns, Pythagorean triples, palindromic-type, polygonal-type, prime numbers, embedded, repeated**, etc. Some quotes and historical notes on Ramanujan's life are also specified. This work brings **magic squares** connected with S. Ramanujan's life and with Hardy-Ramanujan number 1729. There are three different types of **magic squares**. The **first type** is based on some historical years of S. Ramanujan's life. The **second type** is with magic sum as 1729. In this case the magic squares constructed are of orders 7, 13, 14 and 19. The **third type** is magic squares based on **Pythagorean triples** where the number 1729 is one the entry. In this case the magic squares constructed are of orders 6, 7, 11 and 19. It is revised and enlarged version of author's previous work [5].*

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An equation means nothing to me unless it expresses a thought of God.
 - S. Ramanujan

mgc	13x13 https://numbers-magic.com/					https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/					1729		
86	68	178	189	75	78	216	71	206	82	214	199	67	1729
180	198	88	77	191	188	50	195	60	184	52	61	205	1729
72	194	153	150	101	112	170	147	98	107	159	63	203	1729
215	51	113	116	165	154	96	119	168	95	171	186	80	1729
79	187	115	151	135	142	122	141	125	156	110	179	87	1729
209	57	160	106	131	124	144	137	129	163	103	176	90	1729
58	208	169	97	123	143	133	121	145	164	102	62	204	1729
183	83	120	146	136	130	128	139	132	94	172	190	76	1729
85	181	157	109	140	126	138	127	134	152	114	185	81	1729
212	54	99	167	118	117	104	173	100	158	161	92	174	1729
66	200	111	155	148	149	162	93	166	108	105	70	196	1729
73	193	182	175	177	65	64	217	59	69	53	192	210	1729
211	55	84	91	89	201	202	49	207	197	213	74	56	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is **double digits bordered** magic square. Since it is based on equal width stripes, we may call it **almost striped** magic square, because the internal parte is only magic square of order 5.

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1 Quotes and Historical Notes

Another famous quote of Ramanujan on his dreams:

While asleep, I had an unusual experience. There was a red screen formed by flowing blood, as it were. I was observing it. Suddenly a hand began to write on the screen. I became all attention. That hand wrote a number of elliptic integrals. They stuck to my mind. As soon as I woke up, I committed them to writing.

S. Ramanujan

Confirmations to Ramanujan's dreams:

Ono and his colleagues (Emory University, Atlanta, GA, USA) drew on modern mathematical tools that had not been developed before Ramanujan's death to prove this theory was correct. We proved that Ramanujan was right. We've solved the problems from his last mysterious letters. For people who work in this area of math, the problem has been open for 90 years.

We found the formula explaining one of the visions that he believed came from his goddess - K. Ono

Read more at:

1. <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-2254352/Deathbed-dream-puzzles-renowned-Indian-mathematician-Srinivasa-finally-solved-100-years-died.html>
2. <http://www.livescience.com/25597-ramanujans-math-theories-proved.html>.
3. <https://www.quantamagazine.org/20160519-ken-ono-mathematician-inspired-by-ramanujan/>

Below are few more **quotes** on Ramanujan's work:

I had never seen anything in the least like them before. A single look at them is enough to show that they could only be written by a mathematician of the highest class. They must be true because, if they were not true, "no one would have the imagination to invent them".
He also said, like other great men "he invented himself".
- G.H. Hardy

Every positive integer is one of Ramanujan's personal friends.
- J. Littlewood

I still don't understand it all. I may be able to prove it, but I don't know where it comes from and where it fits into the rest of mathematics.
- B.C. Berndt

The enigma of Ramanujan's creative process is still covered by a curtain that has barely been drawn.

The Man Who Knew Infinity, 1991.

- R. Kanigel

When we comprehend some of Ramanujan's equations, we realize that he was a true artist, expressing deep and beautiful mathematical truth in familiar symbols.

Mathematical Mysteries, 1996.

- C. Clawson

That was the wonderful thing about Ramanujan. He discovered so much, and yet he left so much more in his garden for other people to discover.

- F. Dyson

He discovered bizarre and strange set of modular mathematical functions which are out of this world ... Civilization has to wait another one hundred years to understand remotely Ramanujan's mind".

- K. Ono.

Read more quotes at

1. <https://www.famousscientists.org/srinivasa-ramanujan/>.
2. <http://quoteaddicts.com/author/srinivasa-ramanujan>.
3. <http://www.azquotes.com/quotes/topics/ramanujan.html>

The history of S. Ramanujan is well-known in the literature. There are so many sites on Internet relating about him. Below are some of them:

1. <http://www-groups.dcs.st-and.ac.uk/history/Biographies/Ramanujan.html>.
2. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Srinivasa-Ramanujan>.
3. <http://www.thebetterindia.com/52974/srinivasa-ramanujan-mathematician-biopic>.
4. <http://www.biography.com/people/srinivasa-ramanujan-082515>.
5. <http://www.livescience.com/25597-ramanujans-math-theories-proved.html>.

Besides from his excellent work on mathematics, the Taxicab number 1729 is famous due to his instantaneous combinations with minimum cubes done by him, such as

$$1729 := 1^3 + 12^3 = 9^3 + 10^3$$

Even though this number is famous as "**Hardy-Ramanujan number**", historically it has been studied before in 1657 (Boyer, 2008).

1. <http://esciencecommons.blogspot.com.br/2015/10/mathematicians-find-magic-key-to-drive.html>.
2. <http://www.zmescience.com/science/math/taxi-number-ramanujan-03213>.
3. **C. Boyer**, *New upper bounds for Taxicab and Cabtaxi Numbers*, *J. Integer Sequences*, **11**(2008), Art. 08.1.6, <https://cs.uwaterloo.ca/journals/JIS/VOL11/Boyer/boyer-new.pdf>.

Ramanujan also worked on magic squares. One of his famous magic square is based on his date of birth. Below are some sites talking about his magic square:

1. <http://www.math.mcgill.ca/styan/Beamer3-18jan12-opt.pdf>.
2. <http://mathstimes.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/Birthday-magic-square.pdf>.
3. <http://slideplayer.com/slide/9142307/>.
4. <http://jollymaths.com/blog/srinivasa-ramanujan-16x16-biography-magic-square/>

Ramanujan's whole work is composed as "**Notebooks**". See the following links:

1. **B. C. Berndt**, *Ramanujan's Notebooks, Parts I-V*. Springer-Verlag, New York, 1985, 1989, 1991, 1994, 1998.
2. **G. E. Andrews** and **B. C. Berndt**, *Ramanujan's Lost Notebook, Part I-IV*, Springer, New York, 2005, 2009, 2012, 2013.

Some of his work and biography can be seen in following books:

1. **C.C. Clawson** *Mathematical Mysteries - The Beauty and Magic of Numbers*. Springer, New York, 1996.
2. **R. Kanigel** *The Man Who Knew Infinity: A Life of the Genius Ramanujan*, Washington Square Press, New York, 1991
3. **C.A. Pickover**, *A Passion for Mathematics*, John Wiley & Sons, New Jersey, 2005.
4. **K. Ono** and **A. D. Aczel**, *My Search for Ramanujan - How I Learned to Count*, Springer, New York, 2016.

The aim of this work is to present different representations of **Hardy-Ramanujan number 1729**. Also to present new types of magic squares with more details of his biography with the presence of number **1729**.

2 Magic Squares with 1729

This section deals with the magic squares of order 4 and 5 are made in such a way that they brings more details of life of Ramanujan.

2.1 Magic Square of Order 4

The following magic square is famous as Ramanujan's magic square of order 4. It contains the details of his date of birth, i.e., 22.12.1887:

				139
22	12	18	87	139
88	17	9	25	139
10	24	89	16	139
19	86	23	11	139
139	139	139	139	139

Ramanujan's Magic Square

Figure 1

The magic sum $S := 139$ is a prime number:

$$22 + 12 + 18 + 87 = 139$$

The above magic square (Figure 1) constructed by Ramanujan brings only his date of birth. Below is modified version of above magic square where we brought *Hardy-Ramanujan number* 1729:

				139
22	12	18	87	139
88	17	29	5	139
20	14	79	26	139
9	96	13	21	139
139	139	139	139	139

Figure 2

Interestingly, if we sum the numbers with his date of death (26.04.1920) in little different way, i.e., considering sum four in four instead two and two digits, we get much more options to put in a magic square. See below

$$2212 + 1887 + 2604 + 1920 = 8623$$

Again we have a prime number. Below is a magic square with followings details of **Ramanujan**:

Date of Birth : 22.12.1887

Date of Death : 26.04.1920

Servived from Smallpox : 1889

Got Job at Madras Port Trust : 1912

Year of Entering England : 1914

Fellow Royal Society, London : 1918

Hardy-Ramanujan Number : 1729.

				8623
2212	1887	2604	1920	8623
1914	2610	1729	2370	8623
1918	2395	1889	2421	8623
2579	1731	2401	1912	8623
8623	8623	8623	8623	8623

Figure 3

We observe that the above magic squares (Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3) are not *pan diagonal*. In all the examples above the magic sum is prime, i.e., odd numbers. It is impossible to construct pan diagonal magic square of order 4 for odd number magic square sum. If we want pan diagonal magic square of order 4 with some Ramanujan’s details, we have to make little change, i.e., to consider magic sum as even number. See below:

Date of Birth : 22.12.1887

Date of Death : 26.04.1920

Hardy-Ramanujan Number : 1729.

		8432	8432	8432	8432
	2212	1887	1729	2604	8432
8432	1696	2637	2179	1920	8432
8432	2487	1612	2004	2329	8432
8432	2037	2296	2520	1579	8432
	8432	8432	8432	8432	8432

Figure 4

In this case the magic sum, $S = 8432$ is not a prime number, but the magic square is pan diagonal. Coincidentally, the number 8432 divided in two by two i.e, 84 and 32 give 84-gonal 7th value is 1729, i.e., $P_{84}(7) := 1729$ and 32 the age Ramanujan died. According to Hindu philosophy "*The number 84 is a "whole" or "perfect" number. Thus the eighty-four siddhas can be seen as archetypes representing the thousands of exemplars and adept of the tantric way*"

<http://keithdowman.net/essays/introduction-mahasiddhas-and-tantra.html>

2.2 Magic Squares of Order 5

The magic square appearing in Figure 4 contains less details as being pan diagonal. Still, we can make pan diagonal magic square of order 5 with more details. See below:

Date of Birth : 22.12.1887
 Date of Death : 26.04.1920
 Age at the time of Death : 32
 Got Job at Madrs Port Trust : 1912
 Year of Entering England : 1914
 Fellow Royal Society, London : 1918
 Hardy-Ramanujan Number : 1729.

		8655	8655	8655	8655	8655
	2212	1887	32	2604	1920	8655
8655	1754	1914	3062	1918	7	8655
8655	2768	38	1729	1064	3056	8655
8655	1039	2206	2762	888	1760	8655
8655	882	2610	1070	2181	1912	8655
	8655	8655	8655	8655	8655	8655

Figure 5

Since our work is more concentrated towards number 1729. Below is another pan diagonal magic square of order 5 with sum $5 \times 1729 = 8645$ with similar details as of Figure 5.

Date of Birth : 22.12.1887
 Date of Death : 26.04.1920
 Worked on Mathematics : 22 years
 Age at the time of Death : 32 years
 Most Struggling Year : 1908
 Year of Entering England : 1914
 Fellow Royal Society, London : 1918
 Hardy-Ramanujan Number : 1729
 Magic Sum : $8645 = 5 \times 1729$.

		5×1729				
	2212	1887	22	2604	1920	5×1729
5×1729	1750	1914	3062	1918	1	5×1729
5×1729	2768	32	1729	1060	3056	5×1729
5×1729	1039	2202	2762	882	1760	5×1729
5×1729	876	2610	1070	2181	1908	5×1729
	5×1729					

Figure 6

It is interesting to observe that the number "22" appearing in the middle of first line is the span period of time Ramanujan worked on mathematics. Also it is famous that Professor Bruce C. Berndt (University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Illinois, USA) spent about 22 years to solve 3254 problems from Ramanujan's notebooks (<http://ramanujans.blogspot.com.br/>). Another number appearing in magic square is 1908. As compared to other years, this year don't brings any this special to Ramanujan's life. His marriage happened in 1909. On the other hand, according to the book "**R. Kanigel** *The Man Who Knew Infinity: A Life of the Genius Ramanujan*, Washington Square Press, New York, 1991", on page 55, it is written that year 1908 was very difficult for him as he was, *out of school, without job, without food, etc.*

The approach applied to construct above four squares is different from the one used by Ramanujan (The Notebooks of Ramanujan, Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Bombay, 1957).

More on magic square see author's another work [11].

3 Single Digit Representations

Below are representations of the number **1729** written in terms of each digit separately using 1 to 9. Even though it can be written using 0 but it requires use of factorials.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} &:= (11 + 1)^{1+1+1} + 1 \\
 &:= (2/2 + 2) \times (22 + 2)^2 + 2/2 \\
 &:= (3 \times 3 + 3)^3 + 3/3 \\
 &:= 4 \times (4 \times 44 + 4^4) + 4/4 \\
 &:= 55 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + (5^5 - 5)/5 + 5 \\
 &:= 6 \times 6 \times (6 \times 6 + 6 + 6) + 6/6 \\
 &:= 7 \times 7 \times (7 \times 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 + 7 \\
 &:= 8 \times (8 \times (8 + 8) + 88) + 8/8 \\
 &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + 999 + 9/9.
 \end{aligned}$$

3.1 Patterns in Single Digit

Below are few patterns based on the above representations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= 55 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + 5 + \frac{5^5 - 5}{5} & 1729 &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + 999 + \frac{9}{9} \\
 11729 &:= 555 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + 5 + \frac{5^5 - 5}{5} & 10729 &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + 9999 + \frac{9}{9} \\
 111729 &:= 5555 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + 5 + \frac{5^5 - 5}{5} & 100729 &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + 99999 + \frac{9}{9} \\
 1111729 &:= 55555 \times (5 \times 5 - 5) + 5 + \frac{5^5 - 5}{5} & 1000729 &:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 + 999999 + \frac{9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

The above two patterns are not uniform. In order to get uniform pattern for all digits, we can replace single letter **a** given in next section by 1 to 9.

4 Single Letter Representation

In Section 3 the number **1729** is written in terms of each digit separately. Instead using each digit separately as of Section 3, one can write this number using single letter "a". It remains true for any value of *a* from 1 to 9.

$$1729 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}.$$

where, $aaa = a10^2 + a10 + a,$
 $aa = a10 + a, a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}.$

4.1 Patterns in Single Letter

Below is a different for 1729 written in single letter a:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 14729 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 144729 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 1444729 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

where, $aaaaa := a10^4 + a10^3 + a10^2 + a10 + a,$ $aaaa := a10^3 + a10^2 + a10 + a,$
 $aaa := a10^2 + a10 + a,$ $aa := a10 + a,$ **etc.**
 $a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}.$

5 Crazy Representations

5.1 Increasing and Decreasing

The number **1729** is written in terms of 1 to 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 and reverse.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} &:= 12^3 - 4 + 5 && = 54 \times 32 + 1 \\
 &:= 12^3 + (-4 + 5)^6 && = 6 \times (5 + 4) \times 32 + 1 \\
 &:= 123 \times (4 \times 5 - 6) + 7 && = (7 - 6) \times (54 \times 32 + 1) \\
 &:= -1 + (2 + 34 + 5) \times 6 \times 7 + 8 && = 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4) \times 32 \times 1 \\
 &:= 12 - 3 + 4^5 - 6 + 78 \times 9 && = (98 - 7) \times (6 \times 5 - 4 \times 3 + 2 - 1).
 \end{aligned}$$

5.2 Ending in Zero

The number **1729** is written with ending in 0, starting with 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} &:= (4 \times 3)^{2+1} + 0! \\
 &:= 54 \times 32 + 1 \times 0! \\
 &:= 6! - 5 - 4 - 3! + 2^{10} \\
 &:= (7 + 6) \times (-5 - 4! \times 3 + 210) \\
 &:= 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2^{10} \\
 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 - 4 - 3 + 2 + 10).
 \end{aligned}$$

5.3 Numbers from 1 to 10 and Reverse

Instead using 1 to 9 or 9 to 1, here the numbers 1 to 10 are used in both ways, i.e., increasing and decreasing.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} &:= 10 \times (98 + 7 + 65 + \sqrt{4}) + 3^2 \times 1 \\
 &:= 1 + 2^3 + (-4 + 56 + ((7 + 8)/\sqrt{9})!) \times 10.
 \end{aligned}$$

6 Powers and Bases: Same Digits

This section deals with the representations of **1729** in such a way that the powers and based are with same set of digits in a permutable way.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^2 \\
 &:= 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^2 \\
 &:= 0^1 + 1^0 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^2 \\
 &:= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
 &:= 0^3 + 1^0 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
 &:= 1^8 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
 &:= 0^6 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 7^2 \\
 &:= 1^9 - 2^6 + 3^2 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 + 9^3 \\
 &:= 0^5 - 1^7 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 8^0 \\
 &:= -1^9 + 2^8 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 + 9^1 \\
 &:= 0^4 + 1^7 + 2^9 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 8^3 + 9^0
 \end{aligned}$$

6.1 Power Patterns

Based on the idea of same set of digits in powers and bases, seperated by addition and subtraction, below are some patterns containing the number **1729**.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} \times 10 + 0 &:= -1^7 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
 \mathbf{1729} \times 10 + 2 &:= 1^7 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
 \mathbf{1729} \times 10 + 4 &:= 1^7 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
 \mathbf{1729} \times 10 + 6 &:= -1^5 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
 \mathbf{1729} \times 10 + 8 &:= 1^5 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^1.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} \times 10 + 0 &:= 1^7 + 2^8 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 \mathbf{1729} \times 10 + 2 &:= 1^8 + 2^6 + 3^2 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^3 - 7^1 + 8^5 \\
 \mathbf{1729} \times 10 + 4 &:= 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^1 \\
 \mathbf{1729} \times 10 + 6 &:= 1^6 + 2^8 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
 \mathbf{1729} \times 10 + 8 &:= 1^8 + 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 8^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

7 Same Digits Both Sides

This section deals with the representations of **1729** in such way the we have almost same digits on both sides of the expressions. These representations are given in different situations.

7.1 Selfie-Type

$$1729665 := 17^2 \times 9 \times 665$$

$$4941729 := (494 + 1729)^2.$$

In the second case, we have power 2 extra. More study of this kind is given in Section 23 along with Fibonacci and Triangular sequence values.

7.2 Multiplication

The representations below are in such a way that we have same digits with each multiplicative factor on both sides.

$$1729 \times 3584 = 1792 \times 3458$$

$$1729 \times 3854 = 1927 \times 3458$$

$$1729 \times 4358 = 2179 \times 3458$$

$$1729 \times 4732 = 2197 \times 3724$$

$$1729 \times 5438 = 2719 \times 3458$$

$$1729 \times 5781 = 1927 \times 5187.$$

7.3 Power Plus

The representations below are in such a way that we have same digits on sides, where the one there the digits are as a power.

$$1729 := 2^7 + 40^2 + 130^0 = 27 + 402 + 1300$$

$$:= 2^6 + 40^2 + 64^1 + 66^0 = 26 + 402 + 641 + 660$$

$$:= 1^6 + 41^2 + 46^1 + 84^0 = 16 + 412 + 461 + 840.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= 3^5 + 3^5 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 8^3 + 150^0 = 35 + 35 + 36 + 40 + 83 + 1500 \\
 &:= 2^4 + 2^4 + 3^5 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 150^1 = 24 + 24 + 35 + 64 + 81 + 1501 \\
 &:= 2^4 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 150^1 = 24 + 28 + 31 + 64 + 81 + 1501 \\
 &:= 2^4 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 150^1 = 24 + 28 + 41 + 64 + 71 + 1501 \\
 &:= 2^4 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 6^4 + 150^1 = 24 + 28 + 51 + 61 + 64 + 1501 \\
 &:= 3^4 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 5^4 + 5^4 + 150^1 = 34 + 35 + 51 + 54 + 54 + 1501.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= 1^0 + 2^3 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 5^4 + 5^4 + 150^1 = 10 + 23 + 43 + 44 + 54 + 54 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^0 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 5^2 + 150^1 = 10 + 29 + 42 + 45 + 50 + 52 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^0 + 3^4 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 5^4 + 150^1 = 10 + 34 + 35 + 41 + 54 + 54 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 150^1 = 11 + 29 + 30 + 45 + 51 + 62 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^8 + 2^4 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 150^1 = 18 + 24 + 29 + 45 + 52 + 60 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^8 + 2^9 + 2^9 + 2^9 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 150^1 = 18 + 29 + 29 + 29 + 61 + 62 + 1501 \\
 &:= 2^0 + 2^9 + 4^0 + 4^2 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 150^1 = 20 + 29 + 40 + 42 + 45 + 52 + 1501 \\
 &:= 2^1 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 4^5 + 6^2 + 150^1 = 21 + 29 + 30 + 41 + 45 + 62 + 1501 \\
 &:= 2^5 + 2^6 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 150^1 = 25 + 26 + 27 + 36 + 54 + 60 + 1501 \\
 &:= 2^9 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 150^1 = 29 + 30 + 30 + 42 + 45 + 52 + 1501 \\
 &:= 2^9 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 6^2 + 150^1 = 29 + 30 + 31 + 31 + 45 + 62 + 1501.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= 1^0 + 2^8 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 4^2 + 4^3 + 150^1 := 10 + 28 + 29 + 36 + 40 + 42 + 43 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^1 + 2^6 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 150^1 := 11 + 26 + 29 + 36 + 40 + 42 + 44 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^2 + 2^4 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 150^1 := 12 + 24 + 29 + 36 + 40 + 43 + 44 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^4 + 2^0 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 150^1 := 14 + 20 + 29 + 36 + 42 + 43 + 44 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^4 + 2^5 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^0 + 4^4 + 4^5 + 150^1 := 14 + 25 + 28 + 32 + 40 + 44 + 45 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^4 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 4^5 + 150^1 := 14 + 28 + 33 + 33 + 35 + 40 + 45 + 1501 \\
 &:= 1^5 + 1^9 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 150^1 := 15 + 19 + 29 + 36 + 42 + 43 + 44 + 1501.
 \end{aligned}$$

There are much more representations of this kind, but only few are written.

7.4 Factorial-Power

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= 1! + (2! \times 4! + 5!) \times 3! + 6! = 1^3 + 2^6 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 3^2 + 6^1 \\
 &= (1^6 + 2^5) \times 4^1 + 5^4 + 3^3 \times 6^2 \\
 &:= 1! + (4! \times 3! + 6!) \times 2! = 1^6 + 4^2 \times 3^4 + 6^3 \times 2^1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= 1! + (6! + 3! \times 4!) \times 2! &&= 1^6 + 6^4 + 3^3 \times 4^1 \times 2^2 \\
 &:= 1! + 2! \times 3! \times (5! + 4!) &&= 1^1 + 2^2 \times (3^5 + 5^3) + 4^4 \\
 &:= 1! + 3! \times 2! \times (4! + 5!) &&= (1^1 + 3^2) \times 2^3 + 4^5 + 5^4 \\
 \\
 &:= 1! + 2! \times 3! \times (5! + 4!) &&= 1^1 + 2^5 \times (3^4 - 5^2) - 4^3 \\
 & &&= 1^2 + 2^3 \times (3^5 + 5^1) - 4^4 \\
 & &&= 1^3 + (2^5 + 3^4 - 5^1) \times 4^2 \\
 &:= 1! + 3! \times 2! \times (5! + 4!) &&= 1^5 - 3^1 \times (2^4 - 5^2) \times 4^3 \\
 & &&= 1^5 + 3^3 \times (2^4 \times 5^1 - 4^2) \\
 &:= 1! + (4! + 5! + 6!) \times 2! &&= 1^5 - 4^4 - (5^1 - 6^2) \times 2^6 \\
 & &&= 1^5 - 4^4 + (5^2 + 6^1) \times 2^6 \\
 &:= 1! + (6! + 4! + 5!) \times 2! &&= 1^6 + 6^4 - 4^2 \times (5^1 - 2^5) \\
 &:= 1! + (6! + 3! \times 4!) \times 2! &&= -1^6 + 6^4 + 3^3 \times 4^2 + 2^1 \\
 & &&= 1^1 + (6^2 - 3^3) \times (4^4 - 2^6) \\
 &:= 1! + (6! + 4! \times 3!) \times 2! &&= 1^1 - 6^3 \times 4^2 + 3^4 \times 2^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

8 Narcissistic-Type Representation

Narcissistic numbers are famous in the literature, when there are same digits on both sides with fixed power and operations of addition. Below is a representation of **1729** in terms division with flexible power instead of fixed.

$$\mathbf{1729} := \frac{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^{15} + 9^2}{1 + 7 + 2 + 9}.$$

9 Power Representations

As explained in Introduction, the idea of power representation of **1729** is given by Ramanujan. Here there are much more possibilities of wring this number as powers of 2 and 3.

9.1 Power 2

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} &:= 6^2 + 18^2 + 37^2 \\
 &:= 8^2 + 12^2 + 39^2 \\
 &:= 8^2 + 24^2 + 33^2 \\
 &:= 10^2 + 27^2 + 30^2 \\
 &:= 12^2 + 17^2 + 36^2 \\
 &:= 18^2 + 26^2 + 27^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

9.2 Power 3

$$\begin{aligned}1729 &:= 1^3 + 12^3 \\ &:= 9^3 + 10^3 \\ &:= 1^3 + 6^3 + 8^3 + 10^3 \\ &:= 1^3 + 3^3 + 4^3 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 10^3.\end{aligned}$$

9.3 Power 3 Multiplication

This subsection give product decomposition of **1729** using power 3.

$$\begin{aligned}1729 &:= (6^3 - 5^3) \times (3^3 - 2^3) \\ &:= (4^3 + 3^3) \times (3^3 - 2^3).\end{aligned}$$

10 Patterns with 1729: Power 3

The idea of power representation of **1729** given in Section 9 is extended here to give some patterns with number **1729**.

10.1 First Pattern

$$\begin{aligned}1729 \times 10 + 0 &:= 13^3 + 18^3 + 21^3 \\ 1729 \times 10 + 1 &:= 1^3 + 13^3 + 18^3 + 21^3 \\ 1729 \times 10 + 2 &:= 2^3 + 7^3 + 13^3 + 16^3 + 22^3 \\ &:= 7^3 + 9^3 + 13^3 + 15^3 + 22^3 \\ 1729 \times 10 + 3 &:= 1^3 + 2^3 + 7^3 + 13^3 + 16^3 + 22^3 \\ &:= 1^3 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 13^3 + 15^3 + 22^3 \\ 1729 \times 10 + 4 &:= 5^3 + 8^3 + 10^3 + 14^3 + 17^3 + 20^3 \\ 1729 \times 10 + 5 &:= 5^3 + 9^3 + 11^3 + 13^3 + 17^3 + 20^3 \\ 1729 \times 10 + 6 &:= 6^3 + 17^3 + 23^3 \\ 1729 \times 10 + 7 &:= 9^3 + 14^3 + 24^3 \\ 1729 \times 10 + 8 &:= 1^3 + 9^3 + 14^3 + 24^3 \\ &:= 2^3 + 13^3 + 18^3 + 21^3 \\ 1729 \times 10 + 9 &:= 7^3 + 11^3 + 25^3,\end{aligned}$$

The last two numbers can also be written as power 4:

$$\begin{aligned}1729 \times 10 + 8 &:= 4^4 + 7^4 + 11^4 \\1729 \times 10 + 9 &:= 1^4 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 11^4.\end{aligned}$$

10.2 Second Pattern

$$\begin{aligned}10000 + 1729 &:= 1^3 + 2^3 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 22^3 \\&:= 6^3 + 9^3 + 12^3 + 13^3 + 19^3 \\20000 + 1729 &:= 1^3 + 5^3 + 16^3 + 19^3 + 22^3 \\&:= 1^3 + 10^3 + 12^3 + 15^3 + 25^3 \\&:= 4^3 + 6^3 + 12^3 + 16^3 + 25^3 \\&:= 7^3 + 13^3 + 16^3 + 18^3 + 21^3 \\30000 + 1729 &:= 1^3 + 10^3 + 13^3 + 16^3 + 19^3 + 26^3 \\&:= 3^3 + 4^3 + 10^3 + 16^3 + 19^3 + 27^3 \\&:= 6^3 + 10^3 + 13^3 + 18^3 + 19^3 + 25^3 \\40000 + 1729 &:= 2^3 + 5^3 + 15^3 + 18^3 + 20^3 + 29^3 \\&:= 2^3 + 8^3 + 11^3 + 13^3 + 17^3 + 32^3 \\&:= 8^3 + 9^3 + 17^3 + 18^3 + 23^3 + 26^3 \\50000 + 1729 &:= 5^3 + 9^3 + 20^3 + 35^3 \\&:= 14^3 + 17^3 + 27^3 + 29^3 \\60000 + 1729 &:= 6^3 + 12^3 + 17^3 + 38^3 \\&:= 6^3 + 20^3 + 26^3 + 33^3 \\70000 + 1729 &:= 4^3 + 14^3 + 41^3 \\80000 + 1729 &:= 10^3 + 12^3 + 17^3 + 42^3 \\90000 + 1729 &:= 9^3 + 30^3 + 40^3.\end{aligned}$$

The last two numbers can also be written as power 4:

$$\begin{aligned}80000 + 1729 &:= 4^4 + 6^4 + 11^4 + 16^4 \\90000 + 1729 &:= 4^4 + 6^4 + 10^4 + 11^4 + 16^4.\end{aligned}$$

11 Functional Representations

This deals with representations of **1729** in two different ways. One in terms of Fibonacci sequence values. Second as particular cases of *s-sides of polygons*.

11.1 Fibonacci Sequences

$$F(0) = F(1) = 1, F(n) = F(n-1) + F(n-2), n \geq 2, \\ 0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, ..$$

Then,

$$1729 := F(2) + F(6) + F(9) + F(11) + F(17)$$

11.2 S-gonol Values

The general formula for **s-sides of a polygon (s-gonal)** is known as

$$P_s(n) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2. \quad (1)$$

Below are particular cases:

Triangle (3-gonal): $P_3(n) = n(n+1)/2 \rightarrow 1729 := P_3(26) + P_3(52)$
Square (4-gonal): $P_4(n) = n^2 \rightarrow 1729 := P_4(6) + P_4(18) + P_4(37)$
Pentagonal (5-gonal): $P_5(n) = n(3n-1)/2 \rightarrow 1729 := P_5(3) + P_5(34)$
Hexagonal (6-gonal): $P_6(n) = n(2n-1) \rightarrow 1729 := P_6(9) + P_6(18) + P_6(22)$
Heptagonal (7-gonal): $P_7(n) = n(5n-3)/2 \rightarrow 1729 := P_7(9) + P_7(14) + P_7(21)$
Octagonal (8-gonal): $P_8(n) = n(3n-2) \rightarrow 1729 := P_8(4) + P_8(12) + P_8(21)$
Nonagonal (9-gonal): $P_9(n) = n(7n-5)/2 \rightarrow 1729 := P_9(1) + P_9(2) + P_9(15) + P_9(17)$
Decagonal (10-gonal): $P_{10}(n) = n(4n-3) \rightarrow 1729 := P_{10}(1) + P_{10}(3) + P_{10}(21)$
Hendecagonal (11-gonal): $P_{11}(n) = n(9n-7)/2 \rightarrow 1729 := P_{11}(1) + P_{11}(9) + P_{11}(18)$

Calculating further values, the exact values are for 12-gonal, 24-gonal and 84-gonal. See below:

12-gonal: $P_{12}(n) = n(5n-4) \rightarrow 1729 := P_{12}(19)$
24-gonal: $P_{24}(n) = n(11n-10) \rightarrow 1729 := P_{24}(13)$
84-gonal: $P_{84}(n) = n(41n-40) \rightarrow 1729 := P_{84}(7)$.

Interestingly, 7, 13 and 19 are the *multiplicative factors* of **1729**.

In case of *decagonal (10-gonal)*, Ramanujan proved that

$$1^3 + 3^3 \times \frac{n-1}{n+1} + 5^3 \times \frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{(n+1)(n+2)} + 7^3 \times \frac{(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)}{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)} + \dots = n(4n-3).$$

<https://oeis.org/A001107>

11.3 Centered Polygonal Numbers

Below are representations of 1729 based on **centered polyon numbers**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= C_3(1) + C_3(2) + C_3(13) + C_3(32). \\
 &:= C_4(1) + C_4(2) + C_4(3) + C_4(7) + C_4(29). \\
 &:= C_5(1) + C_5(2) + C_5(14) + C_5(23). \\
 &:= C_6(1) + C_6(2) + C_6(3) + C_6(4) + C_6(5) + C_6(9) + C_6(22). \\
 &:= C_7(1) + C_7(2) + C_7(3) + C_7(4) + C_7(5) + C_7(9) + C_7(20). \\
 &:= C_8(1) + C_8(2) + C_8(3) + C_8(4) + C_8(5) + C_8(6) + C_8(9) + \\
 &\quad + C_8(12) + C_8(13). \\
 &:= C_{11}(7) + C_{11}(17). \\
 &:= C_{14}(1) + C_{14}(2) + C_{14}(3) + C_{14}(5) + C_{14}(6) + C_{14}(8) + C_{14}(12). \\
 &:= C_{15}(1) + C_{15}(2) + C_{15}(9) + C_{13}(13).
 \end{aligned}$$

The **centered polygonal numbers** are defined as

$$C_k(n) := \frac{kn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad k > 2$$

(<http://www.virtuescience.com/centered-polygonal.html>)

12 Special Value Numbers

12.1 Carmichael number

This section deals with the value of **1729** in different forms. These values are obtained in different situations with different kind of sequence values. All the values given here are already study previous by different authors as specified in each subsection.

Considering Carmichael (Charmick, 1939) numbers of the form

$$(6n + 1)(12n + 1)(18n + 1)$$

where $6n + 1$, $12n + 1$ and $18n + 1$ are primes, then

$$1729 := 7 \times 13 \times 19$$

*J. Chernick (1939), On Fermat's simple theorem,
 Bull. Amer. Math. Soc. **45**: 269-274
<https://oeis.org/A033502>*

Also, Carmichael numbers of the form

$$(6n + 1)(12n + 1)(18n + 1)$$

are known as *Zeisel numbers*.

<https://oeis.org/A051015>.

12.2 Centered cube number

Centered cube numbers are defined as

$$C(n) := n^3 + (n + 1)^3 = (2n + 1) \times (n^2 + n + 1), \quad n \geq 0$$

This gives

$$1729 = C(9) := 9^3 + 10^3$$

<https://oeis.org/A005898>

12.3 Generalized Heptagonal (7-gonal)

Generalized heptagonal number is defined as

$$G_7(n) = n(5n - 3)/2, \quad n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$$

This gives

$$1729 := G_7(-6)$$

<https://oeis.org/A085787>

12.4 Third Spoke of a Hexagonal Spiral

Third spoke of a hexagonal spiral is defined as

$$M(n) := 3n^2 + 1, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

This gives

$$1729 := M(24)$$

<https://oeis.org/A056107>

13 Stair-Type Formula

This sections deals with triangular values written in such way that it brings sum in deslocating sequences after each two values, and then summing them. For all $n > 2$, $S(1) = 0$, $S(2) = 1$, we have

$$S(n) := S(n-2) + \frac{n(n-1)}{2}$$

$$:= \frac{4n^3 + 6n^2 - 4n + 3(-1)^n - 3}{48}$$

This gives

$$1729 := S(27)$$

The "stair-type values" are given by

1					1
3					3
6	1				7
10	3				13
15	6	1			22
21	10	3			34
28	15	6	1		50
36	21	10	3		70
45	28	15	6	1	95
...	...	...	...	...	...

<https://oeis.org/A002623>

This idea of *stair-type* numbers can be applied to other functions given in Section 11.2. This shell be dealt elsewhere.

14 Selfie-Fractions

Selfie numbers are understood as numbers having their representations with same digits or reverse with some operations. For examples,

$$26364 = 26^3 \times 6/4$$

$$34425 = 3^4 \times 425$$

$$35721 = 3^5 \times 7 \times 21.$$

The above examples are with multiplication, division and exponential. There are lot of numbers this kind with more operations. See the reference at the end of this work. The same kind of idea can be applied to fractions, where then numerators and denominators are with same digits as of fractions separated by basic operations. Below are some examples containing the numbers **1729** either in numerator or in denominator.

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1729} = \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(17+2) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{8463} = \frac{1+7+2+9}{84+6+3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{546}{1729} = \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(17+2) \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{6384} = \frac{1+7 \times (2+9)}{(6+3) \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{4368} = \frac{1+7+2+9}{4+36+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{58604} = \frac{1+7+2+9}{5 \times 8 + 604}$$

14.1 Equivalent Selfie Fractions

Above we have written only one selfie representation for each fraction, but there are many fraction those have more than one "selfie-representation". This we shall call as "equivalent selfie fraction. Below are some of these having the number **1729** in the numerator.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{3458} &= \frac{17+29}{34+58} = \frac{17-29}{34-58} = \frac{17+2+9}{3+45+8} = \frac{1+7+2 \times 9}{3 \times 4+5 \times 8} \\ &= \frac{17+2 \times 9}{3 \times 4+58} = \frac{1+7+29}{34+5 \times 8} = \frac{1 \times 7 \times 29}{(3+4) \times 58} = \frac{1+7 \times (2+9)}{3 \times 4 \times (5+8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{3640} = \frac{(17+2) \times 9}{(3+6) \times 40} = \frac{1+7+2+9}{36+4+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{5460} = \frac{(17+2) \times 9}{(5+4) \times 60} = \frac{1+7+2+9}{54+6+0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{8645} &= \frac{1 \times 7 + 2 + 9}{(8+6+4) \times 5} = \frac{1+7+2+9}{86+4+5} = \frac{1+7 \times 2+9}{8 \times (6+4+5)} \\ &= \frac{(1+7+2) \times 9}{(86+4) \times 5} = \frac{1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9}{(8+6) \times 45} = \frac{1^7 \times 2^9}{8 \times 64 \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

15 Equivalent Fractions

Above Section give selfie fractions with the property that there are same digits at numerator and denominators. But there are fractions that are equivalent to each other without use of the basic operations such as $\frac{1}{2} = \frac{2}{4}$, $\frac{2}{3} = \frac{6}{9}$, etc. Below are some equivalent fractions with the digits **1729** in the numerator. Initially are few with triple representations and then with double representations.

15.1 Triple Representations

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{38456} = \frac{3458}{76912} = \frac{4368}{97152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{53846} = \frac{1267}{39458} = \frac{2534}{78916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{45836} = \frac{1976}{52384} = \frac{3458}{91672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{308465} = \frac{2639}{470815} = \frac{5278}{941630}$$

15.2 Double Representations

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{34586} = \frac{3458}{69172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{48563} = \frac{3458}{97126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{348605} = \frac{3458}{697210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{34856} = \frac{3458}{69712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{304586} = \frac{3458}{609172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{350648} = \frac{3458}{701296}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{35648} = \frac{3458}{71296}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{304856} = \frac{3458}{609712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{350846} = \frac{3458}{701692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{35846} = \frac{3458}{71692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{305486} = \frac{3458}{610972}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{354608} = \frac{3458}{709216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{36458} = \frac{3458}{72916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{305864} = \frac{4921}{870536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{354806} = \frac{3458}{709612}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{43586} = \frac{2457}{61938}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{306485} = \frac{3458}{612970}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{356048} = \frac{3458}{712096}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{45638} = \frac{3458}{91276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{308546} = \frac{3458}{617092}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{358046} = \frac{3458}{716092}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{45863} = \frac{3458}{91726}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{308645} = \frac{3458}{617290}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{360458} = \frac{3458}{720916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{46358} = \frac{3458}{92716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{345086} = \frac{3458}{690172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{360548} = \frac{3458}{721096}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{46835} = \frac{2639}{71485}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{346085} = \frac{3458}{692170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{360845} = \frac{3458}{721690}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{48356} = \frac{3458}{96712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{348506} = \frac{3458}{697012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{364508} = \frac{3458}{729016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{364805} = \frac{3458}{729610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{456038} = \frac{3458}{912076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{480635} = \frac{3458}{961270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{380456} = \frac{3458}{760912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{458036} = \frac{3458}{916072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{483506} = \frac{3458}{967012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{380546} = \frac{3458}{761092}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{458603} = \frac{3458}{917206}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{483605} = \frac{3458}{967210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{380645} = \frac{3458}{761290}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{460358} = \frac{3458}{920716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{485063} = \frac{3458}{970126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{384506} = \frac{3458}{769012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{460538} = \frac{3458}{921076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{485306} = \frac{3458}{970612}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{384605} = \frac{3458}{769210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{460835} = \frac{3458}{921670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{485603} = \frac{3458}{971206}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{450638} = \frac{3458}{901276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{460853} = \frac{3458}{921706}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{486053} = \frac{3458}{972106}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{450836} = \frac{3458}{901672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{463085} = \frac{3458}{926170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{486305} = \frac{3458}{972610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{450863} = \frac{3458}{901726}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{463508} = \frac{3458}{927016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{540683} = \frac{1792}{560384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{453086} = \frac{3458}{906172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{463805} = \frac{3458}{927610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{568043} = \frac{1092}{358764}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{453608} = \frac{3458}{907216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{480356} = \frac{3458}{960712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{605834} = \frac{1365}{478290}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{453806} = \frac{3458}{907612}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{480536} = \frac{3458}{961072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{643058} = \frac{1064}{395728}$$

16 Pythagorean Triples and Patterns

16.1 Pythagorean Triples With 1729

$$\begin{array}{ll} 665^2+1596^2 := 1729^2 & 1729^2+11172^2 := 11305^2 \\ 1729^2+672^2 := 1855^2 & 1729^2+16380^2 := 16471^2 \\ 1729^2+1140^2 := 2071^2 & 1729^2+78660^2 := 78679^2 \\ 1729^2+2028^2 := 2665^2 & 1729^2+30480^2 := 30529^2 \\ 1729^2+3960^2 := 4321^2 & 1729^2+114972^2 := 114985^2 \\ 1729^2+5928^2 := 6175^2 & 1729^2+213528^2 := 213535^2 \\ 1729^2+8760^2 := 8929^2 & 1729^2+1494720^2 := 1494721^2 \end{array}$$

16.1.1 Blocks of 10 and 100

$$\begin{array}{ll} 1729 0^2+74736024^2 := 74736026^2 & 1729 5^2+149558512^2 := 149558513^2 \\ 1729 1^2+149489340^2 := 149489341^2 & 1729 6^2+74787903^2 := 74787905^2 \\ 1729 2^2+74753315^2 := 74753317^2 & 1729 7^2+149593104^2 := 149593105^2 \\ 1729 3^2+149523924^2 := 149523925^2 & 1729 8^2+74805200^2 := 74805202^2 \\ 1729 4^2+74770608^2 := 74770610^2 & 1729 9^2+149627700^2 := 149627701^2 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll} 1729 00^2+7473602499^2 := 7473602501^2 & 1729 19^2+14950490280^2 := 14950490281^2 \\ 1729 01^2+14947377900^2 := 14947377901^2 & 1729 20^2+7475331599^2 := 7475331601^2 \\ 1729 02^2+7473775400^2 := 7473775402^2 & 1729 21^2+14950836120^2 := 14950836121^2 \\ 1729 03^2+14947723704^2 := 14947723705^2 & 1729 22^2+7475504520^2 := 7475504522^2 \\ 1729 04^2+7473948303^2 := 7473948305^2 & 1729 23^2+14951181964^2 := 14951181965^2 \\ 1729 05^2+14948069512^2 := 14948069513^2 & 1729 24^2+7475677443^2 := 7475677445^2 \\ 1729 06^2+7474121208^2 := 7474121210^2 & 1729 25^2+14951527812^2 := 14951527813^2 \\ 1729 07^2+14948415324^2 := 14948415325^2 & 1729 26^2+7475850368^2 := 7475850370^2 \\ 1729 08^2+7474294115^2 := 7474294117^2 & 1729 27^2+14951873664^2 := 14951873665^2 \\ 1729 09^2+14948761140^2 := 14948761141^2 & 1729 28^2+7476023295^2 := 7476023297^2 \\ 1729 10^2+7474467024^2 := 7474467026^2 & 1729 29^2+14952219520^2 := 14952219521^2 \\ 1729 11^2+14949106960^2 := 14949106961^2 & 1729 30^2+7476196224^2 := 7476196226^2 \\ 1729 12^2+7474639935^2 := 7474639937^2 & 1729 31^2+14952565380^2 := 14952565381^2 \\ 1729 13^2+14949452784^2 := 14949452785^2 & 1729 32^2+7476369155^2 := 7476369157^2 \\ 1729 14^2+7474812848^2 := 7474812850^2 & 1729 33^2+14952911244^2 := 14952911245^2 \\ 1729 15^2+14949798612^2 := 14949798613^2 & 1729 34^2+7476542088^2 := 7476542090^2 \\ 1729 16^2+7474985763^2 := 7474985765^2 & 1729 35^2+14953257112^2 := 14953257113^2 \\ 1729 17^2+14950144444^2 := 14950144445^2 & 1729 36^2+7476715023^2 := 7476715025^2 \\ 1729 18^2+7475158680^2 := 7475158682^2 & 1729 37^2+14953602984^2 := 14953602985^2 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1729 \ 38^2+7476887960^2 &:= 7476887962^2 \\ 1729 \ 39^2+14953948860^2 &:= 14953948861^2 \\ 1729 \ 40^2+7477060899^2 &:= 7477060901^2 \\ 1729 \ 41^2+14954294740^2 &:= 14954294741^2 \\ 1729 \ 42^2+7477233840^2 &:= 7477233842^2 \\ 1729 \ 43^2+14954640624^2 &:= 14954640625^2 \\ 1729 \ 44^2+7477406783^2 &:= 7477406785^2 \\ 1729 \ 45^2+14954986512^2 &:= 14954986513^2 \\ 1729 \ 46^2+7477579728^2 &:= 7477579730^2 \\ 1729 \ 47^2+14955332404^2 &:= 14955332405^2 \\ 1729 \ 48^2+7477752675^2 &:= 7477752677^2 \\ 1729 \ 49^2+14955678300^2 &:= 14955678301^2 \\ 1729 \ 50^2+7477925624^2 &:= 7477925626^2 \\ 1729 \ 51^2+14956024200^2 &:= 14956024201^2 \\ 1729 \ 52^2+7478098575^2 &:= 7478098577^2 \\ 1729 \ 53^2+14956370104^2 &:= 14956370105^2 \\ 1729 \ 54^2+7478271528^2 &:= 7478271530^2 \\ 1729 \ 55^2+14956716012^2 &:= 14956716013^2 \\ 1729 \ 56^2+7478444483^2 &:= 7478444485^2 \\ 1729 \ 57^2+14957061924^2 &:= 14957061925^2 \\ 1729 \ 58^2+7478617440^2 &:= 7478617442^2 \\ 1729 \ 59^2+14957407840^2 &:= 14957407841^2 \\ 1729 \ 60^2+7478790399^2 &:= 7478790401^2 \\ 1729 \ 61^2+14957753760^2 &:= 14957753761^2 \\ 1729 \ 62^2+7478963360^2 &:= 7478963362^2 \\ 1729 \ 63^2+14958099684^2 &:= 14958099685^2 \\ 1729 \ 64^2+7479136323^2 &:= 7479136325^2 \\ 1729 \ 65^2+14958445612^2 &:= 14958445613^2 \\ 1729 \ 66^2+7479309288^2 &:= 7479309290^2 \\ 1729 \ 67^2+14958791544^2 &:= 14958791545^2 \\ 1729 \ 68^2+7479482255^2 &:= 7479482257^2 \\ 1729 \ 69^2+14959137480^2 &:= 14959137481^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1729 \ 70^2+7479655224^2 &:= 7479655226^2 \\ 1729 \ 71^2+14959483420^2 &:= 14959483421^2 \\ 1729 \ 72^2+7479828195^2 &:= 7479828197^2 \\ 1729 \ 73^2+14959829364^2 &:= 14959829365^2 \\ 1729 \ 74^2+7480001168^2 &:= 7480001170^2 \\ 1729 \ 75^2+14960175312^2 &:= 14960175313^2 \\ 1729 \ 76^2+7480174143^2 &:= 7480174145^2 \\ 1729 \ 77^2+14960521264^2 &:= 14960521265^2 \\ 1729 \ 78^2+7480347120^2 &:= 7480347122^2 \\ 1729 \ 79^2+14960867220^2 &:= 14960867221^2 \\ 1729 \ 80^2+7480520099^2 &:= 7480520101^2 \\ 1729 \ 81^2+14961213180^2 &:= 14961213181^2 \\ 1729 \ 82^2+7480693080^2 &:= 7480693082^2 \\ 1729 \ 83^2+14961559144^2 &:= 14961559145^2 \\ 1729 \ 84^2+7480866063^2 &:= 7480866065^2 \\ 1729 \ 85^2+14961905112^2 &:= 14961905113^2 \\ 1729 \ 86^2+7481039048^2 &:= 7481039050^2 \\ 1729 \ 87^2+14962251084^2 &:= 14962251085^2 \\ 1729 \ 88^2+7481212035^2 &:= 7481212037^2 \\ 1729 \ 89^2+14962597060^2 &:= 14962597061^2 \\ 1729 \ 90^2+7481385024^2 &:= 7481385026^2 \\ 1729 \ 91^2+14962943040^2 &:= 14962943041^2 \\ 1729 \ 92^2+7481558015^2 &:= 7481558017^2 \\ 1729 \ 93^2+14963289024^2 &:= 14963289025^2 \\ 1729 \ 94^2+7481731008^2 &:= 7481731010^2 \\ 1729 \ 95^2+14963635012^2 &:= 14963635013^2 \\ 1729 \ 96^2+7481904003^2 &:= 7481904005^2 \\ 1729 \ 97^2+14963981004^2 &:= 14963981005^2 \\ 1729 \ 98^2+7482077000^2 &:= 7482077002^2 \\ 1729 \ 99^2+14964327000^2 &:= 14964327001^2 \end{aligned}$$

16.2 Pandigital Type Patterns With 1729

16.2.1 Patterns With 1729

$$13271^2 + 166200^2 := 166729^2$$

$$1288271^2 + 16662000^2 := 1671 \mathbf{1729}^2$$

$$128438271^2 + 1666620000^2 := 167156 \mathbf{1729}^2$$

$$\mathbf{1729} 0^2 + 74736024^2 := 74736026^2$$

$$\mathbf{1729} 00^2 + 7473602499^2 := 7473602501^2$$

$$\mathbf{1729} 000^2 + 747360249999^2 := 747360250001^2$$

$$\mathbf{1729} 0000^2 + 74736024999999^2 := 74736025000001^2$$

$$8318^2 + \mathbf{1729} 7280^2 := \mathbf{1729} 7282$$

$$83180^2 + \mathbf{1729} 728099^2 := \mathbf{1729} 728101$$

16.2.2 Pandigital Type Patterns

$$0270684^2 + 1708000^2 := \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{12} 0270684^2 + 18788000^2 := \mathbf{12} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{1232} 0270684^2 + 189588000^2 := \mathbf{1232} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{123432} 0270684^2 + 1897588000^2 := \mathbf{123432} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{12345432} 0270684^2 + 18977588000^2 := \mathbf{12345432} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{1234565432} 0270684^2 + 189777588000^2 := \mathbf{1234565432} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{123456765432} 0270684^2 + 1897777588000^2 := \mathbf{123456765432} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{12345678765432} 0270684^2 + 18977777588000^2 := \mathbf{12345678765432} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{1234567898765432} 0270684^2 + 189777777588000^2 := \mathbf{1234567898765432} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$0270684^2 + 1708000^2 := \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{1020} 0270684^2 + 172508000^2 := \mathbf{1020} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{10203020} 0270684^2 + 17252508000^2 := \mathbf{10203020} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{102030403020} 0270684^2 + 1725252508000^2 := \mathbf{102030403020} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{1020304050403020} 0270684^2 + 172525252508000^2 := \mathbf{1020304050403020} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{10203040506050403020} 0270684^2 + 17252525252508000^2 := \mathbf{10203040506050403020} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{102030405060706050403020} 0270684^2 + 1725252525252508000^2 := \mathbf{102030405060706050403020} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} 0270684^2 + 172525252525252508000^2 := \mathbf{1020304050607080706050403020} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} 0270684^2 + 17252525252525252508000^2 := \mathbf{10203040506070809080706050403020} \mathbf{1729} 316^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &0267264^2 + 1712000^2 && := 1732736^2 \\
 &1020\ 0267264^2 + 1729\ 12000^2 && := 1020\ 1732736^2 \\
 &10203020\ 0267264^2 + 1729\ 2912000^2 && := 10203020\ 1732736^2 \\
 &102030403020\ 0267264^2 + 1729\ 292912000^2 && := 102030403020\ 1732736^2 \\
 &1020304050403020\ 0267264^2 + 1729\ 29292912000^2 && := 1020304050403020\ 1732736^2 \\
 &10203040506050403020\ 0267264^2 + 1729\ 2929292912000^2 && := 10203040506050403020\ 1732736^2 \\
 &102030405060706050403020\ 0267264^2 + 1729\ 292929292912000^2 && := 102030405060706050403020\ 1732736^2 \\
 &1020304050607080706050403020\ 0267264^2 + 1729\ 29292929292912000^2 && := 1020304050607080706050403020\ 1732736^2 \\
 &10203040506070809080706050403020\ 0267264^2 + 1729\ 2929292929292912000^2 && := 10203040506070809080706050403020\ 1732736^2
 \end{aligned}$$

17 Upside Down and Mirror Looking

It is well known that the digits 0, 1 and 8 are always mirror looking and upside down. The digits 6 and 9 are only upside down but not mirror looking. If we write 2 and 5 in digital ways as appears in lifts, watches, etc., then they becomes upside down and mirror looking. The only difference is that in case of mirror looking 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2. Some studies in this direction can be seen in author's work. Later Macau Post Office, China produced a stamp on this work.

<https://bit.ly/30PVM7y>
<https://bit.ly/3F1FEtn>

Below are some representations of **1729** upside down and mirror looking.

17.1 Upside Down

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= 1001 + 619 + 101 + 8 \\
 &:= 1 + 2 + 5 + 6 + 9 + 1691 + 6 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

See below the images:

17.2 Upside Down and Mirror Looking

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= 1001 + 512 + 215 + 1 \\
 &:= 818 + 808 + 81 + 18 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 \\
 &:= 818 + 818 + 88 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 \\
 &:= 1111 + (1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (101 + 11 + 11) + 1 + 1 + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

See below the images:

$$1001+512+215+1$$

$$818+808+81+18+1+1+1+1$$

$$818+818+88+1+1+1+1+1$$

$$1111+(1+1+1+1+1) \times (101+11+11)+1+1+1$$

In case of 2 and 5, the numbers are written in digital form. Looking in mirror, 2 becomes 5 and 5 becomes 2.

18 Prime Numbers with Digits 1, 2, 7, 9

Below are prime numbers obtained from the digits of **1729** without repetition.

17, 29, 71, 127, 179, 197, 271, 719, 971, 2917, 7219, 9721

19 Palindromic Representation

The number **1729**271 is palindrome made from the digits of **1729**. The representation below is in terms of digits of this palindrome.

$$1729 := 1 + 72 \times (9 \times 2 + 7 - 1).$$

20 Multiplicative Factors

It is well known that

$$1729 := 13 \times 133 = 7 \times 13 \times 19$$

The representations below are in terms of multiplicative factors using the digit in order of **1729** and reverse 9271.

$$1729 := (1 + 7 + 2 + \sqrt{9}) \times ((\sqrt{9})! + 2^7 - 1)$$

$$:= ((1 + 7) \times 2 - 9) \times (1 + 7 + 2 + \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 7 + 2 + 9).$$

21 Special Digits

Two date are very important. Once date of birth and second date of death of S. Ramanujan. The **1729** is written in terms of both of these dates in increasing order.

21.1 Birth Day: 22.12.1887

$$1729 := (-2 + 21) \times (-2 - 1 + 8 + 8) \times 7$$

21.2 Death Day: 26.04.1920

$$1729 := -(2 + 60) \times 4 + 1 \times (-9 + 2 + 0)$$

21.3 Four Color Representations

Below are two different ways of representing the above two dates using different colors:

22 Running Equality Expressions

By running expressions we understand as when the numbers are used in a sequence 1 to 9 and 9 to 1 or 9 to 0. The vaules appearing in between are separated by equality sign, for example,

$$\begin{aligned}
 120 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3)! &= 4 + 5!/6 + 7 + 89 \\
 &:= 98 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 = (3 + 2)! \times 1 \\
 &:= \sqrt{9} + 87 + 6 \times 5 &= \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times 2 \times 10.
 \end{aligned}$$

In case of **1729** we are unable to write as above. Extra operations like, **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular number** values are used.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= -1 + T(-2 + T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) &= T(5) + 6 + 7 + T(T(8)) + T(T(9)) \\
 &:= 12^3 - 4 + 5 &= T(6) + 7 + T(T(8)) + T(T(9)) \\
 &:= F(12) \times 3 \times 4 - 5 + 6 &= T(7) + T(T(8)) + T(T(9)) \\
 &:= 12^3 - T(4) + 5 + 6 &= T(7) + T(T(8)) + T(T(9)) \\
 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(7)) + T(T(6)) + T(5) &= T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(3)) - 2)) - 1 \\
 &:= 98 + 7 \times F(F(6) + 5) &= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(3)) + 210 \\
 &:= T(T(9)) + T(T(8)) + 7 + T(6) &= 54 \times 32 + 1 \\
 &:= T(T(9)) + T(T(8)) + T(7) &= -6 \times 5 + T(T(4)) \times 32 - 1 \\
 & &= F(6) \times 54 \times F(3) \times 2 + 1 \\
 & &= -65 + 43^2 - F(10).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= (F(1) - F(6)) \times (F(3) - F(8)) \times F(7) = T(1) + (T(6) + T(3)) \times (T(8) + T(7)) \\
 &:= (-F(1) + F(6) \times F(8) - F(9)) \times F(7) = T(1) \times T(6) \times (T(8) + T(9)) + T(7) \\
 &:= (-F(1) - F(9) + F(8) \times F(6)) \times F(7) = (T(1) \times T(9) + T(8)) \times T(6) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

22.1 Increasing and Decreasing

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= T(9) + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4 &= (F(F(4)) + 5) \times (F(6) + F(F(7))) + 8 + F(9) \\
 & &= 4 - T(56) + T(T(7)) + 8 + T(9) \\
 &:= 12^3 - 4 + 5 &= 5! \times T(4) + T(32) + 1 \\
 &:= 12^3 + (-4 + 5)^6 &= T(F(6) + 5 \times T(4)) - 3 + 21 \\
 & &= (F(6) + 5) \times (T(4!) - F(3!)) - 2 - 1 \times 0! \\
 &:= 123 \times (4 \times 5 - 6) + 7 &= F(7) \times (6 + (5 - F(4)) \times 3 \times 21 + 0!) \\
 &:= T(12) + 3 - 4 + 56 + T(7 \times 8) &= 876 + F(T(5)) + 4 \times 3 + T(21) \\
 & &= \sqrt{\sqrt{87} - 6} + 54 \times 32 - 1 - 0! \\
 &:= 12 - 3 + 4^5 - 6 + 78 \times 9 &= (9 \times F(8) + 7 + T(F(6))) \times 5 \times 4 - 3! + T(21) \\
 & &= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6 + (5 \times 4 \times F(3)) \times (2 + 1)! + 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

23 Selfie Representations

In Sections 11 we have given the idea of selfie numbers and selfie fractions. More detailed study can be seen at author's work given reference list. Here we have written the number **1729** as selfie number by using difference sequence values, such as, **Fibonacci, Triangular, Polygon-type**, etc.

23.1 Fibonacci and Triangular

Below are selfie representation of **1729** in terms of Fibonacci sequence and Triangular values in order of digits and reverse.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= 1 + (F(7) - F(2))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 &:= T(-1 + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(F(9)) \\
 &:= 9!/T\left(\sqrt{-T(T(2)) + T(T(7))}\right) + 1 \\
 &:= T(F(9)) + T(2) \times T(T(7) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

23.2 Polygonal-Type

According to **s-ogonal** values given in subsection 11.2, below are selfie representations of **1729**:

23.2.1 Digit's Order

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (P_4(P_4(P_4(2))) - 9) \\
 &:= 1 + (7 + P_5(2))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 &:= 1 \times P_7\left(\sqrt{P_7(7) \times P_7(2)}\right) - P_7(9) \\
 &:= 1 \times P_8(7) \times (-P_8(2) + P_8(\sqrt{9})) \\
 &:= 1 + 72 \times P_9(\sqrt{9}) \\
 &:= -1 - P_{10}(7 + P_{10}(2)) + P_{10}(P_{10}(\sqrt{9})) \\
 &:= -1^7 + P_{11}(P_{11}(2) + 9) \\
 &:= P_{12}(1 + 7 + 2 + 9) \\
 &:= P_{24}(-1 + 7 - 2 + 9) \\
 &:= P_{84}((1 + 7) \times 2 - 9).
 \end{aligned}$$

23.2.2 Reverse Order of Digits

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} &:= (-9 + P_4(P_4(P_4(2)))) \times 7 \times 1 \\
 &:= P_5(\sqrt{9}) + P_5(P_5(2) \times 7 - 1) \\
 &:= -P_7(9) + P_7(27 + 1) \\
 &:= P_8(9) \times P_8(2) - 71 \\
 &:= P_9(\sqrt{9}) \times (P_9(2))! / 7! + 1 \\
 &:= P_{10}(P_{10}(\sqrt{9})) - P_{10}(P_{10}(2) + 7) - 1 \\
 &:= P_{11}(9) + P_{11}(P_{11}(2) + 7) + 1 \\
 &:= P_{12}(9 + 2 + 7 + 1) \\
 &:= P_{24}(9 - 2 + 7 - 1) \\
 &:= P_{84}(-9 + 2 \times (7 + 1)).
 \end{aligned}$$

Combining the results given above with given in Subsection 11.2, we have following unified values:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1729} &:= P_{12}(19) = P_{12}(1 + 7 + 2 + 9) = P_{12}(9 + 2 + 7 + 1) \\
 &:= P_{24}(13) = P_{24}(-1 + 7 - 2 + 9) = P_{24}(9 - 2 + 7 - 1) \\
 &:= P_{84}(7) = P_{84}((1 + 7) \times 2 - 9) = P_{84}(-9 + 2 \times (7 + 1)).
 \end{aligned}$$

24 Fixed Digits Repetitions Prime Patterns

This section deals with patterns with prime numbers with **1729**. These patterns are considered in such a way that after second prime number there is fixed digit or digits repeats in subsequent primes. But the approach don't go much longer. Below are examples of patterns of 6, 7 and 8 prime numbers, i.e., 6-patterns, 7-patterns and 8-patterns respectively. These patterns are always with **1729**. The detailed work shall be given elsewhere.

24.1 6-Patterns

▶ **2611729**

261 0 **1729**

261 0 0 **1729**

261 0 0 0 **1729**

261 0 0 0 0 **1729**

261 0 0 0 0 0 **1729**

▶ **172987**

939 **172987**

939 939 **172987**

939 939 939 **172987**

939 939 939 939 **172987**

939 939 939 939 939 **172987**

▶ **1017293**

87 **1017293**

87 87 **1017293**

87 87 87 **1017293**

87 87 87 87 **1017293**

87 87 87 87 87 **1017293**

▶ **1017299**

1 435 **017299**

1 435 435 **017299**

1 435 435 435 **017299**

1 435 435 435 435 **017299**

1 435 435 435 435 435 **017299**

▶ **2371729**

237 99 **1729**

237 99 99 **1729**

237 99 99 99 **1729**

237 99 99 99 99 **1729**

237 99 99 99 99 99 **1729**

▶ **1217299**

861 **1217299**

861 861 **1217299**

861 861 861 **1217299**

861 861 861 861 **1217299**

861 861 861 861 861 **1217299**

▶ **172973**

17297 444 3

17297 444 444 3

17297 444 444 444 3

17297 444 444 444 444 3

17297 444 444 444 444 444 3

▶ 1531729

15 348 31729
15 348 348 31729
15 348 348 348 31729
15 348 348 348 348 31729
15 348 348 348 348 348 31729

▶ 1531729

153 483 1729
153 483 483 1729
153 483 483 483 1729
153 483 483 483 483 1729
153 483 483 483 483 483 1729

▶ 1729237

954 1729237
954 954 1729237
954 954 954 1729237
954 954 954 954 1729237
954 954 954 954 954 1729237

▶ 1729477

172947 966 7
172947 966 966 7
172947 966 966 966 7
172947 966 966 966 966 7
172947 966 966 966 966 966 7

▶ 1729493

519 1729493
519 519 1729493
519 519 519 1729493
519 519 519 519 1729493
519 519 519 519 519 1729493

▶ 1729543

1729 783 543
1729 783 783 543
1729 783 783 783 543
1729 783 783 783 783 543
1729 783 783 783 783 783 543

▶ 1729723

1729 327 723
1729 327 327 723
1729 327 327 327 723
1729 327 327 327 327 723
1729 327 327 327 327 327 723

▶ 1729901

330 1729901
330 330 1729901
330 330 330 1729901
330 330 330 330 1729901
330 330 330 330 330 1729901

▶ 1729909

172990 663 9
172990 663 663 9
172990 663 663 663 9
172990 663 663 663 663 9
172990 663 663 663 663 663 9

▶ 2172901

2 576 172901
2 576 576 172901
2 576 576 576 172901
2 576 576 576 576 172901
2 576 576 576 576 576 172901

► **2172979**

789 **2172979**
789 789 **2172979**
789 789 789 **2172979**
789 789 789 789 **2172979**
789 789 789 789 789 **2172979**

► **5817293**

840 **5817293**
840 840 **5817293**
840 840 840 **5817293**
840 840 840 840 **5817293**
840 840 840 840 840 **5817293**

► **3217297**

32 450 **17297**
32 450 450 **17297**
32 450 450 450 **17297**
32 450 450 450 450 **17297**
32 450 450 450 450 450 **17297**

► **6041729**

6041729 579
6041729 579 579
6041729 579 579 579
6041729 579 579 579 579
6041729 579 579 579 579 579

► **3617293**

361729 183 3
361729 183 183 3
361729 183 183 183 3
361729 183 183 183 183 3
361729 183 183 183 183 183 3

► **6172927**

61729 723 27
61729 723 723 27
61729 723 723 723 27
61729 723 723 723 723 27
61729 723 723 723 723 723 27

► **3917297**

534 **3917297**
534 534 **3917297**
534 534 534 **3917297**
534 534 534 534 **3917297**
534 534 534 534 534 **3917297**

► **6211729**

621 219 **1729**
621 219 219 **1729**
621 219 219 219 **1729**
621 219 219 219 219 **1729**
621 219 219 219 219 219 **1729**

► **5617291**

5617291 363
5617291 363 363
5617291 363 363 363
5617291 363 363 363 363
5617291 363 363 363 363 363

► **6917299**

6 654 **917299**
6 654 654 **917299**
6 654 654 654 **917299**
6 654 654 654 654 **917299**
6 654 654 654 654 654 **917299**

► 6917299

691729 948 9
691729 948 948 9
691729 948 948 948 9
691729 948 948 948 948 9
691729 948 948 948 948 948 9

► 6917299

6917299 489
6917299 489 489
6917299 489 489 489
6917299 489 489 489 489
6917299 489 489 489 489 489

► 7051729

70 186 51729
70 186 186 51729
70 186 186 186 51729
70 186 186 186 186 51729
70 186 186 186 186 186 51729

► 7617293

7 963 617293
7 963 963 617293
7 963 963 963 617293
7 963 963 963 963 617293
7 963 963 963 963 963 617293

► 8101729

810 660 1729
810 660 660 1729
810 660 660 660 1729
810 660 660 660 660 1729
810 660 660 660 660 660 1729

► 8172911

817291 840 1
817291 840 840 1
817291 840 840 840 1
817291 840 840 840 840 1
817291 840 840 840 840 840 1

► 8617291

588 8617291
588 588 8617291
588 588 588 8617291
588 588 588 588 8617291
588 588 588 588 588 8617291

► 9172957

9172957 603
9172957 603 603
9172957 603 603 603
9172957 603 603 603 603
9172957 603 603 603 603 603

► 172973

6891 172973
6891 6891 172973
6891 6891 6891 172973
6891 6891 6891 6891 172973
6891 6891 6891 6891 6891 172973

► 551729

5 3036 51729
5 3036 3036 51729
5 3036 3036 3036 51729
5 3036 3036 3036 3036 51729
5 3036 3036 3036 3036 3036 51729

▶ **611729**

611729 8151
611729 8151 8151
611729 8151 8151 8151
611729 8151 8151 8151 8151
611729 8151 8151 8151 8151 8151

▶ **931729**

93 3288 1729
93 3288 3288 1729
93 3288 3288 3288 1729
93 3288 3288 3288 3288 1729
93 3288 3288 3288 3288 3288 1729

▶ **817291**

8 9354 17291
8 9354 9354 17291
8 9354 9354 9354 17291
8 9354 9354 9354 9354 17291
8 9354 9354 9354 9354 9354 17291

24.2 7-Patterns

▶ **2251729**

225 0 1729
225 0 0 1729
225 0 0 0 1729
225 0 0 0 0 1729
225 0 0 0 0 0 1729
225 0 0 0 0 0 0 1729

▶ **73217297**

7 15 3217297
7 15 15 3217297
7 15 15 15 3217297
7 15 15 15 15 3217297
7 15 15 15 15 15 3217297
7 15 15 15 15 15 15 3217297

▶ **611729**

611729 81
611729 81 81
611729 81 81 81
611729 81 81 81 81
611729 81 81 81 81 81
611729 81 81 81 81 81 81

▶ **2671729**

267 714 1729
267 714 714 1729
267 714 714 714 1729
267 714 714 714 714 1729
267 714 714 714 714 714 1729
267 714 714 714 714 714 714 1729

▶ **3172907**

3 615 **172907**
3 615 615 **172907**
3 615 615 615 **172907**
3 615 615 615 615 **172907**
3 615 615 615 615 615 **172907**
3 615 615 615 615 615 615 **172907**

▶ **5491729**

54 234 **91729**
54 234 234 **91729**
54 234 234 234 **91729**
54 234 234 234 234 **91729**
54 234 234 234 234 234 **91729**
54 234 234 234 234 234 234 **91729**

▶ **5011729**

501 222 **1729**
501 222 222 **1729**
501 222 222 222 **1729**
501 222 222 222 222 **1729**
501 222 222 222 222 222 **1729**
501 222 222 222 222 222 222 **1729**

▶ **5651729**

5 126 65**1729**
5 126 126 65**1729**
5 126 126 126 65**1729**
5 126 126 126 126 65**1729**
5 126 126 126 126 126 65**1729**
5 126 126 126 126 126 126 65**1729**

▶ **5491729**

5 423 49**1729**
5 423 423 49**1729**
5 423 423 423 49**1729**
5 423 423 423 423 49**1729**
5 423 423 423 423 423 49**1729**
5 423 423 423 423 423 49**1729**

▶ **6317293**

631729 897 3
631729 897 897 3
631729 897 897 897 3
631729 897 897 897 897 3
631729 897 897 897 897 897 3
631729 897 897 897 897 897 897 3

24.3 8-Patterns

▶ **13172983**

1 6 **3172983**
1 6 6 **3172983**
1 6 6 6 **3172983**
1 6 6 6 6 **3172983**
1 6 6 6 6 6 **3172983**
1 6 6 6 6 6 6 **3172983**

▶ **78172993**

7 876 **8172993**
7 876 876 **8172993**
7 876 876 876 **8172993**
7 876 876 876 876 **8172993**
7 876 876 876 876 876 **8172993**
7 876 876 876 876 876 876 **8172993**

▶ 78**172993**

78 768 **172993**

78 768 768 **172993**

78 768 768 768 **172993**

78 768 768 768 768 **172993**

78 768 768 768 768 768 **172993**

78 768 768 768 768 768 768 **172993**

78 768 768 768 768 768 768 768 **172993**

▶ 9039**1729**

141 9039**1729**

141 141 9039**1729**

141 141 141 9039**1729**

141 141 141 141 9039**1729**

141 141 141 141 141 9039**1729**

141 141 141 141 141 141 9039**1729**

141 141 141 141 141 141 141 9039**1729**

25 Embedded Palindromic Prime Numbers

Embedded or Nested palindromic prime numbers are well known in literature (ref. <https://oeis.org/A158089>). In this section we have given embedded palindromic numbers in such a way that it has the number **1729**. The study is done in two different ways. One considering all the digits, and second considering only the digits 1, 7, 2 and 9. In both the situations the we have the number **1729**.

25.1 All Digits With 1729

131	
11311	191
9271131 1729	71917
339271131 172933	792719 17297
9339271131 1729339	197792719 17297791
	1197792719 172977911
131	
71317	191
1592713 172951	71917
31592713 1729513	792719 17297
331592713 17295133	92792719 1729729
	792792719 17297297
191	
71917	
3092719 172903	
73092719 1729037	
973092719 17290379	

191
71917
792719**1729**7
92792719**1729**729
992792719**1729**7299

313
9931399
7299931399927
11729993139992711
1117299931399927111

191
9919199
72991919927
17**1729**91919927171
117**1729**919199271711

787
194787491
71947874917
92719478749**1729**
992719478749**1729**9

313
93139
7299931399927
11729993139992711
1117299931399927111

797
17971
711797117
19927117971**1729**91
119927117971**1729**911

313
93139
9931399
11729993139992711
1117299931399927111

797
77977
9779779
717297797792717
17172977977927171

313
93139
9931399
7299931399927
11729993139992711
1117299931399927111

797
77977
9779779
717297797792717
97172977977927179

93139
9931399
7299931399927
11729993139992711
11**1729**9931399927111

97379
729737927
17297379271
92**1729**737927129
992**1729**7379271299

93239
9932399
199323991
92719932399**1729**
1192719932399**1729**11

97379
729737927
17297379271
95**1729**737927159
995**1729**7379271599

97379
729737927
17297379271
3**1729**73792713
113**1729**7379271311

729272927
17292729271
3**1729**27292713
93**1729**272927139
1193**1729**27292713911

97379
729737927
17297379271
3**1729**73792713
753**1729**7379271357

927**1729**
11927**1729**11
311927**1729**113
1311927**1729**1131
111311927**1729**113111

97379
729737927
17297379271
3**1729**73792713
783**1729**7379271387

313
93139
9931399
7299931399927
11729993139992711
11**1729**9931399927111

97379
729737927
17297379271
3**1729**73792713
903**1729**7379271309

25.2 Digits 1, 7, 2, 9 and 1729

9271729
9129271729219
92912927172921929
1929129271729219291
11192912927172921929111.

9271729
77927172977
917792717297719
7791779271729771977.

9271729
92927172929
1929271729291
1191929271729291911.

9271729
1179271729711
7971179271729711797
979711792717297117979.

9271729
1929271729291
1191929271729291911
979711792717297117979.

9271729
9729271729279
997292717292799
1199729271729279911.

9271729
191992717299191
1219199271729919121
712191992717299191217.

729272927
17292729271
121729272927121
11271217292729271217211.

729272927
17292729271
771729272927177
121771729272927177121.

17292129271
771729212927177
77717292129271777
927771729212927177729.

17299299271
9172992992719
71917299299271917
1719172992992719171.

72997979927
1729979799271
11172997979927111
721117299797992711127.

99172927199
9991729271999
99999172927199999
199999917292719999991.

79271117297
997927111729799
1299792711172979921
12129979271117297992121.

9271729
11927172911
1197119271729117911

9271729
9271729271729
1299271729271729921.

9271729
122192717291221
9912219271729122199

9271729
197992717299791
1919799271729979191.

971222179
7297122217927
11729712221792711.

11927172911
971192717291179
1197119271729117911.

17292729271
121729272927121
11271217292729271217211.

17299299271
9172992992719
12917299299271921.

77927172977
917792717297719
7791779271729771977.

92927172929
1929271729291
1191929271729291911.

9271191**1729**
119271191**1729**11
177119271191**1729**11771.

792719**1729**7
12792719**1729**721
11112792719**1729**721111.

25.3 More Examples

Below are three examples of embedded palprimes with **1729**. These examples are with palprimes **172909271** and **172959271**.

1.

172909271
17290009271
1729000000009271
17290000000000000000009271
1729000000000000000000000000000000009271

2.

172959271
17295555559271
1729555555559271
1729555555555555555555555555555555559271

3.

1729 5 9271
 32 **1729 5 9271 23**
 3132 **1729 5 9271 2313**
 323132 **1729 5 9271 231323**
 16323132 **1729 5 9271 23132361**
 1216323132 **1729 5 9271 2313236121**
 741216323132 **1729 5 9271 231323612147**
 72741216323132 **1729 5 9271 23132361214727**
 36172741216323132 **1729 5 9271 23132361214727163**
 1236172741216323132 **1729 5 9271 2313236121472716321**
 91236172741216323132 **1729 5 9271 23132361214727163219**
 7791236172741216323132 **1729 5 9271 2313236121472716321977**
 9037791236172741216323132 **1729 5 9271 2313236121472716321977309**
 759037791236172741216323132 **1729 5 9271 231323612147271632197730957**
 13759037791236172741216323132 **1729 5 9271 23132361214727163219773095731**

The first two examples uses extra only numbers 0 and 5. The last example is all digits except 8.

26 Magic Square Type Palprimes

This section brings magic square type **palindromic prime numbers**, sometimes called as **palprimes**, where rows, columns and principal diagonals are also **palprimes**. The embedded properties are also true. Here we have given three examples of order 7×7 , where there is symmetry in representations

1.

```

9 9 1 9 1 9 9
9 7 3 2 3 7 9
1 3 1 7 1 3 1
9 2 7 1 7 2 9
1 3 1 7 1 3 1
9 7 3 2 3 7 9
9 9 1 9 1 9 9
  
```

2.

```

9 7 1 1 1 7 9
1 7 1 2 1 7 1
9 2 1 2 1 2 9
9 2 7 1 7 2 9
9 2 1 2 1 2 9
1 7 1 2 1 7 1
9 7 1 1 1 7 9
  
```

3.

```

1 9 9 3 9 9 1
9 2 7 1 7 2 9
9 7 7 0 7 7 9
3 1 0 6 0 1 3
9 7 7 0 7 7 9
9 2 7 1 7 2 9
1 9 9 3 9 9 1
  
```

Below are **extended palprimes** of above three sets of **magic square type palprimes**:

1. 9919199 9732379 1317131 927**1729** 1317131 9732379 9919199;

2. 9711179 1712171 9212129 927**1729** 9212129 17121719 711179;
3. 1993991 927**1729** 9770779 3106013 9770779 927**1729** 1993991.

27 Palindromic Prime Numbers

Palindromic prime numbers are well known in the literature. Below are some palindromic prime numbers using only the digits of **1729**. The number **1729** appears twice in first subsection and trice in second subsection. Obviously, there are much more numbers with **1729** below are written only few.

27.1 Double 1729

927**1729**27**1729**

129927**1729**27**1729**921
772927**1729**27**1729**277
972927**1729**27**1729**279
922927**1729**27**1729**229

7221927**1729**27**1729**1227
7921927**1729**27**1729**1297
9111927**1729**27**1729**1119
9721927**1729**27**1729**1279
9277927**1729**27**1729**7729
9991927**1729**27**1729**1999

17291729127772192719271
17291729217171292719271
17291729229792292719271
17291729279797292719271
17291729727172792719271

1177927**1729**27**1729**7711
1122927**1729**27**1729**2211
1717927**1729**27**1729**7171
1719927**1729**27**1729**9171
1771927**1729**27**1729**1771

11179927**1729**27**1729**97111
11197927**1729**27**1729**79111
11212927**1729**27**1729**21211
11229927**1729**27**1729**92211
17197927**1729**27**1729**79171

17291729799199792719271
17291729911911992719271
17291729927772992719271
17291729977277992719271
17291729991719992719271

1992927**1729**27**1729**2991
7192927**1729**27**1729**2917
7777927**1729**27**1729**7777
7779927**1729**27**1729**9777
7722927**1729**27**1729**2277
7272927**1729**27**1729**2727

17722927**1729**27**1729**22771
12177927**1729**27**1729**77121
12121927**1729**27**1729**12121
12727927**1729**27**1729**72721
12279927**1729**27**1729**97221

17291172919291927119271
17291172922922927119271
17291172992729927119271
17292172911111927129271
17292172912921927129271

17292172929292927129271
1729217299999927129271
17297172929792927179271
17297172977177927179271
17299172929292927199271

17297271729192717279271
17297991729192719979271
17299711729292711799271
17299791729792719799271
17291299172927199219271

17297299271717299279271
17297929271717292979271
17299229271117292299271
17299729271917292799271
17291992711911729919271
17292292712721729229271

17291117299999271119271
17291917292729271919271
17291917297279271919271
17292917291119271929271
17297117299999271179271

17292211172927111229271
17292219172927191229271
17297221172927112279271
17297712172927121779271
17297719172927191779271

17292292717271729229271
17292792711111729729271
17292792717271729729271
17297792717171729779271
17297792717971729779271

17297717291119271779271
17297717297979271779271
17299117299199271199271
17299717291219271799271
17299917291119271999271

17297929172927192979271
17297977172927177979271
17291112927172921119271
17292122927172922129271
17292771927172917729271

17299192719291729199271
17299792711211729799271
17299992717271729999271
17291927171117172919271
17291927172727172919271

17299917291219271999271
17299917297779271999271
17291171729992717119271
17291211729192711219271
17291711729792711719271

17292912927172921929271
17292917927172971929271
17297199927172999179271
17297229927172992279271
17297711927172911779271

17292927129292172929271
17292927177177172929271
17292927192229172929271
17297927127172172979271
17297927172227172979271

17291721729792712719271
17291921729192712919271
17292221729992712229271
17297111729792711179271
17297121729792712179271

17291199271217299119271
17291299271117299219271
17291999271217299919271
17292919271917291929271
17297129271717292179271

17297927179997172979271
17299927197279172999271
17299927197779172999271
17299271111111117299271
17299271121712117299271

17299271199799117299271
17299271217171217299271
17299271221912217299271
17299271299999217299271
17299271779997717299271

17292711912121911729271
17292711917971911729271
17292711992929911729271
17292712111211121729271
17292712112721121729271

17292712997779921729271
17292717121212171729271
17292717127972171729271
17292717179197171729271
17292717217271271729271

17299271791219717299271
17299271792929717299271
17299271921712917299271
17299271972727917299271
17299271979797917299271

17292712122222121729271
17292712171217121729271
17292712172127121729271
17292712177977121729271
17292712199199121729271

17292717721212771729271
17292717729792771729271
17292717771217771729271
17292717917171971729271
17292717992729971729271

17292711117171111729271
17292711122122111729271
17292711179797111729271
17292711212921211729271
17292711221912211729271

1729271222222221729271
17292712297279221729271
17292712719791721729271
17292712722222721729271
17292712727772721729271

17292719129992191729271
17292719192929191729271
17292719199199191729271
17292719291119291729271
17292719297779291729271

17292711711211711729271
17292711719791711729271
17292711721212711729271
17292711779997711729271
1729271191111911729271

17292712729992721729271
17292712777277721729271
17292712779797721729271
17292712797279721729271
17292712799199721729271

17292719297979291729271
1729271929999291729271
17292719711111791729271
17292719711911791729271

17292719729192791729271
17292719791219791729271
17292719919191991729271
17292719921112991729271

27.2 Triple 1729

$$17292717299799271729271$$

$$17292711729792711729271$$

$$17299927172927172999271$$

28 Palindromic-Type: Multiplications

Palindromic numbers are famous by their property that when reading in reverse order the number remains the same. This deals with the numbers such that they are non palindromic but are separated by multiplication. These separations are in such a way that if we remove the operations the remaining numbers turns palindromic. These are called as **palindromic-type**. Below are palindromic-type number with **1729** only on the one side of the expression. obviously, there are much more numbers of this kind. Only few are written.

$$1729821 \times 1289271 = 1183881 \times 1883811.$$

$$2172912 \times 2192712 = 1163904 \times 4093611$$

$$2172906 \times 6092712 = 3091824 \times 4281903.$$

$$17299221 \times 12299271 = 11293881 \times 18839211$$

$$17299921 \times 12999271 = 11839981 \times 18993811$$

$$11729622 \times 22692711 = 12773802 \times 20837721$$

$$21729162 \times 26192712 = 13291824 \times 42819231$$

$$21729232 \times 23292712 = 12363904 \times 40936321$$

$$21729264 \times 46292712 = 23491824 \times 42819432$$

$$21729344 \times 44392712 = 23563904 \times 40936532$$

$$21729366 \times 66392712 = 33691824 \times 42819633$$

$$21729456 \times 65492712 = 34763904 \times 40936743$$

$$61729332 \times 23392716 = 35273904 \times 40937253$$

$$61729353 \times 35392716 = 35273916 \times 61937253$$

$$21729568 \times 86592712 = 40936954 \times 45963904$$

$$21729468 \times 86492712 = 42819834 \times 43891824$$

$$61729164 \times 46192716 = 35273808 \times 80837253$$

$$61729374 \times 47392716 = 35273928 \times 82937253$$

$$22172913 \times 31927122 = 11251926 \times 62915211$$

$$25172933 \times 33927152 = 13361936 \times 63916331$$

$$33172923 \times 32927133 = 30707553 \times 35570703$$

$$\begin{aligned}36172943 \times 34927163 &= 33708473 \times 37480733 \\90172981 \times 18927109 &= 17208199 \times 99180271 \\18017297 \times 79271081 &= 19817027 \times 72071891 \\26217298 \times 89271262 &= 28836118 \times 81163882 \\34417299 \times 99271443 &= 37855209 \times 90255873\end{aligned}$$

$$172993221 \times 122399271 = 112393881 \times 188393211.$$

$$\begin{aligned}117291351 \times 153192711 &= 126708141 \times 141807621 \\117292472 \times 274292711 &= 126709352 \times 253907621 \\117298887 \times 788892711 &= 128898717 \times 717898821 \\117297231 \times 132792711 &= 121937721 \times 127739121 \\117297711 \times 117792711 &= 107287821 \times 128782701 \\217295241 \times 142592712 &= 130936632 \times 236639031 \\121729642 \times 246927121 &= 145781602 \times 206187541 \\101729853 \times 358927101 &= 110785923 \times 329587011 \\111729654 \times 456927111 &= 121675914 \times 419576121 \\121729455 \times 554927121 &= 132565905 \times 509565231 \\221729331 \times 133927122 &= 112519362 \times 263915211 \\231729031 \times 130927132 &= 111618172 \times 271816111 \\251729541 \times 145927152 &= 133619472 \times 274916331 \\341729011 \times 110927143 &= 101707273 \times 372707101 \\811729821 \times 128927118 &= 117218298 \times 892812711 \\114172912 \times 219271411 &= 116390512 \times 215093611 \\115172902 \times 209271511 &= 105171922 \times 229171501 \\167172952 \times 259271761 &= 147518392 \times 293815741 \\168172942 \times 249271861 &= 147708382 \times 283807741 \\103317294 \times 492713301 &= 123937014 \times 410739321 \\108117297 \times 792711801 &= 118917027 \times 720719811 \\116317298 \times 892713611 &= 127936118 \times 811639721 \\124517299 \times 992715421 &= 136955209 \times 902559631 \\111389271 \times 172983111 &= 102283881 \times 188382201\end{aligned}$$

29 Palindromic-Type: Addition and Multiplication

This section deals with palindromic-type numbers in little different form. In the above section we worked with the operation multiplication. Here both addition and multiplications are used. These operations are used in such way that we have **1729** on both sides of the expression.

29.1 Sequential Patterns: 1729 Both Sides

Even though there are much more values we have considered only few, where **1729** appears in both sides and forming a sequential pattern.

$$\begin{aligned}17291 \times 10001 + 10001 \times 19271 &= 172927291 + 192729271 \\17292 \times 10001 + 10001 \times 29271 &= 172937292 + 292739271 \\17293 \times 10001 + 10001 \times 39271 &= 172947293 + 392749271 \\17294 \times 10001 + 10001 \times 49271 &= 172957294 + 492759271 \\17295 \times 10001 + 10001 \times 59271 &= 172967295 + 592769271 \\17296 \times 10001 + 10001 \times 69271 &= 172977296 + 692779271 \\17297 \times 10001 + 10001 \times 79271 &= 172987297 + 792789271 \\17298 \times 10001 + 10001 \times 89271 &= 172997298 + 892799271\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}172901 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 109271 &= 17290272901 + 10927209271 \\172902 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 209271 &= 17290372902 + 20927309271 \\172903 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 309271 &= 17290472903 + 30927409271 \\172904 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 409271 &= 17290572904 + 40927509271 \\172905 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 509271 &= 17290672905 + 50927609271 \\172906 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 609271 &= 17290772906 + 60927709271 \\172907 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 709271 &= 17290872907 + 70927809271 \\172908 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 809271 &= 17290972908 + 80927909271\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}172911 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 119271 &= 17291272911 + 11927219271 \\172912 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 219271 &= 17291372912 + 21927319271 \\172913 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 319271 &= 17291472913 + 31927419271 \\172914 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 419271 &= 17291572914 + 41927519271 \\172915 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 519271 &= 17291672915 + 51927619271 \\172916 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 619271 &= 17291772916 + 61927719271 \\172917 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 719271 &= 17291872917 + 71927819271 \\172918 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 819271 &= 17291972918 + 81927919271\end{aligned}$$

$$172921 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 129271 = 17292272921 + 12927229271$$

$$172922 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 229271 = 17292372922 + 22927329271$$

$$172923 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 329271 = 17292472923 + 32927429271$$

$$172924 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 429271 = 17292572924 + 42927529271$$

$$172925 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 529271 = 17292672925 + 52927629271$$

$$172926 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 629271 = 17292772926 + 62927729271$$

$$172927 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 729271 = 17292872927 + 72927829271$$

$$172928 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 829271 = 17292972928 + 82927929271$$

$$172931 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 139271 = 17293272931 + 13927239271$$

$$172932 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 239271 = 17293372932 + 23927339271$$

$$172933 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 339271 = 17293472933 + 33927439271$$

$$172934 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 439271 = 17293572934 + 43927539271$$

$$172935 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 539271 = 17293672935 + 53927639271$$

$$172936 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 639271 = 17293772936 + 63927739271$$

$$172937 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 739271 = 17293872937 + 73927839271$$

$$172938 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 839271 = 17293972938 + 83927939271$$

$$172941 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 149271 = 17294272941 + 14927249271$$

$$172942 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 249271 = 17294372942 + 24927349271$$

$$172943 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 349271 = 17294472943 + 34927449271$$

$$172944 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 449271 = 17294572944 + 44927549271$$

$$172945 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 549271 = 17294672945 + 54927649271$$

$$172946 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 649271 = 17294772946 + 64927749271$$

$$172947 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 749271 = 17294872947 + 74927849271$$

$$172948 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 849271 = 17294972948 + 84927949271$$

$$172951 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 159271 = 17295272951 + 15927259271$$

$$172952 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 259271 = 17295372952 + 25927359271$$

$$172953 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 359271 = 17295472953 + 35927459271$$

$$172954 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 459271 = 17295572954 + 45927559271$$

$$172955 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 559271 = 17295672955 + 55927659271$$

$$172956 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 659271 = 17295772956 + 65927759271$$

$$172957 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 759271 = 17295872957 + 75927859271$$

$$172958 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 859271 = 17295972958 + 85927959271$$

$$172961 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 169271 = 17296272961 + 16927269271$$

$$172962 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 269271 = 17296372962 + 26927369271$$

$$172963 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 369271 = 17296472963 + 36927469271$$

$$172964 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 469271 = 17296572964 + 46927569271$$

$$172965 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 569271 = 17296672965 + 56927669271$$

$$172966 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 669271 = 17296772966 + 66927769271$$

$$172967 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 769271 = 17296872967 + 76927869271$$

$$172968 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 869271 = 17296972968 + 86927969271$$

$$172971 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 179271 = 17297272971 + 17927279271$$

$$172972 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 279271 = 17297372972 + 27927379271$$

$$172973 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 379271 = 17297472973 + 37927479271$$

$$172974 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 479271 = 17297572974 + 47927579271$$

$$172975 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 579271 = 17297672975 + 57927679271$$

$$172976 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 679271 = 17297772976 + 67927779271$$

$$172977 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 779271 = 17297872977 + 77927879271$$

$$172978 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 879271 = 17297972978 + 87927979271$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 172981 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 189271 &= 17298272981 + 18927289271 \\
 172982 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 289271 &= 17298372982 + 28927389271 \\
 172983 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 389271 &= 17298472983 + 38927489271 \\
 172984 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 489271 &= 17298572984 + 48927589271 \\
 172985 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 589271 &= 17298672985 + 58927689271 \\
 172986 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 689271 &= 17298772986 + 68927789271 \\
 172987 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 789271 &= 17298872987 + 78927889271 \\
 172988 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 889271 &= 17298972988 + 88927989271
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 172991 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 199271 &= 17299272991 + 19927299271 \\
 172992 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 299271 &= 17299372992 + 29927399271 \\
 172993 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 399271 &= 17299472993 + 39927499271 \\
 172994 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 499271 &= 17299572994 + 49927599271 \\
 172995 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 599271 &= 17299672995 + 59927699271 \\
 172996 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 699271 &= 17299772996 + 69927799271 \\
 172997 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 799271 &= 17299872997 + 79927899271 \\
 172998 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 899271 &= 17299972998 + 89927999271
 \end{aligned}$$

29.2 Non Sequential Patterns

Below are two patterns different from the previous subsection. Here they are in such a way that increasing one zero in each line becomes very interesting pattern. Also, the number **1729** is on both sides of the expression.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 \times 10001 + 10001 \times 9271 &= 17291729 + 92719271 \\
 1729 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 9271 &= 172901729 + 927109271 \\
 1729 \times 1000001 + 1000001 \times 9271 &= 1729001729 + 9271009271 \\
 1729 \times 10000001 + 10000001 \times 9271 &= 17290001729 + 92710009271
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 11729 \times 100001 + 100001 \times 92711 &= 1172911729 + 9271192711 \\
 11729 \times 1000001 + 1000001 \times 92711 &= 11729011729 + 92711092711 \\
 11729 \times 10000001 + 10000001 \times 92711 &= 117290011729 + 927110092711.
 \end{aligned}$$

Still there is one more non sequential pattern giving same digits on both sides except number 0:

$$\begin{aligned}
 10001 \times 1729 + 9271 \times 10001 &= 1729\ 1729 + 7291\ 7291 \\
 10001 \times 1927 + 7291 \times 10001 &= 1927\ 1927 + 7291\ 7291 \\
 10001 \times 2719 + 9172 \times 10001 &= 2719\ 2719 + 9172\ 9172 \\
 10001 \times 2917 + 7192 \times 10001 &= 2917\ 2917 + 7192\ 7192.
 \end{aligned}$$

30 Numbers in Terms of 17291729 and Reverse

Below are numbers from 1 to 1729 written in terms of digits of **1729** used twice, i.e., **17291729** only with the operations **addition**, **subtraction** and **multiplication**. There are lot of **extra brackets** in the reverse order. These can be removed after simplifications.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1} &:= 17 - 29 - 1 + 7 - 2 + 9 &&= 9271/9271 \\
 \mathbf{2} &:= 17 - (29 - 17) \times 2 + 9 &&= (92 - 71) + ((9 - 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{3} &:= 1 \times 72 - 91 - 7 + 29 &&= (92 - (71 - 9)) - (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{4} &:= 1 + 72 - 91 - 7 + 29 &&= 9 + ((2 - 7) \times (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{5} &:= 17 - 2 - 91 + 72 + 9 &&= (9 + (2 - 7)) + (1^{9271}) \\
 \mathbf{6} &:= 17 \times 2 - 91 + 72 - 9 &&= (9 + 27) - ((19 \times 2) - (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{7} &:= 1 + 7 + 2 + 9 + 17 - 29 &&= (92 + 7) - ((19 + 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{8} &:= (1 + 7) \times (-2 - 9 - 17 + 29) &&= ((9 - 27) \times (1^9)) + (27 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{9} &:= 17 + 2 - 91 + 72 + 9 &&= ((9 - 27) - ((1^9) - 27)) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{10} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 + 17 - 29 &&= (9 + 2) - ((7 + 19)/(27 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{11} &:= 17 + 29 - 17 - 2 \times 9 &&= ((92 - 71) - (9^2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{12} &:= 17 - 2 + 9 + 17 - 29 &&= (9 \times 2) - (7 - (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{13} &:= 1 \times 7 - 29 - 1 + 7 + 29 &&= 92 - ((7 + (1^{92})) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{14} &:= 1 + 7 - 29 - 1 + 7 + 29 &&= 9 - ((2 - 7) \times (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{15} &:= 17 \times 2 - 9 + 1 + 7 - 2 \times 9 &&= ((9 + (27 \times 1)) - 92) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{16} &:= 17 + 2 + 9 + 17 - 29 &&= ((92 + (7 - 1)) - 9) - (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{17} &:= -17 + 2 + 9 + 1 - 7 + 29 &&= (9 + (27 - (1 - 9))) - (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{18} &:= 17 - 2 - 9 - 17 + 29 &&= ((9 - (2 + (71 - 9))) + 2) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{19} &:= 17 \times 2 - 9 - 17 + 2 + 9 &&= 9 + ((2 + 7) + (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{20} &:= 17 - 2 \times 9 - 1 - 7 + 29 &&= ((9 + (27 + 1)) + 9) - (27 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{21} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 + 17 - 2 \times 9 &&= (9 - (2 - 7)) - ((19 - 27) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{22} &:= 17 + 29 - 17 + 2 - 9 &&= (92 - 7) + ((1 + 9) - (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{23} &:= 17 - 29 + 17 + 2 \times 9 &&= (9 - (2 - 7)) - ((19 - 27) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{24} &:= 17 \times 2 - 91 + 72 + 9 &= (9 \times 2) + (7 - (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{25} &:= 1 + 7 + 29 + 17 - 29 &= ((9 \times 2) + 7) + ((1^{927}) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{26} &:= 17 \times 2 - 9 - 17 + 2 \times 9 &= 92 - ((71 - (9 + (2 - 7))) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{27} &:= 17 - 2 - 9 - 1 - 7 + 29 &= (9 - (27 - 19)) \times (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{28} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 \times (9 - 1) + 7 + 29 &= 92 + ((7 \times (1^{92})) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{29} &:= 17 + 2 + 91 - 72 - 9 &= (92 + 7) + ((1^{92}) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{30} &:= (1 - 7 + 2 + 9) \times (17 - 2 - 9) &= (((9 - 2) + 7) - 19) \times ((2 - 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{31} &:= 1 + 7 + 2 + 9 - 17 + 29 &= 9 + (((27 - 19) \times 2) + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{32} &:= 17 - 2 \times (-9 + 1 + 7 - 2) + 9 &= (((9 - 27) - 19) - 2) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{33} &:= -17 + 29 - 1 - 7 + 29 &= (9^2) - ((7 - 19) \times (2 - (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{34} &:= 17 + 29 + 17 - 29 &= 92 - (((7 + 19) \times 2) + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{35} &:= 1 - 7 + 29 - 17 + 29 &= 9 + (27 - (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{36} &:= 17 + 29 - 17 - 2 + 9 &= (9 - 27) - (19 - (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{37} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 + 9 + 1 + 7 + 2 + 9 &= (9 + (2 - 7)) + (19 + ((2 \times 7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{38} &:= 17 - (2 + 9 - 17) \times 2 + 9 &= ((92 - 7) - (19 + 27)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{39} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 9 + 1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 &= ((92 - 7) - (19 + 27)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{40} &:= 17 + 29 - 17 + 2 + 9 &= 92 - ((7 + 19) + (27 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{41} &:= -1 + 7 - 2 - 9 + 17 + 29 &= (9 - 2) + (7 - ((1^9) - (27 + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{42} &:= 17 + 29 \times 1 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= 9 - ((2 - 71) + ((9 + 27) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{43} &:= 17 - 2 + 91 - 72 + 9 &= 92 - 7^{1927+1} \\
 \mathbf{44} &:= (-17 + 2 \times 9 + 1) \times (-7 + 29) &= (9^2) - (((71 - 9)/2) + 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{45} &:= 17 + 2 - 9 + 17 + 2 \times 9 &= 92 - (((7 - 19) \times 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{46} &:= 17 - 2 + 9 \times 1 - 7 + 29 &= (((9 + 2) + 71) - 9) - (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{47} &:= 1 + 72 + 9 + 1 - 7 - 29 &= ((9 + 27) + (19 - 2)) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{48} &:= (1 + 7) \times (-29 + 17 + 2 \times 9) &= (9 \times (2 + 7)) + ((19 \times 2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{49} &:= 17 \times 2 - 9 + 17 - 2 + 9 &= (9 \times 2) + (((7 + 19) - (2 - 7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{50} &:= 17 + (29 - 17) \times 2 + 9 &= (9 + 2) - ((7 - (19 + 27)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{51} &:= 17 - 29 \times 1 + 72 - 9 &= (9 + (2 + 7)) - ((19 \times 2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{52} &:= 17 + 29 + 17 - 2 - 9 &= (92 - 7) + ((19 \times 2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{53} &:= 17 + 2 - 9 + 17 \times 2 + 9 &= (92 + 7) - (19 + (27 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{54} &:= 17 + 2 - 9 - 1 + (7 - 2) \times 9 &= (9 - ((27 + 1) - 9)) + 2^{7-1} \\
 \mathbf{55} &:= 17 + 2 \times (9 + 1) + 7 + 2 + 9 &= ((9 + 2) \times 7) - (1 + (92 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{56} &:= 17 + 2 - 9 + 17 + 29 &= (92 - (71 - 9)) + (27 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{57} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times (9 - 1 - 7 + 2) + 9 &= 9 - ((2 - 71) + (92 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{58} &:= 17 + 29 - 17 + 29 &= ((9 \times 2) - (7 - (19 + 27))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{59} &:= -1 + 7 + 29 + 17 - 2 + 9 &= 9 - (2 - ((71 + (9 - 27)) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{60} &:= 1 + 7 + 29 + 1 - 7 + 29 &= (9 \times (27 - 19)) - (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{61} &:= 1 + 7 - 29 + 1 + 72 + 9 &= (((9 + 2) + 71) - 92) + 71
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{62} &:= 1 + 7 \times (-2 + 9) - 17 + 29 &= (9 \times 2) + ((7 + (1 + (9 + 27))) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{63} &:= 1 + 72 - 9 - 1 - 7 - 2 + 9 &= ((92 + (71 - 92)) - 7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{64} &:= (1 + 72 - 9) \times (1 + 7 + 2 - 9) &= ((92 + (71 - 92)) - 7) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{65} &:= 1 + 72 - 9 + 1 + 7 + 2 - 9 &= ((92 + (71 - 92)) - 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{66} &:= 1 + 7 \times (2 + 9) + 17 - 29 &= (9 + 27) + ((19 \times 2) - (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{67} &:= -1 - 7 + 29 + 17 + 29 &= (((9 - 27) + 1) + (92 - 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{68} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 + 17 + 29 &= (((9 - 27) + 1) + (92 - 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{69} &:= 17 - 29 \times 1 + 72 + 9 &= (((9 - 27) + 1) + (92 - 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{70} &:= 17 + 29 + 17 - 2 + 9 &= ((9 + (2 \times (7 + 19))) + 2) + (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{71} &:= 17 \times 2 - 9 + 17 + 29 &= (9 + (27 - (1 - 9))) + (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{72} &:= 1 - 7 - 2 + 91 + 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + (27 + 1)) + 9) + (27 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{73} &:= -1 - 7 + 2 \times 9 \times 1 + 72 - 9 &= (9^2) - (7 + (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{74} &:= 17 + 29 + 17 + 2 + 9 &= (9 - 27) + (19 + (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{75} &:= 1 \times 72 - 9 - 17 + 29 &= (9^2) - (7 - (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{76} &:= 172 - 91 - 7 \times 2 + 9 &= ((92 - 7) + (19 - 27)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{77} &:= 1 + (-72 + 91) \times (-7 + 2 + 9) &= 92 + (71 - ((92 - 7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{78} &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 + 1 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= ((92 + 7) \times 1) - (92 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{79} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 - 9 + 1 + 72 + 9 &= ((92 + (71 - 92)) + 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{80} &:= 1 \times 72 - 9 - 1 + 7 + 2 + 9 &= (9 \times (2 + 7)) - (1^{9271}) \\
 \mathbf{81} &:= 17 + 2 \times 9 + 17 + 29 &= 92 - (((71 + 9) + 2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{82} &:= (1 + 72 + 9) \times (1 + 7 + 2 - 9) &= (9 + 27) + (19 + (27 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{83} &:= 1 + 72 + 9 + 1 + 7 + 2 - 9 &= (92 - 7) - ((1^{927}) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{84} &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 - 1 - 7 + 2 + 9 &= 92 - (7 + (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{85} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + (-9 + 17 + 2) \times 9 &= 92 - (7 \times (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{86} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + 9 + 1 + 72 + 9 &= ((9 + 27) - 19) - (2 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{87} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 - 9 \times 1 + 72 + 9 &= (92 - 7) + ((1^{927}) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{88} &:= 1 + 72 - 9 - 1 + 7 + 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 2) + (71 - 9)) + ((2 \times 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{89} &:= (-17 + 29) \times (1 + 7) + 2 - 9 &= (9^2) + (7 + (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{90} &:= (-1 + 7) \times ((29 - 17) \times 2 - 9) &= 9 \times ((2 + 7) + (1^{9271})) \\
 \mathbf{91} &:= 1 \times 72 - 9 + 17 + 2 + 9 &= (9 - (27 - (19 \times 2))) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{92} &:= 17 + 29 + 17 + 29 &= ((9 - (2 + 7)) + 19) + (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{93} &:= 17 + (2 \times 9 + 1) \times (-7 + 2 + 9) &= 92 + ((7 + 19)/(27 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{94} &:= 1 + 72 + 9 - 17 + 29 &= (92 - ((71 - 92)/7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{95} &:= -1 + 7 - 2 + 9 + 1 + 72 + 9 &= (92 - ((71 - 92)/7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{96} &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 + 91 + 7 + 2 - 9 &= (92 - ((71 - 92)/7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{97} &:= 1 + 72 + 9 + 1 + 7 - 2 + 9 &= (92 + 7) - ((1^{927}) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{98} &:= 17 + 2 \times (9 + 17) + 29 &= (92 - (((7 \times 1) \times 9) + 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{99} &:= 1 \times 72 - 9 \times 1 + 7 + 29 &= 92 + (7 \times (1^{9271}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$100 := 1 + 72 - 9 \times 1 + 7 + 29 = (((9 + 2) + 71) - 9) + (27 \times 1)$$

Above there are representations up to 100. Further representations from 101 to 1729 are given below in the last section as Appendix.

31 Colored Pattern Designs With 17-29

Below are few patterns on 1729 with two colors having 17 and 29. These colors are on a board of 9×9 .

Above we have written 6 different designs representing the same thing i.e., the numbers 17 and 29.

32 Magic Squares with Sum 1729

Below are magic squares of orders 7, 13, 14 and 19 in different ways. These are of type **single digits bordered, double digits bordered, striped, cornered** magic squares. Some of them are **block-wise bordered** magic squares. In all the situations the **magic sum** is always **1729**. In order to bring the sums 1729 in some cases, the negative entries are considered. Moreover, the entries are integers as the number 1729 is divisible by 7, 13 and 19.

32.1 Magic Squares of Order 7

Below are four magic squares of order 7 with magic sum as 1729.

7x7	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	7x7	mgc		1729					
1729	223	231	239	247	255	263	271	1729		264	260	262	227	226	224	266	1729
1729	262	270	229	230	238	246	254	1729		223	256	259	239	241	240	271	1729
1729	245	253	261	269	228	236	237	1729		225	236	246	251	244	258	269	1729
1729	235	243	244	252	260	268	227	1729		265	237	245	247	249	257	229	1729
1729	267	226	234	242	250	251	259	1729		263	252	250	243	248	242	231	1729
1729	257	258	266	225	233	241	249	1729		261	254	235	255	253	238	233	1729
	240	248	256	264	265	224	232	1729		228	234	232	267	268	270	230	1729
©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

7x7	mgc						1729	7x7	mgc							1729	
	248	243	250	252	242	230	264	1729		255	235	254	267	224	225	269	1729
	249	247	245	255	239	234	260	1729		239	259	240	227	270	257	237	1729
	244	251	246	236	258	270	224	1729		271	223	246	251	244	264	230	1729
	256	254	253	235	237	267	227	1729		238	256	245	247	249	258	236	1729
	238	240	241	257	259	232	262	1729		226	268	250	243	248	231	263	1729
	268	271	229	269	228	233	231	1729		266	228	242	229	262	241	261	1729
	226	223	265	225	266	263	261	1729		234	260	252	265	232	253	233	1729
©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

The first magic square is traditional **pandiagonal** magic square. The second one is **single digits bordered** magic square. The third one is **cornered** magic square and the last one is **double digits bordered** magic squares. These are constructed using sequential entries: {223, 224, ..., 270, 271}. For more details refer authors work [10, 11, 2, 14, 15].

32.2 Magic Squares of Order 13

Below are four magic squares of order 13 with magic sum as 1729. These are constructed with **sequential entries**: {49, 50, ..., 216, 217}.

- 1.

mgc	13x13 https://numbers-magic.com/										https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/		1729
86	68	178	189	75	78	216	71	206	82	214	199	67	1729
180	198	88	77	191	188	50	195	60	184	52	61	205	1729
72	194	153	150	101	112	170	147	98	107	159	63	203	1729
215	51	113	116	165	154	96	119	168	95	171	186	80	1729
79	187	115	151	135	142	122	141	125	156	110	179	87	1729
209	57	160	106	131	124	144	137	129	163	103	176	90	1729
58	208	169	97	123	143	133	121	145	164	102	62	204	1729
183	83	120	146	136	130	128	139	132	94	172	190	76	1729
85	181	157	109	140	126	138	127	134	152	114	185	81	1729
212	54	99	167	118	117	104	173	100	158	161	92	174	1729
66	200	111	155	148	149	162	93	166	108	105	70	196	1729
73	193	182	175	177	65	64	217	59	69	53	192	210	1729
211	55	84	91	89	201	202	49	207	197	213	74	56	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is **double digits bordered** magic square. Since it is based on equal width stripes, we may call it **almost striped** magic square, because the internal part is only magic square of order 5. For more details refer author's work [14].

2.

mgc	13x13 https://numbers-magic.com/										https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/		1729
130	135	134	139	127	146	120	99	167	91	175	207	59	1729
137	133	129	140	126	153	113	108	158	182	84	49	217	1729
132	131	136	122	144	150	116	104	162	85	181	56	210	1729
128	124	125	143	145	147	119	106	160	192	74	54	212	1729
138	142	141	121	123	111	155	169	97	87	179	53	213	1729
148	112	149	152	110	109	151	166	100	83	183	195	71	1729
118	154	117	114	156	115	157	105	161	187	79	200	66	1729
170	171	107	101	102	103	173	172	98	188	78	205	61	1729
96	95	159	165	164	163	93	168	94	92	174	203	63	1729
184	76	178	75	73	177	81	180	77	186	176	52	214	1729
82	190	88	191	193	89	185	86	189	90	80	197	69	1729
62	194	199	202	57	206	201	198	55	196	51	50	58	1729
204	72	67	64	209	60	65	68	211	70	215	208	216	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is **cornered** magic square. For more details refer author's work [15]

3.

mgc	13x13 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/												1729
204	195	197	199	201	203	205	57	55	53	51	49	60	1729
50	84	92	90	88	86	185	186	188	190	192	82	216	1729
52	193	100	172	170	168	167	104	106	108	102	73	214	1729
54	191	93	150	146	148	113	112	110	152	173	75	212	1729
56	189	95	109	142	145	125	127	126	157	171	77	210	1729
58	187	97	111	122	132	137	130	144	155	169	79	208	1729
59	83	165	151	123	131	133	135	143	115	101	183	207	1729
202	85	163	149	138	136	129	134	128	117	103	181	64	1729
200	87	161	147	140	121	141	139	124	119	105	179	66	1729
198	89	159	114	120	118	153	154	156	116	107	177	68	1729
196	91	164	94	96	98	99	162	160	158	166	175	70	1729
194	184	174	176	178	180	81	80	78	76	74	182	72	1729
206	71	69	67	65	63	61	209	211	213	215	217	62	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is **single digit bordered** magic square. For more details refer author’s work [2].

4.

204	195	197	199	201	203	205	57	55	53	51	49	60	1729
50	84	92	90	88	86	185	186	188	190	192	82	216	1729
52	193	114	163	122	119	156	124	112	161	126	73	214	1729
54	191	127	113	159	120	115	164	125	117	157	75	212	1729
56	189	158	123	118	160	128	111	162	121	116	77	210	1729
58	187	132	100	167	137	93	169	130	98	171	79	208	1729
59	83	172	131	96	165	133	101	170	135	94	183	207	1729
202	85	95	168	136	97	173	129	99	166	134	181	64	1729
200	87	150	145	104	155	138	106	148	143	108	179	66	1729
198	89	109	149	141	102	151	146	107	153	139	177	68	1729
196	91	140	105	154	142	110	147	144	103	152	175	70	1729
194	184	174	176	178	180	81	80	78	76	74	182	72	1729
206	71	69	67	65	63	61	209	211	213	215	217	62	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is **block bordered** magic square. The internal block is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 formed by equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. For more details refer [10, 11].

32.3 Magic Squares of Order 14

Below are four different type magic squares of order 14 with magic sum as 1729. These are constructed with **sequential entries**: {26, 27, . . . , 220, 221}

1.

14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	1729											
138	141	107	108	104	143	153	94	174	73	195	52	44	203	1729
109	106	140	139	99	148	96	151	173	74	197	50	214	33	1729
142	149	100	103	145	102	158	89	169	78	65	182	37	210	1729
105	98	147	144	146	101	155	92	81	166	54	193	206	41	1729
87	90	152	159	156	97	93	154	71	176	58	189	29	218	1729
160	157	95	88	91	150	86	161	162	85	188	59	212	35	1729
164	70	172	167	79	84	175	77	76	171	178	69	38	209	1729
83	177	75	80	168	163	72	170	82	165	180	67	200	47	1729
53	60	186	191	66	51	185	183	68	192	57	190	201	46	1729
194	187	61	56	181	196	62	64	179	55	63	184	45	202	1729
207	217	211	48	26	31	49	208	28	32	205	220	43	204	1729
40	30	36	199	221	216	198	39	219	215	42	27	213	34	1729
110	136	125	134	114	132	131	117	129	119	120	126	112	124	1729
137	111	122	113	133	115	116	130	118	128	127	121	135	123	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is **cornered striped** magic square. For more details refer author’s work [5].

2.

14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	1729											
85	166	165	77	75	173	155	92	216	31	42	208	35	209	1729
162	81	82	170	172	74	168	79	207	40	205	39	212	38	1729
87	160	148	98	147	101	156	91	44	203	49	198	28	219	1729
159	88	99	149	100	146	78	169	204	43	46	201	221	26	1729
157	90	143	105	102	144	89	158	33	214	199	48	29	218	1729
171	76	104	142	145	103	95	152	37	210	200	47	220	27	1729
84	163	154	161	97	96	153	80	34	41	202	217	211	36	1729
83	164	93	86	150	151	94	167	213	206	45	30	32	215	1729
57	192	61	183	180	68	58	189	119	128	109	140	106	139	1729
190	55	186	64	67	179	65	182	127	120	138	107	141	108	1729
185	62	70	73	176	175	178	69	123	124	135	112	117	130	1729
184	63	177	174	71	72	193	54	122	125	110	137	132	115	1729
59	188	52	197	53	196	187	56	129	118	113	134	114	133	1729
66	181	195	50	194	51	60	191	121	126	136	111	131	116	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is **striped** magic square made with equal width **magic rectangles**. For more details refer author’s work [5].

3.

14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	1729											
32	217	26	219	60	189	61	182	185	64	40	209	34	211	1729
27	218	33	216	63	68	178	181	67	184	35	210	41	208	1729
221	28	215	30	188	179	69	66	180	59	213	36	207	38	1729
214	31	220	29	183	58	186	65	62	187	206	39	212	37	1729
96	99	152	147	106	140	139	138	107	111	72	75	176	171	1729
153	104	143	94	135	113	133	114	116	130	177	80	167	70	1729
97	142	105	150	129	128	120	121	125	118	73	166	81	174	1729
146	145	102	101	123	119	126	127	122	124	170	169	78	77	1729
149	103	144	98	112	131	115	132	134	117	173	79	168	74	1729
100	148	95	151	136	110	108	109	137	141	76	172	71	175	1729
56	193	50	195	84	165	85	158	161	88	48	201	42	203	1729
51	194	57	192	87	92	154	157	91	160	43	202	49	200	1729
197	52	191	54	164	155	93	90	156	83	205	44	199	46	1729
190	55	196	53	159	82	162	89	86	163	198	47	204	45	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is constructed with magic squares of orders 4 and 6 along with 4 equal sums **bordered magic rectangles** of order 4×6 . For more details refer author's work [6].

4.

14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	1729											
26	29	28	27	30	217	218	219	220	221	50	196	187	61	1729
212	215	214	213	216	31	32	33	34	35	47	193	190	64	1729
211	208	209	210	207	40	39	38	37	36	48	194	189	63	1729
45	42	43	44	41	206	205	204	203	202	49	195	188	62	1729
86	152	151	105	106	140	139	138	107	111	46	192	191	65	1729
87	153	150	104	135	113	133	114	116	130	197	51	60	186	1729
88	154	149	103	129	128	120	121	125	118	198	52	59	185	1729
89	155	148	102	123	119	126	127	122	124	199	53	58	184	1729
90	156	147	101	112	131	115	132	134	117	200	54	57	183	1729
161	95	96	142	136	110	108	109	137	141	201	55	56	182	1729
158	92	99	145	66	67	68	69	70	177	178	181	180	179	1729
159	93	98	144	172	173	174	175	176	71	72	75	74	73	1729
160	94	97	143	171	170	169	168	167	80	79	76	77	78	1729
157	91	100	146	85	84	83	82	81	166	165	162	163	164	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is constructed with **bordered** magic square of order 6 along with 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 4×10 . For more details refer author's work [6].

32.4 Magic Squares of Order 19

Below are five magic squares of order 19 with magic sum as 1729. These magic squares are constructed with **sequential entries**: $\{-89, -88, \dots, 270, 271\}$.

1.

mgc	19x19		https://numbers-magic.com/						https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/						1729					
94	87	92	102	80	114	68	130	52	42	140	10	172	-7	189	218	-36	270	-88	1729	
89	91	93	103	79	77	105	126	56	48	134	158	24	176	6	209	-27	265	-83	1729	
90	95	88	82	100	75	107	124	58	144	38	13	169	179	3	210	-28	263	-81	1729	
84	86	101	85	99	112	70	60	122	44	138	8	174	181	1	212	-30	264	-82	1729	
98	96	81	83	97	73	109	128	54	47	135	156	26	-16	198	-53	235	269	-87	1729	
67	111	106	69	72	108	104	59	123	49	133	163	19	190	-8	-37	219	257	-75	1729	
115	71	76	113	110	78	74	64	118	147	35	9	173	182	0	-43	225	261	-79	1729	
53	51	119	117	121	125	55	62	116	145	37	153	29	-15	197	-44	226	-63	245	1729	
129	131	63	65	61	57	127	66	120	151	31	167	15	180	2	-51	233	258	-76	1729	
33	39	142	36	136	139	141	132	137	34	32	154	28	185	-3	-52	234	267	-85	1729	
149	143	40	146	46	43	41	50	45	150	148	18	164	184	-2	215	-33	-62	244	1729	
17	157	16	12	14	11	159	162	7	161	155	152	160	-17	199	220	-38	-71	253	1729	
165	25	166	170	168	171	23	20	175	21	27	22	30	-11	193	-48	230	-66	248	1729	
203	-10	4	-5	201	-1	194	5	-9	196	195	200	-4	-6	202	204	-22	-56	238	1729	
-21	192	178	187	-19	183	-12	177	191	-14	-13	-18	186	-20	188	-49	231	-60	242	1729	
217	211	-50	-40	-39	208	-46	-41	216	213	205	214	-45	206	-42	207	-47	-67	249	1729	
-35	-29	232	222	221	-26	228	223	-34	-31	-23	-32	227	-24	224	229	-25	-72	254	1729	
266	271	251	-57	-61	-74	-65	-54	-68	-64	-58	252	259	268	-59	260	262	-55	255	1729	
-84	-89	-69	239	243	256	247	236	250	246	240	-70	-77	-86	241	-78	-80	-73	237	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is **cornered** magic square. For more details refer author’s work [15].

2.

mgc	19x19 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/																1729		
264	268	-66	-60	253	225	217	-63	-62	-42	-25	-39	240	254	271	-36	-52	246	-64	1729
-82	-86	248	242	-71	-43	-35	245	244	224	207	221	-58	-72	-89	218	234	247	-65	1729
208	-26	30	21	-3	201	7	-20	26	186	14	169	153	199	200	163	19	235	-53	1729
230	-48	152	161	185	-19	175	202	156	-4	168	13	29	-17	-18	170	12	-76	258	1729
-79	261	155	27	48	52	120	117	145	53	126	127	31	125	57	197	-15	-61	243	1729
-83	265	174	8	134	130	62	65	37	129	56	55	151	141	41	0	182	226	-44	1729
-80	262	189	-7	54	128	106	115	85	70	79	114	68	49	133	176	6	219	-37	1729
223	-41	167	15	123	59	76	67	97	112	103	74	108	61	121	165	17	-56	238	1729
215	-33	-5	187	45	137	81	101	90	95	88	99	83	38	144	-13	195	241	-59	1729
204	-22	192	-10	142	40	78	104	89	91	93	86	96	122	60	-1	183	-81	263	1729
-84	266	181	1	124	58	110	72	94	87	92	82	100	34	148	-9	191	-77	259	1729
-85	267	9	173	33	149	73	109	71	77	102	107	98	118	64	18	164	-74	256	1729
211	-29	157	25	44	138	113	69	111	105	80	75	84	131	51	160	22	249	-67	1729
212	-30	5	177	135	47	32	140	35	116	46	36	132	143	139	159	23	-68	250	1729
214	-32	-6	188	119	63	150	42	147	66	136	146	50	39	43	-2	184	228	-46	1729
206	-24	-14	196	154	158	-16	190	180	3	178	-12	10	16	-11	162	171	227	-45	1729
210	-28	-21	203	28	24	198	-8	2	179	4	194	172	166	193	20	11	-78	260	1729
-87	269	-69	205	213	231	236	-70	229	-75	232	209	-73	-51	222	237	-57	-34	-38	1729
-88	270	251	-23	-31	-49	-54	252	-47	257	-50	-27	255	233	-40	-55	239	216	220	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It is **double digits bordered** magic square. For more details refer author's work [14].

3.

6. **(864, 1152, 1440)** $\Rightarrow 1440 - 864 = 24^2$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 55296$, $T_{576} := 1152^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 2877, 2879\}$.
7. **(624, 1457, 1585)** $\Rightarrow 1585 - 624 = 31^2$, $S_{31 \times 31} := 68479$, $T_{961} := 1457^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1730, \dots, 2688, 689\}$.
8. **(864, 2223, 2385)** $\Rightarrow 2385 - 864 = 39^2$, $S_{39 \times 39} := 126711$, $T_{1521} := 2223^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 4767, 4769\}$.
9. **(864, 2852, 2980)** $\Rightarrow 2980 - 864 = 46^2$, $S_{46 \times 46} := 176824$, $T_{2116} := 2852^2$,
 $E := \{1729, 1731, \dots, 5957, 5959\}$.

33.1 Magic Squares

Based on triples given above, below are magic squares of orders 6, 7, 11 and 19 referring the first four items.

33.1.1 Magic Squares of Order 6

Below are magic squares of order 6 with alternative numbers entries: $\{1729, 1731, \dots, 1797, 1799\}$

6x6	mgc							10584
	1729	1797	1795	1793	1731	1739	10584	
	1787	1743	1783	1745	1749	1777	10584	
	1775	1773	1757	1759	1767	1753	10584	
	1763	1755	1769	1771	1761	1765	10584	
	1741	1779	1747	1781	1785	1751	10584	
	1789	1737	1733	1735	1791	1799	10584	
©IJT	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	

6x6	mgc							10584
	1739	1787	1733	1799	1735	1791	10584	
	1797	1761	1771	1749	1775	1731	10584	
	1785	1751	1773	1763	1769	1743	10584	
	1781	1779	1753	1767	1757	1747	10584	
	1745	1765	1759	1777	1755	1783	10584	
	1737	1741	1795	1729	1793	1789	10584	
©IJT	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	

It is **cornered** magic square. For more details refer author's work [15].

6x6	mgc							10584
	1775	1761	1771	1759	1755	1763	10584	
	1741	1789	1737	1793	1795	1729	10584	
	1785	1781	1745	1751	1779	1743	10584	
	1731	1747	1783	1777	1749	1797	10584	
	1799	1739	1791	1735	1733	1787	10584	
	1753	1767	1757	1769	1773	1765	10584	
©IJT	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	

6x6	mgc							10584
	1761	1771	1749	1775	1785	1743	10584	
	1751	1773	1763	1769	1781	1747	10584	
	1779	1753	1767	1757	1797	1731	10584	
	1765	1759	1777	1755	1745	1783	10584	
	1735	1733	1799	1787	1739	1791	10584	
	1793	1795	1729	1741	1737	1789	10584	
©IJT	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	

It is **double digits bordered** magic square. For more details refer author's work [14].

6x6	mgc						10584	6x6	mgc						10584
	1749	1783	1747	1777	1733	1795	10584		1749	1779	1739	1789	1733	1795	10584
	1779	1745	1781	1751	1799	1729	10584		1783	1745	1785	1743	1799	1729	10584
	1739	1785	1791	1741	1731	1797	10584		1747	1781	1791	1737	1731	1797	10584
	1789	1743	1737	1787	1793	1735	10584		1777	1751	1741	1787	1793	1735	10584
	1769	1753	1767	1765	1757	1773	10584		1769	1753	1767	1765	1757	1773	10584
	1759	1775	1761	1763	1771	1755	10584		1759	1775	1761	1763	1771	1755	10584
©IJT	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	©IJT	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584	10584

It is **double digits bordered** magic square. For more details refer author’s work [14].

Thus the **Pythagorean triple** generates the above magic squares of order 6 having 1729 as one of the entry.

We have $6 \times 10584 = 252^2 := 900^2 - 864^2$. Thus the **Pythagorean triple** $252^2 + 864^2 := 900^2$ generates the above magic squares of order 6 having 1729 as one of the entry. For more details refer authors work [10, 11, 12, 14, 15].

33.1.2 Magic Squares of Order 7

Below are magic squares of order 7 with alternative numbers entries: {1633, 1635, ..., 1727, **1729**}

7x7	pan	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	7x7	mgc						11767	
11767	1633	1649	1665	1681	1697	1713	1729	11767		1715	1707	1711	1641	1639	1635	1719	11767
11767	1711	1727	1645	1647	1663	1679	1695	11767		1633	1699	1705	1665	1669	1667	1729	11767
11767	1677	1693	1709	1725	1643	1659	1661	11767		1637	1659	1679	1689	1675	1703	1725	11767
11767	1657	1673	1675	1691	1707	1723	1641	11767		1717	1661	1677	1681	1685	1701	1645	11767
11767	1721	1639	1655	1671	1687	1689	1705	11767		1713	1691	1687	1673	1683	1671	1649	11767
11767	1701	1703	1719	1637	1653	1669	1685	11767		1709	1695	1657	1697	1693	1663	1653	11767
	1667	1683	1699	1715	1717	1635	1651	11767		1643	1655	1651	1721	1723	1727	1647	11767
©IJT	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	©IJT	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767

7x7	mgc						11767	7x7	mgc						11767		
	1683	1673	1687	1691	1671	1647	1715	11767		1697	1657	1695	1721	1635	1637	1725	11767
	1685	1681	1677	1697	1665	1655	1707	11767		1665	1705	1667	1641	1727	1701	1661	11767
	1675	1689	1679	1659	1703	1727	1635	11767		1729	1633	1679	1689	1675	1715	1647	11767
	1699	1695	1693	1657	1661	1721	1641	11767		1663	1699	1677	1681	1685	1703	1659	11767
	1663	1667	1669	1701	1705	1651	1711	11767		1639	1723	1687	1673	1683	1649	1713	11767
	1723	1729	1645	1725	1643	1653	1649	11767		1719	1643	1671	1645	1711	1669	1709	11767
	1639	1633	1717	1637	1719	1713	1709	11767		1655	1707	1691	1717	1651	1693	1653	11767
©IJT	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	©IJT	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767	11767

The first magic square is well known **pandiagonal** magic square. The second magic square is **single digit bordered** magic square. The third one is known as **cornered** magic square. The fourth one is **double digits bordered** magic square. For more details refer authors work [10, 11, 12, 14, 15, 21].

Thus, $7 \times 11767 = 287^2 := 865^2 - 816^2$, i.e, the **Pythagorean triple** $287^2 + 816^2 := 865^2$ generates the above magic squares of order 7 having 1729 as one of the entry.

33.1.3 Magic Square of Order 11

1.

11x11	pan	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339
20339	1729	1769	1787	1805	1823	1841	1881	1899	1917	1935	1953	20339
20339	1929	1969	1745	1763	1781	1799	1817	1857	1875	1893	1911	20339
20339	1887	1905	1945	1963	1739	1757	1775	1815	1833	1851	1869	20339
20339	1845	1863	1903	1921	1939	1957	1733	1751	1791	1809	1827	20339
20339	1803	1821	1839	1879	1897	1915	1933	1951	1749	1767	1785	20339
20339	1761	1779	1797	1837	1855	1873	1891	1909	1927	1967	1743	20339
20339	1961	1737	1755	1773	1813	1831	1849	1867	1885	1925	1943	20339
20339	1919	1937	1955	1731	1771	1789	1807	1825	1843	1861	1901	20339
20339	1877	1895	1913	1931	1949	1747	1765	1783	1801	1819	1859	20339
20339	1835	1853	1871	1889	1907	1947	1965	1741	1759	1777	1795	20339
	1793	1811	1829	1847	1865	1883	1923	1941	1959	1735	1753	20339
©IJT	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339

2.

11x11	mgc											20339	
		1751	1767	1763	1759	1755	1953	1955	1959	1963	1967	1747	20339
		1969	1783	1927	1923	1919	1917	1791	1795	1799	1787	1729	20339
		1965	1769	1883	1875	1879	1809	1807	1803	1887	1929	1733	20339
		1961	1773	1801	1867	1873	1833	1837	1835	1897	1925	1737	20339
		1957	1777	1805	1827	1847	1857	1843	1871	1893	1921	1741	20339
		1749	1913	1885	1829	1845	1849	1853	1869	1813	1785	1949	20339
		1753	1909	1881	1859	1855	1841	1851	1839	1817	1789	1945	20339
		1757	1905	1877	1863	1825	1865	1861	1831	1821	1793	1941	20339
		1761	1901	1811	1823	1819	1889	1891	1895	1815	1797	1937	20339
		1765	1911	1771	1775	1779	1781	1907	1903	1899	1915	1933	20339
		1951	1931	1935	1939	1943	1745	1743	1739	1735	1731	1947	20339
©IJT	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339

3.

11x11	mgc											20339
	1751	1767	1763	1759	1755	1953	1955	1959	1963	1967	1747	20339
	1969	1811	1909	1827	1821	1895	1831	1807	1905	1835	1729	20339
	1965	1837	1809	1901	1823	1813	1911	1833	1817	1897	1733	20339
	1961	1899	1829	1819	1903	1839	1805	1907	1825	1815	1737	20339
	1957	1847	1783	1917	1857	1769	1921	1843	1779	1925	1741	20339
	1749	1927	1845	1775	1913	1849	1785	1923	1853	1771	1949	20339
	1753	1773	1919	1855	1777	1929	1841	1781	1915	1851	1945	20339
	1757	1883	1873	1791	1893	1859	1795	1879	1869	1799	1941	20339
	1761	1801	1881	1865	1787	1885	1875	1797	1889	1861	1937	20339
	1765	1863	1793	1891	1867	1803	1877	1871	1789	1887	1933	20339
	1951	1931	1935	1939	1943	1745	1743	1739	1735	1731	1947	20339
©IJT	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339

4.

11x11	mgc											20339
	1843	1853	1851	1835	1863	1813	1885	1901	1797	1753	1945	20339
	1857	1849	1841	1837	1861	1883	1815	1777	1921	1935	1763	20339
	1847	1845	1855	1871	1827	1877	1821	1775	1923	1743	1955	20339
	1839	1831	1833	1873	1869	1803	1895	1905	1793	1733	1965	20339
	1859	1867	1865	1829	1825	1805	1893	1911	1787	1939	1759	20339
	1889	1801	1807	1879	1881	1875	1811	1785	1913	1737	1961	20339
	1809	1897	1891	1819	1817	1887	1823	1773	1925	1937	1761	20339
	1769	1919	1909	1781	1903	1907	1771	1899	1783	1943	1755	20339
	1929	1779	1789	1917	1795	1791	1927	1915	1799	1941	1757	20339
	1967	1745	1963	1959	1969	1749	1765	1957	1751	1747	1767	20339
	1731	1953	1735	1739	1729	1949	1933	1741	1947	1931	1951	20339
©IJT	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339

5.

11x11	mgc											20339
	1799	1787	1901	1763	1737	1967	1759	1959	1969	1757	1941	20339
	1899	1911	1797	1935	1961	1731	1939	1739	1729	1927	1771	20339
	1923	1775	1825	1819	1831	1875	1895	1861	1837	1909	1789	20339
	1795	1903	1873	1879	1867	1823	1803	1881	1817	1769	1929	20339
	1747	1951	1889	1809	1851	1853	1843	1813	1885	1915	1783	20339
	1745	1953	1863	1835	1841	1849	1857	1807	1891	1955	1743	20339
	1931	1767	1871	1827	1855	1845	1847	1883	1815	1741	1957	20339
	1779	1919	1821	1877	1805	1887	1829	1859	1865	1907	1791	20339
	1965	1733	1801	1897	1893	1811	1869	1839	1833	1761	1937	20339
	1963	1735	1949	1781	1933	1753	1777	1947	1943	1773	1785	20339
	1793	1905	1749	1917	1765	1945	1921	1751	1755	1925	1913	20339
©IJT	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339	20339

The first magic square is well known **pandiagonal** magic square. The second magic square is **single digit bordered** magic square. The third one is known as **cornered** magic square. The fourth one is **double digits bordered** magic square. All these magic squares are constructed with alternative numbers entries, i.e., {1633, 1635, ..., 1727, **1729**}. For more details refer authors work [10, 11, 12, 14, 15, 21].

Thus, $11 \times 20339 = 473^2 := 985^2 - 864^2$. Thus the **Pythagorean triple** $473^2 + 864^2 := 985^2$ generates the above magic square of order 11 having 1729 as one of the entry.

33.1.4 Magic Square of Order 19

Based on the entries given in item 4, below are two magic squares of order 19. Both of them are with entry as 1729.

- 1.

19x19	pan	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011
26011	1009	1081	1115	1149	1183	1217	1251	1285	1319	1353	1425	1459	1493	1527	1561	1595	1629	1663	1697	26011
26011	1657	1729	1041	1075	1109	1143	1177	1211	1245	1279	1313	1385	1419	1453	1487	1521	1555	1589	1623	26011
26011	1583	1617	1689	1723	1035	1069	1103	1137	1171	1205	1239	1311	1345	1379	1413	1447	1481	1515	1549	26011
26011	1509	1543	1615	1649	1683	1717	1029	1063	1097	1131	1165	1199	1271	1305	1339	1373	1407	1441	1475	26011
26011	1435	1469	1503	1575	1609	1643	1677	1711	1023	1057	1091	1125	1197	1231	1265	1299	1333	1367	1401	26011
26011	1361	1395	1429	1501	1535	1569	1603	1637	1671	1705	1017	1051	1085	1157	1191	1225	1259	1293	1327	26011
26011	1287	1321	1355	1389	1461	1495	1529	1563	1597	1631	1665	1699	1011	1083	1117	1151	1185	1219	1253	26011
26011	1213	1247	1281	1315	1387	1421	1455	1489	1523	1557	1591	1625	1659	1693	1043	1077	1111	1145	1179	26011
26011	1139	1173	1207	1241	1275	1347	1381	1415	1449	1483	1517	1551	1585	1619	1691	1725	1037	1071	1105	26011
26011	1065	1099	1133	1167	1201	1273	1307	1341	1375	1409	1443	1477	1511	1545	1579	1651	1685	1719	1031	26011
26011	1713	1025	1059	1093	1127	1161	1233	1267	1301	1335	1369	1403	1437	1471	1505	1577	1611	1645	1679	26011
26011	1639	1673	1707	1019	1053	1087	1159	1193	1227	1261	1295	1329	1363	1397	1431	1465	1537	1571	1605	26011
26011	1565	1599	1633	1667	1701	1013	1047	1119	1153	1187	1221	1255	1289	1323	1357	1391	1463	1497	1531	26011
26011	1491	1525	1559	1593	1627	1661	1695	1045	1079	1113	1147	1181	1215	1249	1283	1317	1351	1423	1457	26011
26011	1417	1451	1485	1519	1553	1587	1621	1655	1727	1039	1073	1107	1141	1175	1209	1243	1277	1349	1383	26011
26011	1343	1377	1411	1445	1479	1513	1547	1581	1653	1687	1721	1033	1067	1101	1135	1169	1203	1237	1309	26011
26011	1269	1303	1337	1371	1405	1439	1473	1507	1541	1613	1647	1681	1715	1027	1061	1095	1129	1163	1235	26011
26011	1195	1229	1263	1297	1331	1365	1399	1433	1467	1539	1573	1607	1641	1675	1709	1021	1055	1089	1123	26011
26011	1121	1155	1189	1223	1257	1291	1325	1359	1393	1427	1499	1533	1567	1601	1635	1669	1703	1015	1049	26011
26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011

It is **pandiagonal** magic square. For more details refer author's work [12].

2.

mgc	19x19 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/																	26011	
1047	1079	1075	1071	1067	1063	1059	1055	1051	1697	1699	1703	1707	1711	1715	1719	1723	1727	1043	26011
1729	1111	1655	1651	1647	1643	1639	1635	1631	1629	1119	1123	1127	1131	1135	1139	1143	1115	1009	26011
1725	1081	1337	1343	1303	1307	1305	1587	1593	1553	1557	1555	1237	1243	1203	1207	1205	1657	1013	26011
1721	1085	1297	1317	1327	1313	1341	1547	1567	1577	1563	1591	1197	1217	1227	1213	1241	1653	1017	26011
1717	1089	1299	1315	1319	1323	1339	1549	1565	1569	1573	1589	1199	1215	1219	1223	1239	1649	1021	26011
1713	1093	1329	1325	1311	1321	1309	1579	1575	1561	1571	1559	1229	1225	1211	1221	1209	1645	1025	26011
1709	1097	1333	1295	1335	1331	1301	1583	1545	1585	1581	1551	1233	1195	1235	1231	1201	1641	1029	26011
1705	1101	1287	1293	1253	1257	1255	1387	1393	1353	1357	1355	1487	1493	1453	1457	1455	1637	1033	26011
1701	1105	1247	1267	1277	1263	1291	1347	1367	1377	1363	1391	1447	1467	1477	1463	1491	1633	1037	26011
1045	1625	1249	1265	1269	1273	1289	1349	1365	1369	1373	1389	1449	1465	1469	1473	1489	1113	1693	26011
1049	1621	1279	1275	1261	1271	1259	1379	1375	1361	1371	1359	1479	1475	1461	1471	1459	1117	1689	26011
1053	1617	1283	1245	1285	1281	1251	1383	1345	1385	1381	1351	1483	1445	1485	1481	1451	1121	1685	26011
1057	1613	1537	1543	1503	1507	1505	1187	1193	1153	1157	1155	1437	1443	1403	1407	1405	1125	1681	26011
1061	1609	1497	1517	1527	1513	1541	1147	1167	1177	1163	1191	1397	1417	1427	1413	1441	1129	1677	26011
1065	1605	1499	1515	1519	1523	1539	1149	1165	1169	1173	1189	1399	1415	1419	1423	1439	1133	1673	26011
1069	1601	1529	1525	1511	1521	1509	1179	1175	1161	1171	1159	1429	1425	1411	1421	1409	1137	1669	26011
1073	1597	1533	1495	1535	1531	1501	1183	1145	1185	1181	1151	1433	1395	1435	1431	1401	1141	1665	26011
1077	1623	1083	1087	1091	1095	1099	1103	1107	1109	1619	1615	1611	1607	1603	1599	1595	1627	1661	26011
1695	1659	1663	1667	1671	1675	1679	1683	1687	1041	1039	1035	1031	1027	1023	1019	1015	1011	1691	26011
26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011

It is **block bordered** magic square. The internal block is a magic of order 15 with different sums **block bordered** magic squares of order 5. For more details refer author's work [21].

3.

mgc	19x19 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/																26011			
1375	1361	1371	1391	1347	1415	1323	1447	1291	1271	1467	1207	1531	1173	1565	1623	1115	1727	1011	26011	
1365	1369	1373	1393	1345	1341	1397	1439	1299	1283	1455	1503	1235	1539	1199	1605	1133	1717	1021	26011	
1367	1377	1363	1351	1387	1337	1401	1435	1303	1475	1263	1213	1525	1545	1193	1607	1131	1713	1025	26011	
1355	1359	1389	1357	1385	1411	1327	1307	1431	1275	1463	1203	1535	1549	1189	1611	1127	1715	1023	26011	
1383	1379	1349	1353	1381	1333	1405	1443	1295	1281	1457	1499	1239	1155	1583	1081	1657	1725	1013	26011	
1321	1409	1399	1325	1331	1403	1395	1305	1433	1285	1453	1513	1225	1567	1171	1113	1625	1701	1037	26011	
1417	1329	1339	1413	1407	1343	1335	1315	1423	1481	1257	1205	1533	1551	1187	1101	1637	1709	1029	26011	
1293	1289	1425	1421	1429	1437	1297	1311	1419	1477	1261	1493	1245	1157	1581	1099	1639	1061	1677	26011	
1445	1449	1313	1317	1309	1301	1441	1319	1427	1489	1249	1521	1217	1547	1191	1085	1653	1703	1035	26011	
1253	1265	1471	1259	1459	1465	1469	1451	1461	1255	1251	1495	1243	1557	1181	1083	1655	1721	1017	26011	
1485	1473	1267	1479	1279	1273	1269	1287	1277	1487	1483	1223	1515	1555	1183	1617	1121	1063	1675	26011	
1221	1501	1219	1211	1215	1209	1505	1511	1201	1509	1497	1491	1507	1153	1585	1627	1111	1045	1693	26011	
1517	1237	1519	1527	1523	1529	1233	1227	1537	1229	1241	1231	1247	1165	1573	1091	1647	1055	1683	26011	
1593	1167	1195	1177	1589	1185	1575	1197	1169	1579	1577	1587	1179	1175	1591	1595	1143	1075	1663	26011	
1145	1571	1543	1561	1149	1553	1163	1541	1569	1159	1161	1151	1559	1147	1563	1089	1649	1067	1671	26011	
1621	1609	1087	1107	1109	1603	1095	1105	1619	1613	1597	1615	1097	1599	1103	1601	1093	1053	1685	26011	
1117	1129	1651	1631	1629	1135	1643	1633	1119	1125	1141	1123	1641	1139	1635	1645	1137	1043	1695	26011	
1719	1729	1689	1073	1065	1039	1057	1079	1051	1059	1071	1691	1705	1723	1069	1707	1711	1077	1697	26011	
1019	1009	1049	1665	1673	1699	1681	1659	1687	1679	1667	1047	1033	1015	1669	1031	1027	1041	1661	26011	
26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011

It is **cornered** magic square. For more details refer author's work [15].

4.

mgc	19x19																https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	26011	
1715	1723	1055	1067	1693	1637	1621	1061	1063	1103	1137	1109	1667	1695	1729	1115	1083	1679	1059	26011	
1023	1015	1683	1671	1045	1101	1117	1677	1675	1635	1601	1629	1071	1043	1009	1623	1655	1681	1057	26011	
1603	1135	1247	1229	1181	1589	1201	1147	1239	1559	1215	1525	1493	1585	1587	1513	1225	1657	1081	26011	
1647	1091	1491	1509	1557	1149	1537	1591	1499	1179	1523	1213	1245	1153	1151	1527	1211	1035	1703	26011	
1029	1709	1497	1241	1283	1291	1427	1421	1477	1293	1439	1441	1249	1437	1301	1581	1157	1065	1673	26011	
1021	1717	1535	1203	1455	1447	1311	1317	1261	1445	1299	1297	1489	1469	1269	1187	1551	1639	1099	26011	
1027	1711	1565	1173	1295	1443	1399	1417	1357	1327	1345	1415	1323	1285	1453	1539	1199	1625	1113	26011	
1633	1105	1521	1217	1433	1305	1339	1321	1381	1411	1393	1335	1403	1309	1429	1517	1221	1075	1663	26011	
1617	1121	1177	1561	1277	1461	1349	1389	1367	1377	1363	1385	1353	1263	1475	1161	1577	1669	1069	26011	
1595	1143	1571	1167	1471	1267	1343	1395	1365	1369	1373	1359	1379	1431	1307	1185	1553	1025	1713	26011	
1019	1719	1549	1189	1435	1303	1407	1331	1375	1361	1371	1351	1387	1255	1483	1169	1569	1033	1705	26011	
1017	1721	1205	1533	1253	1485	1333	1405	1329	1341	1391	1401	1383	1423	1315	1223	1515	1039	1699	26011	
1609	1129	1501	1237	1275	1463	1413	1325	1409	1397	1347	1337	1355	1449	1289	1507	1231	1685	1053	26011	
1611	1127	1197	1541	1457	1281	1251	1467	1257	1419	1279	1259	1451	1473	1465	1505	1233	1051	1687	26011	
1615	1123	1175	1563	1425	1313	1487	1271	1481	1319	1459	1479	1287	1265	1273	1183	1555	1643	1095	26011	
1599	1139	1159	1579	1495	1503	1155	1567	1547	1193	1543	1163	1207	1219	1165	1511	1529	1641	1097	26011	
1607	1131	1145	1593	1243	1235	1583	1171	1191	1545	1195	1575	1531	1519	1573	1227	1209	1031	1707	26011	
1013	1725	1049	1597	1613	1649	1659	1047	1645	1037	1651	1605	1041	1085	1631	1661	1073	1119	1111	26011	
1011	1727	1689	1141	1125	1089	1079	1691	1093	1701	1087	1133	1697	1653	1107	1077	1665	1619	1627	26011	
26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011	26011

It is **double digits bordered** magic square. For more details refer author's work [14].

We have $19 \times 26011 = 703^2 := 865^2 - 504^2$. Thus the **Pythagorean triple** $703^2 := 865^2 - 504^2$ generates the above magic squares of order 19 having 1729 as one of the entry.

34 Appendix: Numbers in Terms of 17291729 and Reverse

Below are numbers from 101 to 1729 written in terms of digits of **1729** used twice, i.e., **17291729** only with the operations **addition**, **subtraction** and **multiplication**. The numbers 1 to 100 are given in above in Section 34.

There are lot of **extra brackets** in the reverse order. These can be removed after simplifications.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{101} &:= 1 - 72 - 9 + 172 + 9 &&= (((9^2) - 7) + ((19 + 2) + 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{102} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9) + (1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 &&= (((9^2) - 7) + ((19 + 2) + 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{103} &:= (-17 + 29) \times (1 + 7) - 2 + 9 &&= (9 - (27 - 192)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{104} &:= (-1 \times 72 + 91) \times 7 - 29 &&= ((92 + 7)/((1^9) + 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{105} &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 + 17 - 2 + 9 &&= (9 - 27) - (19 - (2 \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{106} &:= 1 + 7 + (-2 + 9) \times (1 \times 7 - 2 + 9) &&= (92 - 71) + (92 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{107} &:= -1 + 7 + (29 + 17) \times 2 + 9 &&= (92 - (7 - 1)) + (92 - 71)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 108 &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + 91 - 7 + 29 &= 92 + (((7 - 19) + 27) + 1) \\
 109 &:= 172 - (9 - 1) \times 7 + 2 - 9 &= ((9 - (27 \times 1)) \times 9) + 271 \\
 110 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 \times (9 \times 1 - 7) \times 29 &= 92 + (71 + ((9 \times 2) - 71)) \\
 111 &:= 172 + 9 \times (1 - 7) + 2 - 9 &= (((92 - 7) + (1 + (9 \times 2))) + 7) \times 1 \\
 112 &:= -1 + 7 - 2 - 9 + (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= (9 - 2) + (((7 \times 19) - 27) - 1) \\
 113 &:= -1 + 7 - 2 + 91 + 7 + 2 + 9 &= 9 + (27 - (1 - (9 - (2 - 71)))) \\
 114 &:= -1 - 72 + (91 + 7) \times 2 - 9 &= ((9 + (2 \times 71)) - 9) - (27 + 1) \\
 115 &:= 17 \times (-2 + 9) \times 1 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= (((92 - 7) - (1 - 9)) \times 2) - 71 \\
 116 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 \times (9 + 1) \times 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((927 - (1^9)) + 2)/(7 + 1) \\
 117 &:= 172 - 9 - 17 - 29 &= (9 + (271 - 92)) - 71 \\
 118 &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 + 91 - 7 + 29 &= (927 + (19 - 2))/(7 + 1) \\
 119 &:= -17 + 2 + 9 - 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (92 + ((7 - 1) \times 9)) - (27 \times 1) \\
 120 &:= 17 - 2 + 91 + 7 - 2 + 9 &= ((92 + 7) \times 1) + (92 - 71) \\
 121 &:= -1 - 7 + 2 + 91 + 7 + 29 &= (9 + 27) - (1 - (92 - (7 - 1))) \\
 122 &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + 91 + 7 + 29 &= (9 + (((27 \times 1) + 92) - 7)) + 1 \\
 123 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 + 91 + 7 + 29 &= 92 + (7 + (192/(7 + 1))) \\
 124 &:= -1 + 72 - 9 - 1 + 72 - 9 &= ((9 + (27 \times 1)) + ((9^2) + 7)) \times 1 \\
 125 &:= 172 + 9 \times (1 - 7) - 2 + 9 &= (((9^2) + 7) + (1 + 9)) + (27 \times 1) \\
 126 &:= -1 \times 7 - 2 + 9 \times 17 - 2 \times 9 &= (92 + 71) - ((9 + 27) + 1) \\
 127 &:= 17 + 29 \times 1 + 72 + 9 &= ((9 + (2 + 7)) \times (1 - 9)) + 271 \\
 128 &:= 1 - 7 - 2 + 91 + (7 - 2) \times 9 &= (92 + (71 - 9)) - (27 - 1) \\
 129 &:= 1 + 7 + (-2 + 9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (9^2) + ((7 \times (19 - 2)) - 71) \\
 130 &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 9 \times 17 - 29 &= ((92 - 7) - 19) + 2^{7-1} \\
 131 &:= 17 \times (-2 + 9) - 17 + 29 &= ((92 - 7) + (19 \times 2)) + (7 + 1) \\
 132 &:= 17 - 2 \times 9 \times (1 - 7) - 2 + 9 &= (92 - 7) + ((19 + 27) + 1) \\
 133 &:= 17 + 2 + 91 + 7 \times 2 + 9 &= 9 - ((2^7) + (19 - 271)) \\
 134 &:= 172 - (9 - 1) \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= 9 + ((2 \times 71) + (9 - (27 - 1))) \\
 135 &:= (17 \times 2 - 91 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 \times 27) + ((19 - (2^7)) + 1) \\
 136 &:= (1 - 7 - 29 + 1) \times (7 - 2 - 9) &= (9 + 27) + (((1 + 92) + 7) \times 1) \\
 137 &:= 1 + 7 + 2 + 91 + 7 + 29 &= (((9 \times 2) \times 7) + 19) - ((2 + 7) - 1) \\
 138 &:= -(1 + 7) \times 2 + 91 + 72 - 9 &= ((9 + 2) \times 71) - ((92 \times 7) - 1) \\
 139 &:= 1 - 7 - 29 - (1 - 7) \times 29 &= (9 + 2) + ((7 + 192) - 71) \\
 140 &:= 1 \times 72 + 91 - 7 \times 2 - 9 &= (((9 + (2^7)) - 1) + ((9 + 2) - 7)) \times 1 \\
 141 &:= 1 \times 7 - 29 + 172 - 9 &= 92 + ((71 - 9) - ((2 \times 7) - 1)) \\
 142 &:= 1 + 7 - 29 + 172 - 9 &= (92 + 71) - (92 - 71) \\
 143 &:= 1 \times 72 - 9 - 1 + 72 + 9 &= ((9 + (271 - 9)) - (2^7)) \times 1 \\
 144 &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 - 9 + 17 \times 2 - 9) &= ((9 + (271 - 9)) - (2^7)) + 1 \\
 145 &:= 17 + 2 + 9 \times (17 - 2) - 9 &= 92 + ((71 - (9 + 2)) - (7 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 146 &:= (-1 + 72) \times 9 - 17 \times 29 &= ((9 + 2) + (71 - 9)) + (2 + 71) \\
 147 &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 - 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 2) \times 7) - ((1^{92}) - 71) \\
 148 &:= (17 + 2) \times 9 - 1 + 7 - 29 &= (92 - 7) - ((1 + (9 - 2)) - 71) \\
 149 &:= 1 - 7 + 29 + 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= 92 - ((7 \times 1) + (9 - (2 + 71))) \\
 150 &:= (17 - 2) \times (9 + 1 + 7 + 2 - 9) &= (92 + 71) - (9 - ((2 - 7) + 1)) \\
 151 &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 + 9 \times 17 + 2 - 9 &= (((9 \times 27) - 19) - 2) - 71 \\
 152 &:= 1 - 7 + (2 + 9) \times 17 - 29 &= 9 - ((27 - (19 \times (2 + 7))) + 1) \\
 153 &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 91 - 7 - 29 &= (9 - (2^7)) + ((1^9) + 271) \\
 154 &:= 1 + 7 + 2 \times 91 - 7 - 29 &= (9 - 2) + ((7 \times 19) + (2 \times (7 \times 1))) \\
 155 &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 + 9 \times 17 + 2 - 9 &= ((9 \times 27) - 19) + (2 - 71) \\
 156 &:= -17 - 29 - 1 + 7 \times 29 &= 92 - ((7 \times (1^{92})) - 71) \\
 157 &:= 172 - 9 - 17 + 2 + 9 &= (9 + 27) + (192 - 71) \\
 158 &:= 1 \times 72 + 91 - 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (92 + 71) - (9 + ((2 - 7) + 1)) \\
 159 &:= 172 + 9 + 1 - 7 \times 2 - 9 &= (92 - (71 - 9)) + ((2^7) + 1) \\
 160 &:= 1 + 7 - 29 + 172 + 9 &= (92 + 71) - ((9 + (2 - 7)) - 1) \\
 161 &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 - 1 + 72 + 9 &= (9 \times ((27 - 19) + 2)) + 71 \\
 162 &:= -1 - 7 - 2 - 9 + 172 + 9 &= (9 \times 2) - ((7 - 19) \times (2 \times (7 - 1))) \\
 163 &:= 17 + 2 \times 91 - 7 - 29 &= 92 - (((7 - 19) + 2) \times 7) - 1) \\
 164 &:= 1 - 7 - 2 - 9 + 172 + 9 &= 92 + ((7 - 19) \times ((2 - 7) - 1)) \\
 165 &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 + 9 \times 17 - 2 + 9 &= (9 \times (27 + 1)) - ((9^2) + (7 - 1)) \\
 166 &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 - 9 + 172 - 9 &= (9 - (27 - 192)) - (7 + 1) \\
 167 &:= (-17 - 2 + 91 + 7) \times 2 + 9 &= (92 + 71) - (9 - ((2 \times 7) - 1)) \\
 168 &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 + 91 + 72 - 9 &= (92 + 71) + (9 + ((2 - 7) + 1)) \\
 169 &:= 17 - 2 - 9 + 172 - 9 &= (9 + ((27 \times 1) - 9)) + (2 \times 71) \\
 170 &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 + 9 - (1 - 7) \times 29 &= (92 + (7 \times (1^{92}))) + 71 \\
 171 &:= -1 + 7 + 291 - 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 - ((2^7) - 19)) + 271 \\
 172 &:= 1 - 7 + (29 - 1) \times 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times 2) + 7) + ((19 + 2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 173 &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 \times (1 + 7) + 29 &= (92 + ((7 - 1) \times 9)) + (27 \times 1) \\
 174 &:= -1 - 7 - (2 - 9) \times (1 + 7 + 2 \times 9) &= (9 + ((2 + 7) \times 19)) + ((2 - 7) - 1) \\
 175 &:= 172 - 9 - 17 + 29 &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 1)) + (92 + (7 - 1)) \\
 176 &:= -1 + 7 - 2 + 9 + 172 - 9 &= (((927 \times 1)/9) + 2) + 71 \\
 177 &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 \times 1 \times (7 + 2 + 9) &= (92 - ((7 - 19) - 2)) + 71 \\
 178 &:= 17 + 2 + (91 - 7) \times 2 - 9 &= ((9 + 27) \times (1^9)) + (2 \times 71) \\
 179 &:= (1 + 7 + 2 + 91 - 7) \times 2 - 9 &= (9 \times (27 + 1)) - (9 + 2^{7-1}) \\
 180 &:= (1 - 7) \times (2 - 9 - 1 + 7 - 29) &= (9 - (27 - 192)) + (7 - 1) \\
 181 &:= 1 \times 72 + 91 + 7 + 2 + 9 &= (9 \times 2) - (71 - (9 \times (27 - 1))) \\
 182 &:= 172 + 91 - 72 - 9 &= (9 - (27 - 192)) + (7 + 1) \\
 183 &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 - 9 + 17 \times (2 + 9) &= (92 - ((7 + 1) - (92 + 7))) \times 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{184} &:= 172 - 9 - 1 - 7 + 29 &= (92 - (71 - 92)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{185} &:= 1 \times 7 + (29 - 1) \times 7 - 2 \times 9 &= 9 + (((2 \times 7) - 1) + (92 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{186} &:= 1 + 72 + 91 - 7 + 29 &= (9 + (2 \times 71)) + (9 + (27 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{187} &:= 172 + 9 + 17 - 2 - 9 &= 9 + ((2^7) - (19 + (2 - 71))) \\
 \mathbf{188} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 + 91 + 72 + 9 &= ((9 \times 2) + (71 + 92)) + (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{189} &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 - (1 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times (2 \times 7)) - (1 + 9)) + (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{190} &:= 17 - 29 - 1 + 7 \times 29 &= ((9 + 2^{7+1}) - (9^2)) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{191} &:= 172 - 9 + 17 + 2 + 9 &= (92 + 7) + ((19 + 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{192} &:= 1 + 7 \times 29 + 17 - 29 &= (9 + (271 - ((9^2) + 7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{193} &:= -17 + 291 - 72 - 9 &= (9 + (271 - ((9^2) + 7))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{194} &:= (17 + 2) \times 9 + 1 - 7 + 29 &= (((9^2) - 7) + 1) - (9 - ((2^7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{195} &:= 17 + 2 \times 91 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= (9 + 271) - (92 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{196} &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 \times 17 - 29 &= (9 - 2) \times (7 \times (19 - ((2 \times 7) + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{197} &:= 1 - 7 + 29 - (1 - 7) \times 29 &= 92 + (((7 \times 19) - 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{198} &:= -1 + 7 + 2 \times (91 + 7 \times 2 - 9) &= (9 - 2) - ((71 + 9) - 271) \\
 \mathbf{199} &:= 1 \times 7 + 29 + 172 - 9 &= (9 + (27 \times 1)) + (92 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{200} &:= 1 + 7 + 29 + 172 - 9 &= (92 + 71) + ((9 + 27) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{201} &:= 17 - 2 \times 9 - 1 + 7 \times 29 &= (((9 \times (27 + 19))/2) - 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{202} &:= 17 - 2 + (91 + 7) \times 2 - 9 &= (9 + 2) - ((71 + 9) - 271) \\
 \mathbf{203} &:= 172 + (9 - 1) \times (7 - 2) - 9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times 7) - ((1 - 9) + (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{204} &:= 172 + 9 + 1 - 7 + 29 &= (9 + ((2 + 7) + 192)) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{205} &:= 17 \times 2 + (91 - 72) \times 9 &= (92 - 7) - ((1 - 9) \times ((2 \times 7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{206} &:= -1 - 7 + 2 + 9 \times 1 + 7 \times 29 &= (((9 \times 27) - 1) - 9) - (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{207} &:= -1 \times 7 - 2 \times 9 + (1 + 7) \times 29 &= (9 + (2^7)) - ((1^{92}) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{208} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 \times 1 + (7 + 2) \times 9 &= (92 - (7 + 19)) + (2 \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{209} &:= 17 + 29 + 172 - 9 &= (9 + (2^7)) + ((1^{92}) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{210} &:= -1 + 7 + 2 \times 91 - 7 + 29 &= ((9 + 27) - (1^{92})) \times (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{211} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 \times 91 + 7 + 29 &= (9 \times 27) - (192/(7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{212} &:= 17 + 2 - 9 - 1 + 7 \times 29 &= ((92 \times 7) - (19^2)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{213} &:= (1 - 7 + 2) \times (-9 + 1) \times 7 - 2 - 9 &= ((9 - (2 - 7)) + 192) + (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{214} &:= 17 \times 2 + 9 + (17 + 2) \times 9 &= (9^2) - ((7 \times 1) \times (9 - (27 + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{215} &:= 1 - 7 + 29 \times (1 + 7) - 2 - 9 &= ((9 - 27) - 1) + (9 \times (27 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{216} &:= (1 - 7 + 2) \times (9 \times 1 - 72 + 9) &= (9 + ((2 + 7) + 192)) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{217} &:= 172 + 9 \times 1 + 7 + 29 &= ((9 - 27) \times ((1 - 9) \times 2)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{218} &:= -1 \times 7 \times 2 - (9 - 17) \times 29 &= ((9 + 27) \times (1 + 9)) - (2 \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{219} &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 - (9 - 17) \times 29 &= (92 + 71) + ((9 - 2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{220} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 + (9 \times 1 + 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= ((9 + 271) + 9) + (2 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{221} &:= 172 + (9 - 1) \times (7 - 2) + 9 &= (92 - 7) + ((19 - 2) \times (7 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 222 &:= 1 - 7 + 291 - 72 + 9 &= ((9 + 27) + 192) - (7 - 1) \\
 223 &:= 1 \times 7 + 29 + 17 \times (2 + 9) &= (92 + 71) - (9 + (2 - 71)) \\
 224 &:= -1 \times 7 + 29 - 1 + 7 \times 29 &= ((9 \times 2) + (7 + 192)) + (7 \times 1) \\
 225 &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 91 + 7 + 29 &= (9 - 27) + (1 + ((9 \times 27) - 1)) \\
 226 &:= 1 + 7 + 2 \times 91 + 7 + 29 &= ((92 + 7) \times ((1^9) + 2)) - 71 \\
 227 &:= 1 + 72 - 9 + 172 - 9 &= (9 \times 2) - ((71 - 9) - 271) \\
 228 &:= 1 \times 7 \times 29 + 17 \times 2 - 9 &= 92 + (((7 - 19)^2) - 7) - 1 \\
 229 &:= (-1 + 7) \times (29 + 1 + 7) - 2 + 9 &= (9^2) + (71 + ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 1))) \\
 230 &:= 1 - 7 \times (2 + 9) + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= (92 - (7 \times 19)) + 271 \\
 231 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 \times 9 + 1 + 7 - 2 + 9) &= 9 + (((2^7) - (19 \times (2 - 7))) - 1) \\
 232 &:= (1 + 7) \times (-2 + 9 + 1 - 7) \times 29 &= (9 \times 2) + (((7 + 1) \times 9) + (2 \times 71)) \\
 233 &:= 17 - 2 \times 9 \times (17 - 29) &= (9 - 27) - (1 - (9 \times (27 + 1))) \\
 234 &:= (1 - 72 + 91 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (((9 \times 2) \times 7) - 19) + ((2^7) - 1) \\
 235 &:= 1 + 72 - 9 + (17 + 2) \times 9 &= 92 + (((7 \times 19) + (2 + 7)) + 1) \\
 236 &:= -1 \times 7 + (2 \times 9 + 1 \times 7 + 2) \times 9 &= ((92 + 71) + ((9^2) - 7)) - 1 \\
 237 &:= 1 + 72 + 9 \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= (((9^2) + 71) + 92) - (7 \times 1) \\
 238 &:= 17 \times (29 - 1 - 7 + 2 - 9) &= (92 - ((71 - 92) \times 7)) - 1 \\
 239 &:= 1 + 7 \times (29 - 1 + 7) + 2 - 9 &= (92 - ((71 - 92) \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 240 &:= 1 + 7 + 29 \times 1 + 7 \times 29 &= (92 - ((71 - 92) \times 7)) + 1 \\
 241 &:= 172 + 91 + 7 - 29 &= (92 + 71) + (9 - (2 - 71)) \\
 242 &:= (17 + 2 + 9 + 1 - 7) \times (2 + 9) &= 9 + (((27 \times 1) \times 9) - ((2 + 7) + 1)) \\
 243 &:= 172 - 9 - 1 + 72 + 9 &= (((9 \times 27) + 1) + 9) - (2 + (7 + 1)) \\
 244 &:= 1 \times 72 + 91 + 72 + 9 &= ((9 \times ((2 + 7) \times 1)) + 92) + 71 \\
 245 &:= 17 + 291 - 72 + 9 &= (9 - (27 - 192)) + 71 \\
 246 &:= 172 + (9 - 1) \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times 2)/(7 - 1)) \times (9 + (2 + 71)) \\
 247 &:= -1 - 7 + 291 - 7 - 29 &= 92 + (7 + ((19 + (2^7)) + 1)) \\
 248 &:= -1 + 7 \times 29 + 17 + 29 &= ((9 \times 2) - (7 + 19)) + 2^{7+1} \\
 249 &:= 1 - 7 + 291 - 7 - 29 &= (92 - 7) + (1 + (92 + 71)) \\
 250 &:= 1 + 7 \times 29 + 17 + 29 &= (((9 \times 27) \times 1) - 9) + (2 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 251 &:= 1 \times 7 \times 29 - 1 - 7 \times (2 - 9) &= 9 + ((27 \times 19) - 271) \\
 252 &:= -17 + 291 + 7 - 29 &= (9 - 2) \times ((7 + (1^9)) + (27 + 1)) \\
 253 &:= (1 + 7) \times 29 - 1 - 7 + 29 &= ((9 + 2) + (7 + 1)) + (9 \times (27 - 1)) \\
 254 &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 \times 17 + 29 &= (9 - (27 - (1^9))) + 271 \\
 255 &:= 1 + 72 + 9 \times 17 + 29 &= (92 - 7) \times (((1 - 9)/2) + (7 \times 1)) \\
 256 &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times (-9 + 17 \times 2 - 9) &= (((9 \times 2) - 7) + 1) + ((9 \times 27) + 1) \\
 257 &:= 1 \times 7 + 29 \times (1 + 7) + 2 \times 9 &= (((92 - 7) - (1 - 9)) \times 2) + 71 \\
 258 &:= (-1 + 7) \times (-2 + 9 \times 1 + 7 + 29) &= (9 + 271) - ((9 + (2 \times 7)) - 1) \\
 259 &:= 172 + 91 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= (9 + (271 - 92)) + 71
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 260 &:= 1 + 7 + 2 \times (9 \times (17 - 2) - 9) &= (((9 \times 27) - 1) - 9) + (27 \times 1) \\
 261 &:= (17 \times 2 - 9 - 1 + 7 - 2) \times 9 &= (92 + 71) + (92 + (7 - 1)) \\
 262 &:= (-1 + 7 + 29) \times (1 + 7) - 2 \times 9 &= (((92 + 7) \times 1) + 92) + 71 \\
 263 &:= 172 + 91 + 7 + 2 - 9 &= 9 - (((27 - 1) - 9) - 271) \\
 264 &:= -1 + 7 \times 29 - 1 + 72 - 9 &= (9 + 2^{7+1^{927}}) - 1 \\
 265 &:= 1 \times 7 \times 29 - 1 + 72 - 9 &= (9 + 2) - (((7 + 1) + 9) - 271) \\
 266 &:= (1 \times 72 - 91) \times (-7 + 2 - 9) &= (9 - (2 - 7)) - (19 - 271) \\
 267 &:= 172 + 91 - 7 + 2 + 9 &= (9 + 271) - (((9 - 2) + 7) - 1) \\
 268 &:= 1 + 72 - 9 + 1 + 7 \times 29 &= ((9 + 2^{7+1}) - 9) + (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 269 &:= (17 + 29) \times (-1 + 7) + 2 - 9 &= 92 - ((7 - 192) + (7 + 1)) \\
 270 &:= ((-1 + 7) \times 2 - 9) \times (1 + 7 + 2) \times 9 &= 9 + (271 - ((9^2) - 71)) \\
 271 &:= 1 + 72 - 9 \times 1 \times (7 - 29) &= ((9 \times 27) + ((1^9) + 27)) \times 1 \\
 272 &:= 17 + 291 - 7 - 29 &= ((9 \times 27) + ((1^9) + 27)) + 1 \\
 273 &:= (17 - 2 + 9 \times (1 - 7)) \times (2 - 9) &= (((((9 + 2) + 7) \times 1)/9) + 271) \\
 274 &:= 172 + 91 - 7 + 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times 2) - (7 - 1)) - (9 - 271) \\
 275 &:= 1 \times 7 + 291 - 7 \times 2 - 9 &= ((9 + (2 \times 7)) - 19) + 271 \\
 276 &:= 1 \times 7 + 291 + 7 - 29 &= 92 \times (((7 + 1) \times 9) + (2 - 71)) \\
 277 &:= 1 + 7 + 291 + 7 - 29 &= (9 - 2) + (7 + (192 + 71)) \\
 278 &:= -17 - 2 - 9 + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times 7) + (19 \times ((2 + 7) - 1)) \\
 279 &:= 17 \times 2 \times (-9 + 17) - 2 + 9 &= ((9 + 271) + (9 - 2)) - (7 + 1) \\
 280 &:= 17 + 2 \times 91 + (7 + 2) \times 9 &= ((9 + (2 + 7)) \times 1) - (9 - 271) \\
 281 &:= 172 + 91 + 7 + 2 + 9 &= (9 + (271 - 9)) + ((2 + 7) + 1) \\
 282 &:= 1 - 7 + (-2 + 9 + 1) \times (7 + 29) &= (9 + (2 \times (((7 - 19)^2) - 7))) - 1 \\
 283 &:= 17 + 291 - 7 - 2 \times 9 &= (927 + 1) - ((92 \times 7) + 1) \\
 284 &:= 172 - 91 + 7 \times 29 &= 92 - (((7 - 192) - 7) \times 1) \\
 285 &:= -1 + 7 + (29 + 1) \times (7 + 2) + 9 &= (92 + 7) + (192 - (7 - 1)) \\
 286 &:= 17 + 291 + 7 - 29 &= 9 + (((2 \times 7) + 192) + 71) \\
 287 &:= -1 - 7 - 2 - 9 + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (27 + 19)) - ((2^7) - 1) \\
 288 &:= (1 + 7 + 29 \times 1) \times 7 + 29 &= (9 + 27) \times (((1^{92}) + 7) \times 1) \\
 289 &:= 1 + 72 + 9 \times (17 - 2 + 9) &= 9 - ((2 - ((7 - 1) \times (9 - 2))) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 290 &:= 172 - 9 + 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 271) + (9 \times 2)) - (7 + 1) \\
 291 &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times 9 - (1 - 7) \times 29 &= 9 + ((2 \times ((7 - 19)^2)) - (7 - 1)) \\
 292 &:= 17 \times 2 \times 9 \times 1 - 7 + 2 - 9 &= ((9 \times 2) - 7) + ((1 + 9) + 271) \\
 293 &:= 1 \times 7 + 291 - 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (((9 \times 27) - 19) - 2) + 71 \\
 294 &:= 1 + 7 + 291 - 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (92 - 71) \times ((9 - 2) + (7 \times 1)) \\
 295 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2 + 9) \times 17 - 2 - 9 &= ((9 + 271) + (9 - 2)) + (7 + 1) \\
 296 &:= -17 + 291 - 7 + 29 &= ((9 + 27) + (1^{92})) \times (7 + 1) \\
 297 &:= 1 \times 72 + (-9 + 17 \times 2) \times 9 &= ((9^2) \times 7) + ((1^9) - 271)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 298 &:= 172 + 9 + (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= ((9 + 27) \times 1) - (9 - 271) \\
 299 &:= 172 + 91 + 7 + 29 &= ((9 + 2) + 7) + (1 + (9 + 271)) \\
 300 &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 91 + 7 \times 29 &= ((9 \times 2) + (7 + 19)) + 2^{7+1} \\
 301 &:= (1 + 7 + 29 - 1 + 7) \times (-2 + 9) &= (92 - 71) + (9 + 271) \\
 302 &:= -1 \times 7 + 291 + 7 + 2 + 9 &= (9 + 271) + ((9 + (2 \times 7)) - 1) \\
 303 &:= 17 + 291 - 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (9 + (2 \times ((7 - 19)^2))) + (7 - 1) \\
 304 &:= (1 + 7) \times ((-2 + 9 + 1) \times 7 - 2 \times 9) &= (9 - (2 - 7)) + (19 + 271) \\
 305 &:= 17 - 2 \times (9 - 17) \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 - 271) + ((9^2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 306 &:= (1 - 72 + 91 + 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= ((9 + 271) + (9 \times 2)) + (7 + 1) \\
 307 &:= 1 - 7 + 291 - 7 + 29 &= (((92 - 71) \times 9) \times 2) - 71 \\
 308 &:= 172 + 9 + 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 - (2 \times (7 - 192))) - 71 \\
 309 &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 \times 17 \times 2 - 9 &= 927 / (19 - (2 \times (7 + 1))) \\
 310 &:= 17 \times 2 \times 9 \times 1 - 7 + 2 + 9 &= 92 + ((7 \times (19 + 2)) + 71) \\
 311 &:= 17 \times 2 \times 9 + 1 - 7 + 2 + 9 &= ((9 \times (2 \times 7)) + 192) - (7 \times 1) \\
 312 &:= 17 + 291 - 7 + 2 + 9 &= (92 + 7) + (((1^9) + 2) \times 71) \\
 313 &:= 17 + 291 + 7 \times 2 - 9 &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) + (19 + 271) \\
 314 &:= (17 + 2) \times (9 - 1 + 7) + 29 &= ((9 - 2) \times ((7 \times 1) \times 9)) - ((2^7) - 1) \\
 315 &:= (17 - 2 \times (9 - 17) + 2) \times 9 &= (9^2) + (71 + (92 + 71)) \\
 316 &:= 17 + 2 - 9 + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= 9 + (((27 \times 1) + 9) + 271) \\
 317 &:= 1 \times (7 + 2 + 9) \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= (9 + 271) + (9 + (27 + 1)) \\
 318 &:= (-1 + 7) \times (-2 + 9 + 17 + 29) &= ((9 \times 2) + (7 \times ((1 + 9) / 2))) \times (7 - 1) \\
 319 &:= -17 + 291 + (7 - 2) \times 9 &= ((9 + (27 \times 1)) \times 9) + ((2 - 7) \times 1) \\
 320 &:= -1 \times 7 + 291 + 7 + 29 &= (((9 + 27) - 1) \times 9) - ((2 - 7) \times 1) \\
 321 &:= (1 \times 72 + 91 - 7) \times 2 + 9 &= 9 + (2 \times (71 + (92 - (7 \times 1)))) \\
 322 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9 + 17 + 2 \times 9) &= (9 + 271) + ((9 - 2) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 323 &:= 17 \times (-2 + 9 - 17 + 29) &= (9 \times 2) + (71 + (9 \times (27 - 1))) \\
 324 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (29 + (1 + 7) \times 2) + 9 &= 9 \times ((27 - (1 - (9^2))) - 71) \\
 325 &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 + 172 + 9 &= (((9 + 27) \times 1) \times (9 + 2)) - 71 \\
 326 &:= 17 + 291 + 7 + 2 + 9 &= ((9 + 27) + (19^2)) - 71 \\
 327 &:= (-1 - 7 + 29) \times (1 + 7) \times 2 - 9 &= (((9 + 27) + 1) \times 9) + (2 - 7) - 1 \\
 328 &:= 17 \times 2 \times 9 \times 1 - 7 + 29 &= ((9 + 2) - 7) \times (1 + (9 \times ((2 + 7) \times 1))) \\
 329 &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 \times 1 + 7 \times 29 &= (((9 - 2) \times 7) \times 1) + 9 + 271 \\
 330 &:= 17 \times 29 - 172 + 9 &= ((9 \times 2) - 7) \times ((19 \times 2) - (7 + 1)) \\
 331 &:= (1 - 7) \times (2 - 91) - 7 \times 29 &= (((9 \times 27) + 19) - 2) + 71 \\
 332 &:= (-1 + 7 + 2 - 91) \times (7 - 2 - 9) &= (9 \times 2) + ((7 \times ((19 \times 2) + 7)) - 1) \\
 333 &:= (-1 + 72 - (9 + 1 + 7) \times 2) \times 9 &= (9 \times 2) - (((7 \times 1) \times 9) \times ((2 - 7) \times 1)) \\
 334 &:= 17 + 2 + 9 \times 17 \times 2 + 9 &= 92 + ((7 + 1) + (9 \times (27 - 1))) \\
 335 &:= 1 + 7 + 291 + 7 + 29 &= (((9 + (2 \times 7)) \times 1) \times 9) + (2^7) \times 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 336 &:= (1 + 7) \times (-2 + 9 - 1 + 7 + 29) &= (((9 \times 2) + (7 + 19)) - 2) \times (7 + 1) \\
 337 &:= (172 + 9 - 17) \times 2 + 9 &= (92 - (7 + 19)) + 271 \\
 338 &:= (17 - 2) \times 9 + 1 \times 7 \times 29 &= ((9 + (2 + 7)) - (1 - 9)) \times ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 339 &:= ((-1 + 7) \times 2 + 9) \times 17 - 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (27 + 1)) + ((9^2) + (7 - 1)) \\
 340 &:= -17 - 291 + 72 \times 9 &= 9 + ((271 - (9 + 2)) + 71) \\
 341 &:= 17 + 2 \times 9 + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9^2) + ((7 \times (1 + (9 + 27)))) + 1) \\
 342 &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 - 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= 9 \times ((27 + 19) - ((2 + 7) - 1)) \\
 343 &:= 172 + (91 - 72) \times 9 &= (9 \times (27 - 19)) + 271 \\
 344 &:= 172 + 91 + 72 + 9 &= ((9 \times 27) + 1) + ((92 + 7) + 1) \\
 345 &:= (-1 - 7 + 29) \times (1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 &= (9^2) - ((7 \times (1^9)) - 271) \\
 346 &:= 1 + (-7 + 29) \times 17 - 29 &= (92 + (7 \times 1)) - (9 - 2^{7+1}) \\
 347 &:= -1 \times 7 + 291 + 72 - 9 &= (9^2) + (7 \times ((1 + (9 + 27)) + 1)) \\
 348 &:= 1 - 7 + 291 + 72 - 9 &= 92 - ((7 - 192) - 71) \\
 349 &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times (9 \times 17 + 2 \times 9) &= ((9 - 27) + ((19^2) + 7)) - 1 \\
 350 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (29 - 1 - 7 + 29) &= ((9 - 27) + ((19^2) + 7)) \times 1 \\
 351 &:= 1 \times (7 - 2) \times (9 - 1) \times (7 + 2) - 9 &= (9^2) + (7 + (192 + 71)) \\
 352 &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times (9 - 1 + 7 - 2 + 9) &= (9 + ((27 \times (1 + 9)) + 2)) + 71 \\
 353 &:= 17 + 291 + (7 - 2) \times 9 &= (9 + 2^{7+1}) + (((9^2) + 7) \times 1) \\
 354 &:= -(1 - 72 + 9) \times (-1 + 7) - 2 \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) - (19 + 271) \\
 355 &:= 172 + 9 + (-1 + 7) \times 29 &= ((9^2) - (7 - 1)) + (9 + 271) \\
 356 &:= (1 + 72) \times (9 + 1 - 7 + 2) - 9 &= (9 \times 2) + ((7 + 19) \times ((2 \times 7) - 1)) \\
 357 &:= (-1 + 7 + 2 + 9) \times (-1 - 7 + 29) &= ((9 \times 2) \times ((7 \times 1) + 9)) - (2 - 71) \\
 358 &:= (1 + 7) \times 29 + 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 271) + 9) - (2 - 71) \\
 359 &:= -1 + 72 + (9 - 1) \times (7 + 29) &= (927 - 1) - ((9^2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 360 &:= -1 + 7 + 291 + 72 - 9 &= (9 - 27) \times ((1 - 92) + 71) \\
 361 &:= 1 \times 7 + 291 + 72 - 9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times 7) + (1 + (9 \times (27 - 1))) \\
 362 &:= (1 - 7 + 29) \times 17 - 29 &= (92 + 7) + (192 + 71) \\
 363 &:= 17 \times 2 \times (9 + 1) + 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (((9 \times 27) + 1) - 9) + (2^7)) \times 1 \\
 364 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-29 \times 1 + 72 + 9) &= ((9 \times 27) + 192) - 71 \\
 365 &:= -1 \times 7 + 291 + 72 + 9 &= (9 + 271) + (92 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 366 &:= 1 - 7 + 291 + 72 + 9 &= (9 \times 27) - (19 - (2 \times 71)) \\
 367 &:= (1 + 7) \times 29 + (17 - 2) \times 9 &= 9 + ((271 + (9^2)) + (7 - 1)) \\
 368 &:= -1 + 72 - 9 + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((92 + 7) \times ((1^9) + 2)) + 71 \\
 369 &:= 1 \times 72 - 9 + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= 9 + ((271 + (9 \times 2)) + 71) \\
 370 &:= 1 + 72 - 9 + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 - 2)/7) + (((19^2) + 7) + 1) \\
 371 &:= 17 + 291 + 72 - 9 &= ((9 \times (2 + 7)) + (19^2)) - 71 \\
 372 &:= (-1 + 7) \times (2 \times 9 - 1 + (7 - 2) \times 9) &= ((9 \times 27) + ((1^9) + (2^7))) \times 1 \\
 373 &:= -1 + (7 - 2) \times 91 - 72 - 9 &= ((9 \times 27) + ((1^9) + (2^7))) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 374 &:= 17 \times (2 - 9) + 17 \times 29 &= (92 \times 7) - (((1 + 9) \times 27) \times 1) \\
 375 &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 + (9 + 1) \times (7 + 29) &= (9 - (2 - (71 \times 9))) - 271 \\
 376 &:= -1 \times 7 + (29 - 1) \times 7 \times 2 - 9 &= 92 + ((71 \times (9 + (2 - 7))) \times 1) \\
 377 &:= (1 \times 7 - 2 - 9 + 17) \times 29 &= (9 \times (2 + 71)) - (9 + 271) \\
 378 &:= -1 + 7 + 291 + 72 + 9 &= (9^2) + ((7 + 19) + 271) \\
 379 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 \times 91 + 7 \times 29 &= 9 + ((2 + (71 \times 9)) - 271) \\
 380 &:= (-1 + 7 - 2 + 91) \times (-7 + 2 + 9) &= (9 \times ((2 + 7) + 19)) + 2^{7 \times 1} \\
 381 &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 \times (9 + 17) + 2 \times 9 &= (9 - 271) + ((92 \times 7) - 1) \\
 382 &:= -1 - 7 - 2 + (9 - 1) \times 7 \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 - ((2 - 7) - (19^2))) + (7 \times 1) \\
 383 &:= 172 + 9 - 1 + 7 \times 29 &= (92 \times 7) + (1 + (9 - 271)) \\
 384 &:= 1 - 72 + 91 \times (7 \times 2 - 9) &= (9 + (2^7)) + (19 \times ((2 \times 7) - 1)) \\
 385 &:= 172 + 9 + 1 + 7 \times 29 &= ((9 + 2) \times ((7 \times (1^9)) - 2)) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 386 &:= 1 + 7 + (29 - 1 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (27 + 19)) - (27 + 1) \\
 387 &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (2 - 7)) + ((19^2) + 71) \\
 388 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + (9 - 1) \times 7) - 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + (27 - 1)) \times 9) + (2 + 71) \\
 389 &:= 17 \times (2 + 9) - 1 + 7 \times 29 &= (9 + (2^7)) - (19 - 271) \\
 390 &:= (1 - 72 + 9) \times (1 - 7) + 2 \times 9 &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) + ((19^2) + (7 - 1)) \\
 391 &:= 17 \times (29 - 17 + 2 + 9) &= (9 \times (2 \times 7)) + ((19 \times (2 \times 7)) - 1) \\
 392 &:= (-1 - 7 + 2 \times (9 - 1)) \times 7 \times (-2 + 9) &= (((9 \times 2) - 7) + (19 \times 2)) \times (7 + 1) \\
 393 &:= 1 + 7 + 2 \times 91 + 7 \times 29 &= (9 + (((27 \times 1)/9) \times (2^7))) \times 1 \\
 394 &:= -1 \times 7 + (29 - 1) \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (9 + (((27 \times 1)/9) \times (2^7))) + 1 \\
 395 &:= 17 \times (29 - 1) - 72 - 9 &= 927 - (19 \times (27 + 1)) \\
 396 &:= (-1 + 7 + 29 + 1) \times (-7 + 2 \times 9) &= (9 \times 2) - (7 \times (19 - (2 + 71))) \\
 397 &:= 1 + (7 + 2 \times 9) \times 17 - 29 &= (((9 - 2) \times 71) - 92) - (7 + 1) \\
 398 &:= 17 \times 2 \times (9 - 1) + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + (271 - 9)) + (2^7)) - 1 \\
 399 &:= 1 - 7 + (29 + (1 + 7) \times 2) \times 9 &= ((9 + (271 - 9)) + (2^7)) \times 1 \\
 400 &:= -17 + 291 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + (271 - 9)) + (2^7)) + 1 \\
 401 &:= -17 \times 2 + (9 - 1 + 7) \times 29 &= ((92 \times 7) \times 1) - (9 \times (27 \times 1)) \\
 402 &:= (1 - 7 + 29) \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= ((9^2) + (7 \times (19 + 27))) - 1 \\
 403 &:= -1 \times (7 - 29) \times 17 + 29 &= ((9^2) + (7 \times (19 + 27))) \times 1 \\
 404 &:= (1 + 7 + 2 + 91) \times (-7 + 2 + 9) &= ((9^2) + (7 \times (19 + 27))) + 1 \\
 405 &:= (17 + (-2 + 9 \times 1 + 7) \times 2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (((2^7) + 1) - 92) + (7 + 1) \\
 406 &:= (-17 + 2 \times 9 + 1) \times 7 \times 29 &= (9 \times (27 + 19)) - ((2 + 7) - 1) \\
 407 &:= -(1 + 7) \times 29 + (-1 + 72) \times 9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times 7) + ((1 + 9) + 271) \\
 408 &:= 17 \times 2 \times (9 - 1 - 7 + 2 + 9) &= (((9 \times 2) + (7 \times 1)) + 9) \times (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 409 &:= 17 - (2 - 9 \times (1 - 7)) \times (2 - 9) &= ((9 + (2 \times 7)) \times 19) - (27 + 1) \\
 410 &:= -1 \times 7 + 291 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (92 + (71 - 9)) + 2^{7+1} \\
 411 &:= 17 \times 29 - 1 - 72 - 9 &= 9 - (2 - ((7 \times 19) + 271))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 412 &:= (1 \times 72 - 9 \times 1) \times 7 - 29 &= (9 + (2^7)) + (19 + 2^{7+1}) \\
 413 &:= 17 \times 29 + 1 - 72 - 9 &= (927 - (19 \times 27)) - 1 \\
 414 &:= (1 \times 7 - 2 \times (9 - 17)) \times 2 \times 9 &= 927 - ((19 \times 27) \times 1) \\
 415 &:= (1 + 72 + 9 + 1) \times (7 \times 2 - 9) &= (927 - (19 \times 27)) + 1 \\
 416 &:= (1 + 7) \times (-2 - 9 \times 1 + 72 - 9) &= ((9 + (2^7)) - (1 - 9)) + 271 \\
 417 &:= -(1 - 7) \times 2 + 9 \times 1 \times (7 - 2) \times 9 &= (92 - ((7 - 19) \times 27)) + 1 \\
 418 &:= -1 - 7 + 2 \times (9 + 1 + 7 \times 29) &= (9 + 2) \times ((7 + ((19 \times 2) - 7)) \times 1) \\
 419 &:= (17 - 2 + 9) \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 + ((19 \times 2) - 7))) + 1 \\
 420 &:= (1 - 7 + 29) \times 17 + 29 &= ((9 - 2) \times (7 - 19)) \times (2 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 421 &:= 17 \times 2 \times (9 + 1) + (7 + 2) \times 9 &= ((9 - 2) \times (((7 \times 1) \times 9) - 2)) - (7 - 1) \\
 422 &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 + (9 - 1 + 7) \times 29 &= (9 \times 2) + ((7 \times 19) + 271) \\
 423 &:= 1 \times 729 - 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (27 + 19)) + (2 + (7 \times 1)) \\
 424 &:= 1 \times 7 + 291 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (((9^2) - 7) - (19 + 2)) \times (7 + 1) \\
 425 &:= 1 + 7 + 291 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (92 + (71 - 9)) + 271 \\
 426 &:= 1 + 7 + (2 \times 9 + 1) \times (-7 + 29) &= 92 + (((7 \times 1) \times 9) + 271) \\
 427 &:= (-1 + 72 - 9) \times 1 \times 7 + 2 - 9 &= (9^2) - (((7 - (19^2)) + 7) + 1) \\
 428 &:= -1 + 7 \times (-2 - 9 - 1 + 72) + 9 &= ((9 + (2 \times 7)) \times 19) - ((2 + 7) \times 1) \\
 429 &:= -1 - 72 + 9 + 17 \times 29 &= (9^2) - (((7 - (19^2)) + 7) - 1) \\
 430 &:= -1 - 7 - 291 + 729 &= ((9 - 27) + (((1 - 9)^2) \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 431 &:= -1 \times 7 - 291 + 729 &= (((9 - 2) + 71) \times 9) - 271 \\
 432 &:= 1 - 7 - 291 + 729 &= (9 \times 2) \times (((7 - 1) - 9) + (27 \times 1)) \\
 433 &:= -17 + 2 \times 9 \times ((1 + 7) \times 2 + 9) &= 927 - (19 \times (27 - 1)) \\
 434 &:= 17 + 291 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 - 2) \times (((7 \times 1) \times 9) - 2)) + (7 \times 1) \\
 435 &:= (1 - 7 + 29 - 1 - 7) \times 29 &= (9 + 2) + ((71 - (9 \times 2)) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 436 &:= 1 \times 7 + (29 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= 9 + (((2 - 7) + (19^2)) + 71) \\
 437 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 - 9 \times 1 \times 7 \times (2 - 9) &= (9 + (2 - 71)) + ((9 - 2) \times 71) \\
 438 &:= (1 + 72) \times (-9 + 1 + 7 - 2 + 9) &= (92 - (7 - ((19^2) - 7))) - 1 \\
 439 &:= -1 + 7 - 2 + (9 - 1 + 7) \times 29 &= 92 - ((7 - ((19^2) - 7)) \times 1) \\
 440 &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times (9 - 1 + 7 + 29) &= ((9 \times (27 + 19)) + 27) - 1 \\
 441 &:= (17 + 29 + 17) \times (-2 + 9) &= (92 - 71) \times (92 - 71) \\
 442 &:= 1 - 72 \times (9 - 17 + 2) + 9 &= (9 \times (27 + 19)) + (27 + 1) \\
 443 &:= (1 - 7 - 2) \times 9 \times (1 - 7) + 2 + 9 &= (92 + (71 + 9)) + 271 \\
 444 &:= -1 - 7 + 2 + 9 \times (1 - 7 \times (2 - 9)) &= 9 - ((2 - 7) \times ((1 + 92) - (7 - 1))) \\
 445 &:= 1 \times 7 - 291 + 729 &= (92 \times 7) - ((192 + 7) \times 1) \\
 446 &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 + 1 - 7 \times 29 &= (9 - 2) + ((7 + (19^2)) + 71) \\
 447 &:= -17 + 29 \times 17 - 29 &= 9 - (2 \times (((7 - 1) - 9) \times (2 + 71))) \\
 448 &:= 1 \times (-72 - 9 + 17) \times (2 - 9) &= ((9 - 2) + 7) \times (((19 \times 2) - 7) + 1) \\
 449 &:= 1 + (-72 - 9 + 17) \times (2 - 9) &= 9 + (((27 \times 19) - 2) - 71)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 450 &:= (1 + 7 - 29 - 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 - (2 \times (7 - 192))) + 71 \\
 451 &:= -1 + (72 - 9 - 1) \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (27 - (((1 - 9) \times 2) - 7))) + 1 \\
 452 &:= (1 - 7) \times 2 + 91 \times (7 - 2) + 9 &= (92 \times (7 - 1)) - ((92 + 7) + 1) \\
 453 &:= (-1 + 7) \times (-2 + 91) - 72 - 9 &= ((9 + 2) - (7 + 1)) \times (9 + (2 \times 71)) \\
 454 &:= -1 + (7 - 2) \times 91 + 7 + 2 - 9 &= ((9 + 2) + ((7 - 1) \times ((9^2) - 7))) - 1 \\
 455 &:= 17 - 291 + 729 &= 9 - (2 - (719 - 271)) \\
 456 &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 9 \times (1 + 7 \times (-2 + 9)) &= (92 \times (7 + 1)) - (9 + 271) \\
 457 &:= 17 \times 29 \times 1 - 7 - 29 &= ((9^2) + 7) + (((19^2) + 7) + 1) \\
 458 &:= (-1 + 72) \times 9 - 172 - 9 &= (((9^2) \times 7) - (19 \times 2)) - 71 \\
 459 &:= -1 \times (7 - 2) + (9 \times 1 + 7) \times 29 &= 9 + ((2 + 719) - 271) \\
 460 &:= (1 - 72 + 91) \times (7 \times 2 + 9) &= (92 + (71 \times 9)) - 271 \\
 461 &:= 17 \times (29 + 1) + 7 \times (2 - 9) &= (9 + 2) + ((7 - 1) \times (((9^2) - 7) + 1)) \\
 462 &:= -1 - 7 + 2 + (9 + 17) \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times (7 + 19))) + (2 - (7 + 1)) \\
 463 &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + (9 + 17) \times 2 \times 9 &= (((9^2) \times (7 - 1)) - 9) - ((2 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 464 &:= (-1 \times 7 + 29 + 1 - 7) \times 29 &= ((92 \times (7 - 1)) - ((9^2) + 7)) \times 1 \\
 465 &:= (17 + 2 + 9) \times 17 - 2 - 9 &= (((927 + 19)/2) - 7) - 1 \\
 466 &:= -172 - 91 + 729 &= (((927 + 19)/2) - 7) \times 1 \\
 467 &:= -172 - 9 \times 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (((927 + 19)/2) - 7) + 1 \\
 468 &:= 17 \times 29 - 17 \times 2 + 9 &= ((9 - 27) \times ((1^9) - 27)) \times 1 \\
 469 &:= 17 \times 2 + (9 - 1 + 7) \times 29 &= ((9 - 27) \times ((1^9) - 27)) + 1 \\
 470 &:= (1 \times 72 - 9 \times 1) \times 7 + 29 &= (9 + 2) + ((7 + (1 + 9)) \times (27 \times 1)) \\
 471 &:= 17 \times 29 + 1 \times 7 - 29 &= 9 + (((2 \times 7) + 19) \times (2 \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 472 &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 + 9 - 1 - 7 \times (2 - 9)) &= ((9^2) \times 7) + ((19 \times (2 - 7)) \times 1) \\
 473 &:= (1 + 7 + 29 - 1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (((9 - 2) \times 71) - (9 \times 2)) - (7 - 1) \\
 474 &:= 17 \times (29 + 1) - 7 - 29 &= (9 - 271) + (92 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 475 &:= -17 + 2 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 - (2 \times 7)) \times (19 \times (2 - (7 \times 1))) \\
 476 &:= 17 \times (2 - 9) \times 1 \times (7 - 2 - 9) &= ((9 - (2 - ((7 \times 1) \times 9))) - 2) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 477 &:= (-1 + 7) \times (2 + 91) - 72 - 9 &= (9 \times (27 - 1)) + ((9 \times 27) \times 1) \\
 478 &:= -17 + (2 + 9 \times 1) \times (7 - 2) \times 9 &= (((9 \times 27) \times (1^9)) \times 2) - 7 - 1 \\
 479 &:= -1 \times 7 + 29 \times 17 + 2 - 9 &= (((927 + 19)/2) + 7) - 1 \\
 480 &:= 17 \times 2 \times 9 - (1 - 7) \times 29 &= (((927 + 19)/2) + 7) \times 1 \\
 481 &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times (-9 + 17 + 29) &= (((927 + 19)/2) + 7) + 1 \\
 482 &:= 1 - 7 - 2 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times (-2 + 9) &= (92 \times 7) + (1 - (92 + 71)) \\
 483 &:= -17 - 2 + 9 + 17 \times 29 &= (92 \times 7) - (19 + (2 \times 71)) \\
 484 &:= -172 + 9 - 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (((9^2) \times 7) - (1 + (9 + 2))) - 71 \\
 485 &:= -1 + (7 + 2) \times (-9 \times 1 + 72 - 9) &= (((9 - 2) \times 71) - (9 \times 2)) + (7 - 1) \\
 486 &:= (17 + 2 - 9 + 17) \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times 27) \times 1) + (9 \times (27 \times 1)) \\
 487 &:= (17 + 2 + 9) \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= (((92 + 7) \times (1 + 9))/2) - (7 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 488 &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 \times 9 + 17 \times 2 + 9) &= ((9 - 2) + ((7 - 1) \times 9)) \times (2 + (7 - 1)) \\
 489 &:= (1 - 7) \times (2 - 91) - (7 - 2) \times 9 &= (92 + 71) \times ((9 + (2 - 7)) - 1) \\
 490 &:= (1 \times 7 - 2 + 9) \times (-1 + 7 + 29) &= ((9 + 2) - (7 - 1)) \times (92 + (7 - 1)) \\
 491 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9) \times (-1 + 7) + 29 &= ((9 + 2) + ((7 - 1) \times (9^2))) - (7 - 1) \\
 492 &:= (1 - 7) \times 2 + (9 - 1) \times (72 - 9) &= ((9 - 27) + ((1 + 9)^2)) \times (7 - 1) \\
 493 &:= 1 \times 7 + 29 \times 17 + 2 - 9 &= (((9 \times 27) \times (1^9)) \times 2) + (7 \times 1) \\
 494 &:= 1 - 7 + 29 \times 17 - 2 + 9 &= 9 + (((27 \times 19) - 27) - 1) \\
 495 &:= (-1 + 7) \times (-2 + 91 - 7 + 2) - 9 &= (9 \times 27) - (19 - 271) \\
 496 &:= 17 \times (29 + 1) - 7 + 2 - 9 &= 92 + ((7 \times 19) + 271) \\
 497 &:= 1 \times 729 - (1 + 7) \times 29 &= (9/(2 + 7)) - (1 - ((9 - 2) \times 71)) \\
 498 &:= (-1 + 7) \times ((29 + 17) \times 2 - 9) &= (9 - 2) - ((7 - 1) - ((9 - 2) \times 71)) \\
 499 &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 \times (1 + 7 - 2) \times 9 &= (((9 - 2) \times 7) \times (1 + 9)) + ((2 + 7) \times 1) \\
 500 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 + (9 - 1) \times (72 - 9) &= 9 - (((2 \times 7) \times ((1 - 9) - 27)) - 1) \\
 501 &:= -17 + (2 + 9 \times (1 + 7)) \times (-2 + 9) &= (((9 - 2) + 7) + 1) + ((9^2) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 502 &:= 1 + 7 + 291 + 7 \times 29 &= ((9 + 27) \times (1 + 9)) + (2 \times 71) \\
 503 &:= -1 - 7 + 29 \times 17 + 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (2 + (71 - 9))) - (2 + 71) \\
 504 &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 \times 1 \times (-7 + 2 + 9) &= (9 \times (2 \times 7)) \times ((1 + (9 + (2 - 7)))) - 1) \\
 505 &:= -17 + 29 \times 17 + 29 &= (9 \times (27 - (1^9))) + 271 \\
 506 &:= -1 + 7 + 29 \times 17 - 2 + 9 &= (9 \times 27) + (192 + 71) \\
 507 &:= -(1 + 7) \times 2 + 91) \times 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((9^2) \times (7 - 1)) + (92 - 71) \\
 508 &:= (1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 7 \times 2 - 9) &= (((9^2) \times 7) + (1 + (9 + 2))) - 71 \\
 509 &:= 17 \times 2 \times 9 + 1 \times 7 \times 29 &= (9 - ((2 - 7) \times ((1 + 92) + 7))) \times 1 \\
 510 &:= 1 + 7 \times 29 + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 - (2 \times 71)) + ((92 \times 7) - 1) \\
 511 &:= (17 + 2 - 9 \times (1 - 7)) \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 - (2 \times 71)) + ((92 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 512 &:= (1 + 7) \times (29 + 17 + 2 \times 9) &= (((9 \times 2) - (7 + 19))^2) \times (7 + 1) \\
 513 &:= (1 - 7) \times (2 - 91 + 7 - 2) + 9 &= (((9 - 2)/7) \times 19) \times 27) \times 1 \\
 514 &:= -1 - 7 + 29 \times 17 + 29 &= (((9 - 2)/7) \times 19) \times 27) + 1 \\
 515 &:= -1 \times 7 + 29 \times 17 + 29 &= (9 + ((2 + 7) \times 1)) + ((9 - 2) \times 71) \\
 516 &:= 1 - 7 + 29 \times (1 \times 7 + 2 + 9) &= ((92 \times 7) \times (1^9)) - ((2^7) \times 1) \\
 517 &:= -1 + 72 + 91 \times (7 - 2) - 9 &= ((92 - 7) + (19^2)) + 71 \\
 518 &:= 17 \times 29 + (17 \times 2 - 9) &= (9 - (2 - (71 \times 9))) - ((2^7) \times 1) \\
 519 &:= 17 - 2 + 9 \times (1 + 7) \times (-2 + 9) &= (((9 \times 27) - 19) \times 2) + 71 \\
 520 &:= 1 - 7 \times (29 + 1) + 729 &= (9 + ((2 + (7 + 19)) \times 2)) \times (7 + 1) \\
 521 &:= -1 + (-7 + 29 \times 1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 + ((2 \times 7) + 1)) + ((9 - 2) \times 71) \\
 522 &:= 1 \times (-7 + 29 \times 1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= 9 \times ((2 \times (7 + 19)) - (2 - (7 + 1))) \\
 523 &:= 1 - 72 + 9 \times (-1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (9 + 271) + (9 \times (27 \times 1)) \\
 524 &:= -1 - 7 + (-2 + 9) \times (-1 + 7 \times (2 + 9)) &= (92 \times 7) + ((1 - 9) \times ((2 \times 7) + 1)) \\
 525 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 91) - 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 - 2) \times (((71 - 9) + (2 \times 7)) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 526 &:= 1 + 729 - 1 - 7 \times 29 &= (92 \times 7) + (((1 - (9 \times 2)) \times 7) + 1) \\
 527 &:= -1 \times 7 \times 29 + 1 + 729 &= (9 + (271 - 9)) + 2^{7+1} \\
 528 &:= 1 + 729 + 1 - 7 \times 29 &= ((9 \times 2) + (((7 + 1) \times 9) - 2)) \times (7 - 1) \\
 529 &:= (-1 + 7 - 2) \times 9 + 17 \times 29 &= (9^2) + (719 - 271) \\
 530 &:= -17 - 2 \times 91 + 729 &= (((9 \times 2) + 71) \times 9) - 271 \\
 531 &:= (-1 + 72) \times 9 + (1 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (92 + 7) + ((19^2) + 71) \\
 532 &:= (-1 \times 7 \times 2 + 91) \times 7 + 2 - 9 &= ((9 \times (27 + 1)) + 9) + 271 \\
 533 &:= 1 + (-7 \times 2 + 91) \times 7 + 2 - 9 &= ((9 - 2)/7) + (19 \times (27 + 1)) \\
 534 &:= (1 + 7 - 2) \times (9 - 1 + 72 + 9) &= (92 \times (7 - 1)) + (9 - (27 \times 1)) \\
 535 &:= (1 - 7 \times 2 + 91) \times 7 - 2 - 9 &= (((92 \times 7) + 19) - (2^7)) \times 1 \\
 536 &:= 17 \times 2 + 9 + 17 \times 29 &= 9 + ((2 \times 7) + (19 \times (27 \times 1))) \\
 537 &:= 1 + (7 - 2) \times 91 + 72 + 9 &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) + ((19 \times 27) + 1) \\
 538 &:= -1 + 7 + (2 - 9) \times (1 - 7 \times (2 + 9)) &= (((92 \times (7 - 1)) - 9) + 2) - (7 \times 1) \\
 539 &:= 17 + 29 \times 17 + 29 &= (((9 - 2) \times 7) \times 1) \times ((9 \times 2) - 7) \times 1 \\
 540 &:= (17 - 29 \times 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (92 + 719) - 271 \\
 541 &:= 1 + 72 \times (9 - 1) - 7 - 29 &= (9 \times (27 + 19)) + ((2^7) - 1) \\
 542 &:= -1 \times 7 + (-2 - 9 \times 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 + (271 - 9)) + 271 \\
 543 &:= -17 + 29 \times (17 + 2) + 9 &= ((9 \times (27 + 19)) + (2^7)) + 1 \\
 544 &:= 17 \times (29 - 1 - 7 + 2 + 9) &= ((9^2) + 719) - 2^{7+1} \\
 545 &:= 1 - 72 + (9 - 1) \times 7 \times (2 + 9) &= (((9 - 2) \times (7 \times 1)) \times (9 + 2)) + (7 - 1) \\
 546 &:= 17 \times (29 + 1) + 7 + 29 &= 9 + ((2 \times (7 \times 19)) + 271) \\
 547 &:= 1 + 7 + (-2 + 9) \times 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9) &= (92 \times (7 - 1)) + (9 - (2 \times (7 \times 1))) \\
 548 &:= 1 \times 729 - 172 - 9 &= ((9^2) \times (7 \times 1)) + (9 - (27 + 1)) \\
 549 &:= 1 + 729 - 172 - 9 &= 9 \times ((2 \times 7) + ((19 + 27) + 1)) \\
 550 &:= (-1 + 7 + 2 \times 9 + 1) \times (-7 + 29) &= (9 + 2) \times (71 - (92 - 71)) \\
 551 &:= (172 - 9 \times 17) \times 29 &= (92 \times (7 - 1)) - (9/(2 + (7 \times 1))) \\
 552 &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times (9 + 1 + 7 + 29) &= (((9 \times 2) - 7) - 19) \times (2 - 71) \\
 553 &:= -1 \times 7 \times (29 + (1 - 7) \times 2 \times 9) &= ((9 - 2) \times 71) + ((9 - 2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 554 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 - (9 + 1 - 72) \times 9 &= (((92 \times 7) - 1) - (9 \times 2)) - 71 \\
 555 &:= 1 + 7 - 2 \times 91 + 729 &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) + (19 \times (27 + 1)) \\
 556 &:= 17 \times 29 \times 1 + 72 - 9 &= (9 \times (27 + 19)) + (2 \times 71) \\
 557 &:= 17 \times (29 - 1) + 72 + 9 &= ((9 + ((27 - 1) \times 9)) \times 2) + 71 \\
 558 &:= (17 + (-2 + 9 \times 1 + 7)) \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 2) + 7) \times (((19 \times 2) - 7) \times 1) \\
 559 &:= -(1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) - 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (((9 + 2) + 7) \times ((19 \times 2) - 7)) + 1 \\
 560 &:= ((1 - 7) \times 2 + 91) \times 7 - 2 + 9 &= (9 + 271) + (9 + 271) \\
 561 &:= (-1 - 7 + 2 + 9) \times 17 \times (2 + 9) &= ((92 \times 7) - (1 + 9)) - (2 + 71) \\
 562 &:= 1 \times 72 \times (9 - 1) - 7 + 2 - 9 &= (((9^2) \times 7) - 1) - ((9 + (2 - 7)) \times 1) \\
 563 &:= (1 + 72 + 9) \times 1 \times 7 - 2 - 9 &= 9 + (((271 + 9) \times 2) - 7) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{564} &:= (1 - 7 \times 2 + 91) \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) - ((1 + 9) \times ((2 + 7) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{565} &:= -1 - 72 - 91 + 729 &= (((9^2) \times 7) - 1) + (9 - (2 + (7 + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{566} &:= 1 \times 729 - 172 + 9 &= ((92 \times 7) - 1) - ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{567} &:= 1 - 72 - 91 + 729 &= (((9 - (27 \times 1)) + 9)^2) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{568} &:= 1 - 72 + 9 \times 1 \times 72 - 9 &= (((9 - 2) \times ((7 \times 1) \times 9)) + (2^7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{569} &:= 1 + 72 \times 9 + 1 - 72 - 9 &= (92 \times 7) - ((1 + (9^2)) - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{570} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9 + 1) \times 7 - 2 \times 9 &= (92 \times (7 - 1)) - (9 - (27 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{571} &:= -1 - 7 \times (2 + 9) + 1 + 72 \times 9 &= ((9 + (2^{7-1} \times 9)) - (2 \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{572} &:= 17 - 2 - 91 + 72 \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) - ((1^{92}) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{573} &:= 17 \times 29 - 1 + 72 + 9 &= ((9 - 2) + (71 \times 9)) - (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{574} &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 + 17 \times 29 &= ((92 \times 7) + (1^{92})) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{575} &:= 17 \times 29 + 1 + 72 + 9 &= ((9 \times 2) - (7 \times 19)) \times (2 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{576} &:= (1 + 7 \times 2 + 9) \times (17 - 2 + 9) &= (9 + ((2 \times 7) + 1)) \times (((9 \times 2) + 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{577} &:= (-1 + 72) \times 9 + 1 - 72 + 9 &= (9 + 2) + ((71 \times 9) - (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{578} &:= 17 \times 2 \times (-9 + 1 + 7 + 2 \times 9) &= ((9 \times 2) + ((7 \times 1) \times (9^2))) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{579} &:= (1 - 7) \times (2 - 91) + (7 - 2) \times 9 &= 9 - (2 + (71 - ((92 \times 7) - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{580} &:= -1 \times 7 + (291 + 7) \times 2 - 9 &= (9 - 2) - (71 - ((92 \times 7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{581} &:= (1 + 72 + 9 \times 1) \times 7 - 2 + 9 &= ((9 + 2) + (71 \times 9)) + (2 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{582} &:= (-1 + 7) \times (2 + 91 - 7 + 2 + 9) &= (((9^2) + (7 - ((1 + 9)/2))) \times 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{583} &:= 1 \times 72 \times (-9 + 17) - 2 + 9 &= (92 \times 7) - (1 - (9 + (2 - 71))) \\
 \mathbf{584} &:= (1 + 72) \times (-9 - 1 + 7 + 2 + 9) &= ((9 - 27) - (1 - 92)) \times (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{585} &:= (1 - 7 - 2) \times 9 + (1 + 72) \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) + 1) + (9 + (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{586} &:= 1 - 72 + 9 \times 1 \times 72 + 9 &= ((9^2) \times (7 \times 1)) - (9 - (27 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{587} &:= 1 + 72 \times 9 + 1 - 72 + 9 &= ((92 \times 7) - ((1 + (9 - 2)) \times 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{588} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + 9 - 1) \times (7 - 2 + 9) &= ((9 + 2) + 719) - (2 \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{589} &:= -17 - 2 + 91 \times 7 - 29 &= ((92 \times 7) - ((1 + (9 - 2)) \times 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{590} &:= 1 \times 72 \times (9 - 1) + 7 - 2 + 9 &= ((9^2) \times (7 \times 1)) + (9 + ((2 \times 7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{591} &:= (1 \times 7 + 291 - 7) \times 2 + 9 &= 9 + (((27 \times 19) - 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{592} &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 + 9 \times 1 + 72 - 9) &= (92 \times 7) + ((1 + (9 \times 2)) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{593} &:= -1 - 72 + 91 \times 7 + 29 &= ((9 \times (2 + 71)) + 9) - (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{594} &:= -1 \times 72 + 91 \times 7 + 29 &= 9 \times (2 + (((7 \times 19) + 2) - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{595} &:= (1 - 7 \times 2 + 91 + 7) \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 - (2^7)) \times (((1^{92}) - 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{596} &:= 1 - 7 + (2 + 91 - 7) \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 + (2 \times (((7 - 1) \times (9 - 2)) \times 7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{597} &:= (1 - 7) \times (-2 + 9) + (-1 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 + (2 \times (((7 - 1) \times (9 - 2)) \times 7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{598} &:= -1 + 7 - 2 + 9 \times (-1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (92 \times 7) - (19 + (27 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{599} &:= (1 - 7 \times 2) \times (9 + 1) + 729 &= (9^2) + (7 \times ((1^9) + (2 + 71))) \\
 \mathbf{600} &:= (17 \times 2 - 9) \times (17 - 2 + 9) &= (((9^2) \times 7) - (19 \times 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{601} &:= -1 - 7 + 29 \times (-1 - 7 + 29) &= (((92 - 7) \times 1) \times (9 - 2)) + (7 - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{602} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 - 17 - 29 &= 92 + (((7 - 1) \times (92 - 7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{603} &:= (172 - 91 - 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= (92 + (71 \times 9)) - ((2^7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{604} &:= 1 + 729 \times 1 - 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (92 + (71 \times 9)) - ((2^7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{605} &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 \times 9 + 1 + 729 &= (9 + 2) + (((7 \times 1) + 92) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{606} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9 + 1) \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) - 1) - (9 + (27 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{607} &:= (17 \times 2 \times 9 - 1 \times 7) \times 2 + 9 &= ((92 \times 7) \times 1) - (9 + (27 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{608} &:= -1 + (-7 + 2 + 9 + 17) \times 29 &= ((9 + 2) - 7) \times (19 \times (2 + (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{609} &:= -1 - 7 - 2 + 91 \times 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((92 - 7) \times (1 + (9 - 2))) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{610} &:= 1 - 7 + (29 - 1) \times (-7 + 29) &= (9 \times 2) - (((7 \times 1) - (9^2)) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{611} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 - 1 - 7 - 29 &= (92 + 7) + ((19 \times 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{612} &:= 17 \times (2 + 9 + 17 \times 2 - 9) &= (9 - 27) \times (1 - (9 + (27 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{613} &:= 1 + 72 \times (9 - 1) + 7 + 29 &= ((92 \times 7) - ((19 \times 2) - 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{614} &:= 1 - 7 - 29 + 1 + 72 \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) - ((19 \times 2) - 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{615} &:= (-1 + 7) \times (-2 + 91) + 72 + 9 &= ((9 - 2) \times (7 - (1 - 92))) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{616} &:= (-1 \times 7 + 29) \times (17 + 2 + 9) &= (((9^2) + (7 - 1)) \times (9 - 2)) + 7) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{617} &:= 1 + 7 - 29 \times (1 + 7 - 29) &= (((9^2) + (7 - 1)) \times (9 - 2)) + (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{618} &:= 1 + 7 - 29 + (-1 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 - 2) + (((71 \times 9) - 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{619} &:= (-1 + 7 - 2) \times 9 \times 17 - 2 + 9 &= (9 - 27) - (((1 - 92) \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{620} &:= (1 \times 7 - 2) \times (9 \times 17 - 29) &= (((92 \times 7) - 1) - 9) - (2 \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{621} &:= 1 + (7 - 2) \times (9 \times 17 - 29) &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) \times (1 + ((9 \times 2) + (7 + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{622} &:= 17 + (291 + 7) \times 2 + 9 &= (92 \times 7) - (1 + (92 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{623} &:= 1 \times 7 + (29 - 1) \times (-7 + 29) &= 927 - ((19 \times 2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{624} &:= -1 \times 7 \times 2 - 91 + 729 &= (92 \times 7) + (1 - (92 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{625} &:= (1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9) \times (17 \times 2 - 9) &= ((9 \times 2) + 7)^{1927+1} \\
 \mathbf{626} &:= 1 + 7 - 29 - 1 + 72 \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) + (1 + (9 - 27))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{627} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 + (1 - 7) \times 2 - 9 &= ((92 \times 7) + (1 + (9 - 27))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{628} &:= 1 + 7 - 29 + 1 + 72 \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) + (1 + (9 - 27))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{629} &:= 1 \times 72 - 91 + 72 \times 9 &= (((92 \times 7) - 1) - 9) + (2 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{630} &:= (17 + 2 + 9 \times 1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 27) - 1) \times (9 + (2 + (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{631} &:= 1 + 72 + (-9 - 1 + 72) \times 9 &= ((9 + 27) \times (1 + 9)) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{632} &:= -1 + 72 \times 9 - 1 - 7 + 2 - 9 &= ((92 \times 7) \times (1^9)) - (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{633} &:= -1 - 7 - (2 - 91) \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (2 + 71)) - ((9 \times 2) + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{634} &:= (1 + 72) \times 9 - 1 + 7 - 29 &= ((9^2) + 7) - ((1 - 92) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{635} &:= 1 - 7 + (-2 + 91) \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times (2 \times 7)) + 1) \times (9 + ((2 - 7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{636} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 - 1 + 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) + 19) - (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{637} &:= 17 - 29 + 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (927 - 19) - 271 \\
 \mathbf{638} &:= 17 \times (29 - 1 + 7 + 2) + 9 &= (9 - (27 + 1)) + (9 \times (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{639} &:= -1 \times 7 - 2 - 9 + (1 + 72) \times 9 &= (((92 \times 7) - 1) - 9) - (2 - (7 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{640} &:= 1 + 72 \times (9 + 1) - 72 - 9 &= 9 - ((27 - 1) - (9 \times (2 + 71))) \\
 \mathbf{641} &:= 1 + 7 \times (2 + 91) + 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 2) + ((71 \times 9) - 2)) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{642} &:= -1 + 7 - 2 - 91 + 729 &= (92 - 71) - (9 \times (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{643} &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 - 91 + 729 &= ((92 \times 7) - 1) + ((9 - (2 + 7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{644} &:= 1 + 72 \times 9 - 1 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= (((92 \times 7) + (1 + 9)) - (2 + 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{645} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 + (1 - 7) \times 2 + 9 &= (((92 \times 7) + (1 + 9)) - (2 + 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{646} &:= 17 \times (2 \times (9 + 1) + 7 + 2 + 9) &= (((92 \times 7) + (1 + 9)) - (2 + 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{647} &:= -17 - 2 + 91 \times 7 + 29 &= (9 \times (27 + ((19 \times 2) + 7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{648} &:= 1 + 729 - 1 - 72 - 9 &= (9 \times (27 + ((19 \times 2) + 7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{649} &:= 1 + 729 \times 1 - 72 - 9 &= (9 \times (2 + (71 - 9))) + (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{650} &:= 1 - 72 - 9 + 1 + 729 &= ((9 \times 2) + (7 \times (1^9))) \times (27 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{651} &:= -1 - 7 + 2 + 9 \times 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (((92 \times 7) - 19) + 27) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{652} &:= (1 + 72) \times 9 - 1 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= (((92 \times 7) - 19) + 27) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{653} &:= 17 - 2 - 91 + 729 &= (9 - (2 - (719 - 2))) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{654} &:= 17 - 2 - 9 + 1 \times 72 \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) + (19 - (2 + 7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{655} &:= 17 \times 2 \times (91 - 72) + 9 &= (927 - (1^9)) - 271 \\
 \mathbf{656} &:= 17 \times 29 + 172 - 9 &= ((9 + 2) - 7) \times (1 + (92 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{657} &:= 17 + 2 - 91 + 729 &= 9 \times (27 + (19 + (27 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{658} &:= 1 + 72 \times (9 + 1) - 72 + 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 7)) + (19 \times (27 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{659} &:= -17 + 29 - 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (9 + 2) + ((71 \times 9) + (2 + (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{660} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 - 17 + 29 &= ((9 - 2) \times (7 \times 19)) - 271 \\
 \mathbf{661} &:= 1 + 72 \times 9 - 17 + 29 &= ((92 \times 7) \times 1) + ((9 + (2 + 7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{662} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 91) - 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (9 - 2) + (719 - 2^{7-1}) \\
 \mathbf{663} &:= 1 + 7 \times (2 + 91) - 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (((9 + 2) + 7) + 1) + ((92 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{664} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 9 + 1 + 72 \times 9 &= 927 - (192 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{665} &:= -1 - 72 + 9 \times 1 + 729 &= (9 - 271) + (927 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{666} &:= 1 + 729 - 1 - 72 + 9 &= 9 - ((271 - 927) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{667} &:= -17 + (2 \times 9 + 1) \times (7 + 29) &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) - ((1 - (92 \times 7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{668} &:= -1 + 72 \times 9 - 1 - 7 + 29 &= (92 \times 7) + (192/(7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{669} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 + (-1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 &= ((9 \times 2) + ((7 \times 1) + (92 \times 7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{670} &:= 1 \times (7 - 2) \times (9 - 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9) &= ((92 \times (7 \times (1^9))) + 27) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{671} &:= 1 - 7 + 29 + 1 \times 72 \times 9 &= ((92 \times (7 \times (1^9))) + 27) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{672} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 - 1 + 7 + 2 \times 9 &= ((92 \times (7 \times (1^9))) + 27) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{673} &:= -1 + 72 \times 9 + 1 - 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 27) - ((1 - 92) \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{674} &:= 172 + 9 + 17 \times 29 &= ((9 + 27) - ((1 - 92) \times 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{675} &:= 1 + 72 \times 9 + 1 + 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (927 + 19) - 271 \\
 \mathbf{676} &:= (-1 + 7 - 2 + 91) \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= (((9^2) \times 7) + (19 \times 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{677} &:= 1 + 7 \times (2 + 91) + 7 + 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 2) + (71 \times 9)) + (27 \times 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{678} &:= 1 - 7 + (2 \times 9 + 1) \times (7 + 29) &= ((9 \times (2 + 71)) + 92) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{679} &:= (1 \times 7 - 2 + 91) \times 7 - 2 + 9 &= (927 - (1 - 9)) - 2^{7+1} \\
 \mathbf{680} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 + 9 + (1 + 72) \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) - 1) + (9 + (27 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{681} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 + (1 + 72) \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) \times 1) + (9 + (27 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{682} &:= 17 + 2 \times 9 - 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (((9 - (27 - 1)) - 9)^2) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{683} &:= 1 \times 7 + 29 - 1 + 72 \times 9 &= 92 + ((719 - (2^7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{684} &:= 1 + 729 - 17 - 29 &= (9 + (2 - 7)) \times ((19 \times (2 + 7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{685} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 + 1 + 7 + 29 &= (927 \times 1) - ((9 \times 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{686} &:= 1 + 72 \times 9 + 1 + 7 + 29 &= 927 + (1 - ((9 \times 27) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{687} &:= -17 \times 2 - 9 + 1 + 729 &= ((92 - 7) \times (1 + (9 - 2))) + (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{688} &:= (-1 + 7 - 2) \times (9 + 172 - 9) &= 9 + (27 + (((1 + 92) \times 7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{689} &:= -1 + 7 \times (-2 + 91 + 7) + 2 \times 9 &= (9^2) - ((7 \times ((1 - (9^2)) - 7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{690} &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times (91 + 7 - 29) &= (92 \times 7) + (19 + (27 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{691} &:= -1 + 729 - 1 - 7 - 29 &= ((9 \times 2) \times 7) - (1 - (((9^2) \times 7) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{692} &:= 1 \times 729 - 1 - 7 - 29 &= (9 + (27 - 1)) + (9 \times (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{693} &:= 1 - 7 - 29 - 1 + 729 &= (9 \times (2 - ((7 - (1 - 9)) \times (2 - 7)))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{694} &:= -17 + (-2 + 9 \times 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) - ((19 + 2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{695} &:= 1 + 729 + 1 - 7 - 29 &= 9 + ((2 \times ((7 \times (1^9))^2)) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{696} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times (9 \times 1 - 7) \times 29 &= (((92 \times 7) - 1) - (9 \times 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{697} &:= 17 \times (29 - 17 + 29) &= (9 + 2) + ((7 \times 1) \times (92 + (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{698} &:= 1 - 7 + (2 + 9) \times (1 + 72 - 9) &= (9 \times 2) + (((7 + 1) \times (92 - 7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{699} &:= 1 + (-7 + 2) \times (-9 - 1) + 72 \times 9 &= (9 - 2) + (719 - (27 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{700} &:= -17 - 2 - 9 - 1 + 729 &= 9 - (2 - ((719 - 27) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{701} &:= (-1 + 72) \times 9 - 1 + 72 - 9 &= ((9^2) \times 7) + (1 - (9 - (2 \times 71))) \\
 \mathbf{702} &:= -17 - 2 - 9 + 1 + 729 &= (9 + 2) + ((719 - 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{703} &:= -17 \times 2 + 9 - 1 + 729 &= ((9 + 2) \times 71) - (9 - (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{704} &:= 1 + 7 + 29 \times (1 + 7 \times 2 + 9) &= ((92 \times 7) \times 1) - (9 + (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{705} &:= -17 \times 2 + 9 + 1 + 729 &= ((92 \times 7) + 1) - (9 + (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{706} &:= 1 \times 7 - 29 - 1 + 729 &= (9 \times 2) + ((7 + 1) \times (92 - (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{707} &:= 1 + 7 - 29 - 1 + 729 &= (9 + 2) + (((7 - 1) + (9^2)) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{708} &:= -17 + 29 \times (17 \times 2 - 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times (71 - 9)) + (27 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{709} &:= 1 + 7 - 29 + 1 + 729 &= (9 \times 2) + ((719 - 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{710} &:= (-1 + 72) \times (91 - 72 - 9) &= (9 - 27) - ((1 - 92) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{711} &:= 1 \times 729 \times 1 - 7 - 2 - 9 &= (9 \times 2) + ((719 - 27) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{712} &:= 17 + 2 + 9 \times 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9) &= (((9^2) \times (7 + 1)) - 9) + 2) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{713} &:= 1 + 72 \times 9 + 1 + 72 - 9 &= (9^{27 \times 1/9}) - (2 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{714} &:= 1 \times 729 - 1 - 7 + 2 - 9 &= (((9^2) - 71) + 92) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{715} &:= (-17 - 2 + 91 - 7) \times (2 + 9) &= 9 + ((2 + 719) - ((2 \times 7) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{716} &:= -172 + 917 - 29 &= ((92 \times 7) + (1^{92})) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{717} &:= 1 \times 729 + 17 - 29 &= (9 - 2) + ((71 \times (9 + 2)) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{718} &:= 17 - 29 + 1 + 729 &= (9 - 2) + ((719 - (2 + 7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{719} &:= -1 + 72 + 9 \times (1 + 72) - 9 &= 9 + (((27 - 19) + 2) \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{720} &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 \times (-1 + 72) + 9 &= ((92 \times 7) - 1) + ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{721} &:= -1 - 7 + (2 + 9 - 1) \times 72 + 9 &= (9 + 2) - (71 - ((9 + 2) \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{722} &:= -1 + 729 - 17 + 2 + 9 &= (9 \times 2) + ((719 - (2 \times 7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{723} &:= -1 + 729 - 1 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= ((92 + (71 \times 9)) - 2) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{724} &:= 1 \times 729 - 1 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= (9 \times 2) + ((719 - (2 \times 7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{725} &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 + 9 + 1 \times 729 &= ((9 + ((2 + 719) + 2)) - 7) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{726} &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 + 9 + 1 + 729 &= 9 + (2 + (71 + ((92 \times 7) \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{727} &:= -1 + 729 - 1 + 7 + 2 - 9 &= 927 - ((192 + 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{728} &:= -1 + 7 + 2 + (9 - 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (927 - 192) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{729} &:= 1 \times 729 \times 1 + 7 + 2 - 9 &= 9 \times (((27 - 19) + 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{730} &:= 1 + 729 \times (1 - 7 - 2 + 9) &= 92 - ((7 - 1) - (92 \times (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{731} &:= 17 \times (2 \times 9 + (1 + 7) \times 2 + 9) &= (9 \times 2) + (719 + ((2 - 7) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{732} &:= -(1 - 7) \times 2 + (9 - 1 + 72) \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) - 1) + ((9 \times 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{733} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + 9 \times 1 + 729 &= (9 \times 2) + (71 + ((92 \times 7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{734} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 - 9 + 1 + 729 &= (9 - 2) + ((719 + (2 + 7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{735} &:= 1 \times 729 + 17 - 2 - 9 &= (9 - 2) \times (((7 \times 19) - 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{736} &:= 17 - 2 - 9 + 1 + 729 &= (9 - 2) + ((719 + (2 + 7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{737} &:= 1 + 729 + (1 + 7) \times 2 - 9 &= (9 + 2) \times (((7 + 1) \times 9) + ((2 - 7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{738} &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times 9 \times 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (92 + 719) - (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{739} &:= 1 + (7 + 2) \times 91 - (7 + 2) \times 9 &= (92 + (71 \times 9)) + (2 + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{740} &:= -1 + 729 - 17 + 29 &= 9 + (((2 + 719) + 2) + (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{741} &:= 1 \times 729 - 17 + 29 &= (((92 + (71 \times 9)) + 2) + 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{742} &:= 17 + 29 \times (17 \times 2 - 9) &= 92 + (719 + (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{743} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 9 - 1 + 729 &= 927 - (192 - (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{744} &:= 1 \times 729 + 1 + 7 - 2 + 9 &= (92 \times (7 + (1^{92}))) + (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{745} &:= 1 + 729 + 1 + 7 - 2 + 9 &= (((9^2) + 7) \times 1) + (9 \times (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{746} &:= (1 \times 7 \times 2 + 91) \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= (9^2) + (((7 + 1) \times 92) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{747} &:= -1 - 72 + 91 + 729 &= (((9 - (27 - 1)) - 9)^2) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{748} &:= -1 \times 72 + 91 + 729 &= (((9 \times 2) \times ((7 - 1) \times (9 - 2))) - 7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{749} &:= -1 + 729 - 1 - 7 + 29 &= 92 + ((7 \times (1 + 92)) + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{750} &:= 1 \times 729 - 1 - 7 + 29 &= (((9 \times 2) \times ((7 - 1) \times (9 - 2))) - 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{751} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 + 91 + 72 \times 9 &= ((92 - 7) \times (1 + (9 - 2))) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{752} &:= 1 + 729 - 1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (((9^2) - 7) \times (1 + 9)) + (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{753} &:= 17 \times (29 + 17) - 29 &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) + ((1 + 9) \times (2 + 71))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 754 &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 \times 1 + 729 &= (92 \times (7 + 1)) - ((9 - 27) \times 1) \\
 755 &:= 1 + 7 + 2 \times 9 \times 1 + 729 &= (92 \times 7) - (((1 - 9) \times (2 \times 7)) + 1) \\
 756 &:= ((1 - 7) \times 2 - 9 \times (1 - 7)) \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 27) \times 1) \times (92 - 71) \\
 757 &:= 17 + 2 + 9 \times 1 + 729 &= ((92 \times (7 + 1)) + 92) - 71 \\
 758 &:= 1 \times (7 - 2) \times 9 \times 17 + 2 - 9 &= (9 + 2) + (719 + (27 + 1)) \\
 759 &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 + (9 + 17) \times 29 &= (((9 - 2) \times 71) - 9) + 271 \\
 760 &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + (9 + 17) \times 29 &= (9 \times 2) + (((7 + 1) \times 92) + (7 - 1)) \\
 761 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 \times 91 - 72) - 9 &= (9^2) + ((7 + 1) \times ((92 - 7) \times 1)) \\
 762 &:= 1 + 7 \times (2 \times 91 - 72) - 9 &= ((9 \times 2) + (7 + 1)) + (92 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 763 &:= 17 + 2 \times 9 - 1 + 729 &= (927 - (1 + 92)) - 71 \\
 764 &:= 17 + 2 \times 9 \times 1 + 729 &= (92 \times 7) - ((1 - 9) \times ((2 \times 7) + 1)) \\
 765 &:= 1 + 729 - 1 + 7 + 29 &= 927 + ((1 - 92) - 71) \\
 766 &:= 17 \times (-2 + 9) - 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (927 - 19) - (2 \times 71) \\
 767 &:= 1 + 7 + 29 + 1 + 729 &= (((9 + 2) \times 71) - (9 - 2)) - 7 \times 1 \\
 768 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 \times 9 \times (17 \times 2 + 9) &= (((9 + 2) \times 71) - (9 - 2)) - (7 - 1) \\
 769 &:= -1 - (7 - 29) \times (-1 + 7 + 29) &= (9 \times (2 \times (7 \times 1))) + ((92 \times 7) - 1) \\
 770 &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2 + 9) \times (17 + 2 \times 9) &= ((9^2) - (7 + 19)) \times (2 \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 771 &:= -1 + 7 + (2 \times 9 - 1) \times (7 - 2) \times 9 &= ((9 \times (2 \times 7)) + (1 + (92 \times 7))) \times 1 \\
 772 &:= 1 \times 729 + 17 \times 2 + 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 7)) + (1 + ((92 \times 7) + 1)) \\
 773 &:= 1 + 729 + 17 \times 2 + 9 &= (9 + (27 + 1)) + (92 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 774 &:= 17 + 29 - 1 + 729 &= 9 - ((2 - (71 \times 9)) - ((2^7) \times 1)) \\
 775 &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 \times 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (9^2) + (((7 \times 1) + 92) \times 7) + 1) \\
 776 &:= 1 + 729 + 17 + 29 &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times (1 + 9))) - ((2 - 7) - 1) \\
 777 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 91) + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (((92 \times 7) \times 1) - 9) + (2 \times 71) \\
 778 &:= 1 + 7 \times (2 + 91) + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= 9 - ((2 \times (7 - 1)) - ((9 + 2) \times 71)) \\
 779 &:= 1 + 729 - 1 \times 7 \times (2 - 9) &= (927 - ((19 + 2) \times 7)) - 1 \\
 780 &:= 1 + 7 \times (2 \times 91 - 72) + 9 &= (92 - (71 - 9)) \times (27 - 1) \\
 781 &:= (17 + 2 + 91) \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= (927 - ((19 + 2) \times 7)) + 1 \\
 782 &:= (17 + 29) \times (-1 + 7 + 2 + 9) &= (((9 + 2) \times 71) - (9 - 2)) + (7 + 1) \\
 783 &:= 1 \times 72 + (9 + 1) \times 72 - 9 &= ((9^2) \times 7) - ((1 - 9) \times (27 \times 1)) \\
 784 &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 + (1 + 72) \times 9 &= (92 + 719) - (27 \times 1) \\
 785 &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times (9 - 17) \times (2 - 9) &= 92 + (719 - (27 - 1)) \\
 786 &:= (1 + 7) \times (-2 + 91 + 7) + 2 \times 9 &= 92 + (((7 \times 1) \times (92 + 7)) + 1) \\
 787 &:= -(1 + 7 \times (2 - 9)) \times 17 - 29 &= ((9 + 2) \times ((7 + 1) \times 9)) + ((2 - 7) \times 1) \\
 788 &:= (17 + 2 + 91) \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (9 - 2) + (71 \times (((9 \times 2) - 7) \times 1)) \\
 789 &:= 17 + 2 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times (2 + 9) &= (9 \times 27) - ((1 - 92) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 790 &:= -1 + 72 - 9 - 1 + 729 &= ((92 \times 7) + (19 + (2^7))) - 1 \\
 791 &:= 1 \times 72 - 9 - 1 + 729 &= ((92 \times 7) + (19 + (2^7))) \times 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{792} &:= (1 \times 7 + 29 \times 1) \times (-7 + 29) &= (9 \times 2) \times ((7 + (1 + (9 + 27)))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{793} &:= 1 \times 729 + 1 + 72 - 9 &= (9 + (27 \times 19)) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{794} &:= 1 + 72 - 9 + 1 + 729 &= 92 + (((7 + 19) \times 27) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{795} &:= (1 + 7 \times 2) \times (-9 - 1 + 72 - 9) &= (9 - (2 - (719 - 2))) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{796} &:= 1 + 729 + (-1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (92 \times (7 - 1)) + ((9 \times 27) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{797} &:= -17 + (2 + 9 \times (1 + 7)) \times (2 + 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times ((7 + 1) \times 9)) - ((2 - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{798} &:= 1 + 7 + (2 + 9) \times (-1 + 72) + 9 &= (9 + ((2 + (71 \times (9 + 2))) + 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{799} &:= 17 \times (29 \times 1 + 7 + 2 + 9) &= 9 - ((2 - 719) - (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{800} &:= -1 + 72 \times (9 + 1) + 72 + 9 &= (92 + (71 \times 9)) - (2 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{801} &:= -17 - 2 + 91 + 729 &= (9 \times (2 + 71)) + ((9 \times 2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{802} &:= 172 + 91 \times 7 + 2 - 9 &= (92 + 719) - (2 + (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{803} &:= -1 \times 7 + (2 + 9 - 1) \times (72 + 9) &= (9 + 2) + ((719 + 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{804} &:= -1 - 7 + 2 + (9 + 1) \times (7 + 2) \times 9 &= (927 + 19) - (2 \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{805} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + 9 \times (1 + 7 + 2) \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) + (19 + (2 \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{806} &:= 1 + (7 + 2) \times 91 - 7 + 2 - 9 &= 927 - (192 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{807} &:= 17 - (2 + 9) \times (1 - 72) + 9 &= (9 - (2^7)) - (1 - (927 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{808} &:= -1 + (7 + 2) \times 9 - 1 + 729 &= 9 - (((2^7) + 1) - (927 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{809} &:= 1 \times 72 + 9 - 1 + 729 &= (927 + (1 + 9)) - 2^{7 \times 1} \\
 \mathbf{810} &:= 172 - 91 + 729 &= 9 \times (((27 - 1) - (9 - 2)) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{811} &:= 1 + 729 \times 1 + 72 + 9 &= ((9^2) - (7 - 1)) + (92 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{812} &:= 1 - 7 - 2 + 91 + 729 &= (9^2) + (719 + (2 \times (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{813} &:= 1 + (7 \times 2 - 9 - 1) \times 7 \times 29 &= (((9 \times 2) - (7 - 1)) - 9) \times 271 \\
 \mathbf{814} &:= (-1 - 7 - 2 + 91 - 7) \times (2 + 9) &= ((92 \times (7 + 1)) + 9) - (2 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{815} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + 9) \times 17 - 2 \times 9 &= (92 + 71) \times (9 + ((2 - 7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{816} &:= 1 + 7 \times (-2 + 9) \times 17 - 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times 2) - ((7 \times 19) \times ((2 - 7) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{817} &:= 1 \times 729 + (1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= 92 + (((719 - 2) + 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{818} &:= -1 + 7 + 2 + 91 \times (7 + 2) - 9 &= (927 - (19 \times 2)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{819} &:= (1 \times 72 + 91 - 72) \times 9 &= (92 + ((719 + 2) + 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{820} &:= 172 + 91 \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= (92 + 719) + (2 + (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{821} &:= -1 + 72 \times 9 - (1 - 7) \times 29 &= 9 - (((2 + 7) \times (1 - 92)) + 7) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{822} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + 9) \times 17 - 2 - 9 &= 92 + (((7 + 1) \times 92) - 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{823} &:= (1 + 72 - 9) \times (-1 + 7 \times 2) - 9 &= (9^2) + (((7 + 1) \times 92) + 7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{824} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 + 9 \times (1 + 7 + 2) \times 9 &= 92 + ((719 + (2 \times 7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{825} &:= -1 + 72 + (9 + 17) \times 29 &= (92 + (719 + (2 \times 7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{826} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 91 + 729 &= (92 + (719 + (2 \times 7))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{827} &:= (-1 + 7) \times (2 \times 9 + 1) \times 7 + 29 &= (9^2) + ((719 + 27) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{828} &:= 1 - 72 + 917 - 2 \times 9 &= ((927 \times 1) - 92) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{829} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 + 91 + 729 &= (927 \times 1) - (92 + (7 - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{830} &:= 1 + 72 \times 9 + 172 + 9 &= (((9^2) \times 7) + 192) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{831} &:= 17 + (2 + 9 \times (1 + 7)) \times (2 + 9) &= 927 + (((1 - 9) \times 2) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{832} &:= -1 + 7 \times (-2 + 9) \times (-1 + 7 + 2 + 9) &= ((92 - 7) + 19) \times (2 + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{833} &:= -1 - 72 + 917 - 2 - 9 &= (9 - 2) \times ((7 \times 19) - (2 \times (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{834} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 + 91 + 729 &= 927 - (((1 + 9)^2) - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{835} &:= 17 - 2 + 91 + 729 &= (927 - (19 + 2)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{836} &:= (1 + 7 + 29 + 1) \times (-7 + 29) &= (9 \times (2 - ((7 + (1 - 92)) - 7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{837} &:= -1 - 72 + 917 + 2 - 9 &= 92 + ((719 + 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{838} &:= 172 + 9 + (1 + 72) \times 9 &= (92 + 719) + (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{839} &:= 17 + 2 + 91 + 729 &= 927 - ((19 - 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{840} &:= (17 - 2 + 9) \times (-1 + 7 + 29) &= 927 + (((1 - 9) \times 2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{841} &:= (1 + 72 - 9) \times (-1 + 7 \times 2) + 9 &= ((9 + ((2^7) - (19 - 2))) \times 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{842} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times (9 - 1) + 729 &= (927 + 1) - (92 - (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{843} &:= 17 - 2 + 91 \times (7 + 2) + 9 &= ((927 \times 1) - 92) + (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{844} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + 9) \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= 9 + ((2 + (7 \times ((19 - 2) \times 7))) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{845} &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times 9 - 1 + 729 &= (9 \times (2 \times ((7 - 1) \times 9))) - ((2^7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{846} &:= (17 \times 2 + 91) \times 7 - 29 &= 927 + ((1 - 9) - (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{847} &:= 17 \times (-2 + 9) - 1 + 729 &= (9 + 271) + ((9^2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{848} &:= (1 + 7) \times (-2 + 9 \times (-17 + 29)) &= ((927 - 1) - ((9 + 2) \times 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{849} &:= -1 + 7 \times 29 - 1 + 72 \times 9 &= 9 - (((2 - 71) + 9) \times 2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{850} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 - 1 + 7 \times 29 &= (927 + (1 - (9 - 2))) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{851} &:= -1 - 72 + 917 - 2 + 9 &= ((927 - 1) - (9^2)) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{852} &:= 1 + (7 \times 2 - 9) \times 172 - 9 &= 927 - (1 + (((9^2) - 7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{853} &:= 1 - 72 + 917 - 2 + 9 &= (9 - 2) + ((719 + (2^7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{854} &:= 1 + 7 + (-2 + 91 + 7 - 2) \times 9 &= ((9 - 2) + (719 + (2^7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{855} &:= -1 - 72 + 917 + 2 + 9 &= ((9 - 2) + (719 + (2^7))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{856} &:= 1 + 729 \times 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= 9 + (271 + (9 \times 2^{7-1})) \\
 \mathbf{857} &:= 1 - 72 + 917 + 2 + 9 &= (927 + (1^{92})) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{858} &:= (-1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) \times (-1 + 7 - 2 + 9) &= (9 + 2) + (7 \times (192 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{859} &:= -1 + (7 - 2) \times (91 + 72 + 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times 71) + (9 - (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{860} &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 \times (9 + 1 - 72) - 9 &= (92 \times 7) - ((1 - 9) \times (27 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{861} &:= (-17 + 2 \times (9 + 1) \times 7) \times (-2 + 9) &= ((9 \times (2 + 7)) - 1) + ((9 + 2) \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{862} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 \times 9 + 1) + 729 &= 9 - (2 + ((71 - 927) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{863} &:= 1 + 7 \times (2 \times 9 + 1) + 729 &= ((9 + 2) + 71) + ((9 + 2) \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{864} &:= (1 \times 7 + 2) \times (91 + 7) - 2 \times 9 &= (927 + (1 + 9)) - (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{865} &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times 91 + (-7 + 2) \times 9 &= (9 \times 27) + (1 - (9 \times (2 - 71))) \\
 \mathbf{866} &:= 17 \times 2 \times (9 + 17) - 2 \times 9 &= (9 + (2 - (71 - 927))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{867} &:= 17 \times (-2 - 9 - 1 + 72 - 9) &= (9 + (2 - (71 - 927))) \times 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 868 &:= (-1 + 72 - 9) \times 1 \times (7 - 2 + 9) &= (9 + 2) - ((71 - 927) - 1) \\
 869 &:= 1 - 7 + (2 - 9) \times (1 - 7 \times 2 \times 9) &= ((9^2) + 719) - (2 - 71) \\
 870 &:= (1 - 7 + 2 + 9) \times (-1 + 7) \times 29 &= ((9^2) + ((71 \times (9 + 2)) + 7)) + 1 \\
 871 &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times (-9 - 1 + 7 \times (2 + 9)) &= (927 \times 1) - ((9 - 2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 872 &:= -1 - 72 + (91 + 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= ((9 + 2) + 719) + (2 \times 71) \\
 873 &:= (17 - 2 + 91 - 7 - 2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (27 + ((1^9) - (2 - 71))) \\
 874 &:= -1 \times 7 \times 2 + 917 - 29 &= ((9 - 2) \times ((7 \times 19) + 2)) - 71 \\
 875 &:= 1 - 72 + 917 + 29 &= (9 \times (2 \times ((7 \times (1^9))^2))) - (7 \times 1) \\
 876 &:= (1 - 7) \times 2 \times (-91 + 7 + 2 + 9) &= 927 + (((1 + 9) \times 2) - 71) \\
 877 &:= 17 \times 2 \times (9 + 17) + 2 - 9 &= ((927 + 19) + 2) - 71 \\
 878 &:= -1 - 7 - 2 + 917 - 29 &= 9 + (((2^7) + ((1 - 9)/2)) \times 7) + 1) \\
 879 &:= -1 \times 7 - 2 + 917 - 29 &= ((9 \times 27) - ((1 - 92) \times 7)) - 1 \\
 880 &:= 1 - 7 - 2 + 917 - 29 &= (92 + (7 \times 1)) + ((9 + 2) \times 71) \\
 881 &:= 1 + (72 - 9 + 17) \times (2 + 9) &= 927 - ((19 + 27) \times 1) \\
 882 &:= -1 - 7 + 2 + 917 - 29 &= 927 - ((19 + 27) - 1) \\
 883 &:= 1 + (7 + 2) \times 91 + 72 - 9 &= (927 \times 1) + ((9 \times (2 - 7)) + 1) \\
 884 &:= -1 - 7 \times 2 + 917 - 2 \times 9 &= (92 + 719) + (2 + 71) \\
 885 &:= -1 \times 7 \times 2 + 917 - 2 \times 9 &= ((92 - (7 + 1)) \times 9) + ((2^7) + 1) \\
 886 &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 + 917 - 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times 27) - ((1 - (92 \times 7)) \times 1) \\
 887 &:= -17 - 2 + 917 - 2 - 9 &= (9 \times 27) - (1 - ((92 \times 7) + 1)) \\
 888 &:= (1 + 7 + 29) \times (1 + 7 \times 2 + 9) &= (92 \times (7 + 1)) + ((9^2) + 71) \\
 889 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2) \times (91 + 7) - 2 + 9 &= ((9 \times 27) + 1) + ((92 \times 7) + 1) \\
 890 &:= -17 \times 2 + 917 - 2 + 9 &= (((927 - 1) - 9) - 27) \times 1 \\
 891 &:= 172 - 9 - 1 + 729 &= (9 \times (27 - 1)) + (9 \times (2 + 71)) \\
 892 &:= 1 \times 72 + 91 + 729 &= 927 + ((1 - 9) - (27 \times 1)) \\
 893 &:= 1 + 72 + 91 + 729 &= (927 + 1) - (9 + (27 - 1)) \\
 894 &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 917 - 29 &= 927 + ((19 \times 2) - 71) \\
 895 &:= -1 - 7 \times 2 + 917 + 2 - 9 &= 927 + (((1 - 9)/2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 896 &:= -1 \times 7 \times 2 + 917 + 2 - 9 &= (9 + ((27 \times 1) + 92)) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 897 &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 + 917 - 29 &= (927 - (19 \times 2)) + (7 + 1) \\
 898 &:= 1 + 7 + 2 + 917 - 29 &= (927 - 19) - ((2 + 7) + 1) \\
 899 &:= (1 + 7 + 29 + 1 - 7) \times 29 &= 927 - ((1^9) + (27 \times 1)) \\
 900 &:= (17 + 2 + 9 \times 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 + 2) + (7 \times (1 + ((9 \times 2) \times (7 \times 1)))) \\
 901 &:= -1 - 7 + (29 \times 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (927 \times (1^9)) - (27 - 1) \\
 902 &:= 17 \times 2 \times (9 + 17) + 2 \times 9 &= (927 + ((1^9) - 27)) + 1 \\
 903 &:= -1 - 7 + 2 \times 91 + 729 &= 927 - (192/(7 + 1)) \\
 904 &:= (17 \times 2 + 91) \times 7 + 29 &= (927 - (19 - 2)) - (7 - 1) \\
 905 &:= (1 \times 7 \times 2 - 9) \times (172 + 9) &= (927 - (1 + 92)) + 71
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{906} &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times 91 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= (927 + 1) - ((9 + (2 \times 7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{907} &:= 17 + 2 + 917 - 29 &= (9 - 27) - (1 - (927 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{908} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 + 917 - 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 2) \times (71 + 9)) + (27 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{909} &:= 1 + 7 + 2 + 917 - 2 \times 9 &= (927 + ((1 + 9) - 27)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{910} &:= 172 + (9 + 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (927 + ((1 + 9) - 27)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{911} &:= 1 + 729 + 172 + 9 &= ((9 - 27) + 1) + (927 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{912} &:= (-1 + 7) \times (-29 + 172 + 9) &= (927 - (1 + 9)) + ((2 - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{913} &:= -17 + 2 + 917 + 2 + 9 &= (927 - (1 + 9)) + ((2 - 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{914} &:= 17 - 2 + 917 - 2 \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) + (((1 + 9) \times 27) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{915} &:= (1 + 7 - 2) \times (9 \times 17 - 2) + 9 &= 927 + (((1 - 9)/2) - (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{916} &:= 1 + 7 + 2 + 917 - 2 - 9 &= (927 - (19 - 2)) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{917} &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times (9 + 1) \times 7 - 2 + 9 &= (9 - (2 - (71 \times 9))) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{918} &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2 \times (9 - 1) - 7 - 2) \times 9 &= (927 - 19) + ((2 + 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{919} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + 917 - 2 + 9 &= (9 \times (2 + 71)) - (9 - 271) \\
 \mathbf{920} &:= (-1 + 7 - 2) \times (9 + 1) \times (7 \times 2 + 9) &= (927 - (1^{92})) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{921} &:= -1 \times 7 \times 2 + 917 + 2 \times 9 &= (927 - (1 + 9)) - ((2 - 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{922} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 + 917 + 2 - 9 &= (927 - (1 + 9)) - ((2 - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{923} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + 917 + 2 + 9 &= 9 + ((271 + (92 \times 7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{924} &:= (1 - 7) \times (2 - 9 \times 17) + 2 \times 9 &= (927 + (((1 + 9)/2) - 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{925} &:= 17 + 2 + 917 - 2 - 9 &= (927 + 1) - ((9 \times 2)/(7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{926} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 + 917 + 2 - 9 &= 927 - (1^{9271}) \\
 \mathbf{927} &:= 1 \times (7 - 2 + 9 - 1) \times 72 - 9 &= 927 \times (1^{9271}) \\
 \mathbf{928} &:= (1 + 7 - 2 + 9 + 17) \times 29 &= 927 + (1^{9271}) \\
 \mathbf{929} &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 + 917 - 2 + 9 &= (927 + (1^{927})) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{930} &:= (1 + 7 - 2 + 9) \times (-1 + 72 - 9) &= (927 + 19) - (2 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{931} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 29 - 1 + 729 &= (((9 + 2) - 7) - (1 - 927)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{932} &:= -1 \times 7 \times 2 + 917 + 29 &= (927 - (1^{92})) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{933} &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 + 917 + 29 &= (9^2) + (71 \times ((9 \times 2) - (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{934} &:= 1 + 729 + 1 + 7 \times 29 &= (92 \times 7) + (19 + 271) \\
 \mathbf{935} &:= (1 - 7 + 2 + 9) \times 17 \times (2 + 9) &= (92 - 7) \times (19 - (2 + (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{936} &:= -1 - 7 - 2 + 917 + 29 &= (927 + (19 - 2)) - (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{937} &:= -1 + 7 \times (-29 + 172 - 9) &= (9 \times (2 + 71)) + (9 + 271) \\
 \mathbf{938} &:= -1 + 7 \times (29 + 1) + 729 &= (927 + (19 - 2)) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{939} &:= 1 + 7 \times (-29 + 172 - 9) &= (((9 - 2) + 7) - (1 - 927)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{940} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 + 917 - 2 + 9 &= (927 + 1) + ((9 \times 2) - (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{941} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 917 + 2 \times 9 &= (((9 - 2) + 7) - (1 - 927)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{942} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 + 917 + 2 + 9 &= 9 - ((2 - ((7 + 1) + 927)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{943} &:= (17 + 2 + 9) \times 17 \times 2 - 9 &= (9 + 2) + (7 - (1 - (927 - 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{944} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 + 917 + 2 \times 9 &= (((9 + 2) + (7 \times 1)) + 927) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{945} &:= 17 \times (2 + 9 \times (-1 + 7)) + 2 - 9 &= (((9 + 2) + (7 \times 1)) + 927) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{946} &:= 1 + (7 - 2 + 9 - 1) \times 72 + 9 &= (927 + (1 - 9)) + (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{947} &:= 17 + 2 + 917 + 2 + 9 &= (9 + 2) + (((7 + 1) + 927) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{948} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 + 917 + 2 \times 9 &= 92 - (71 - (927 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{949} &:= (1 + 72) \times (-9 \times 1 - 7 + 29) &= 92 - (71 - (927 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{950} &:= -1 + 7 - 2 + 917 + 29 &= (927 + (19 - 2)) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{951} &:= (1 - 72 - 9) \times (1 - 7) \times 2 - 9 &= 927 + (192/(7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{952} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 917 + 29 &= (927 + (19 - 2)) + (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{953} &:= -1 + (72 + (9 + 1 + 7) \times 2) \times 9 &= 92 + (719 + (2 \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{954} &:= -1 + 7 + 2 + 917 + 29 &= 9 + ((27 \times 1) \times ((9 + 27) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{955} &:= 17 \times 2 \times 9 + 1 + 72 \times 9 &= 927 + ((1^9) + (27 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{956} &:= 1 + 7 + 2 + 917 + 29 &= (((927 + 19) + 2) + 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{957} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2) - 9 &= (927 + (19 \times 2)) - (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{958} &:= 1 + 7 \times (-2 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2) - 9 &= 927 + ((19 \times 2) - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{959} &:= 17 \times (2 + 9 \times (-1 + 7)) - 2 + 9 &= 927 - (((1 - 9)/2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{960} &:= (1 - 7) \times 2 + 9 \times (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (927 - (19 \times 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{961} &:= 17 - 2 + 917 + 29 &= (9 + 27) - ((1 - 927) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{962} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 + 917 + 29 &= 927 - ((1 - 9) - (27 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{963} &:= -1 \times 7 - 2 + 9 \times (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (927 + 1) + (9 + (27 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{964} &:= 1 + (72 + 9) \times (-1 + 7) \times 2 - 9 &= (9 + ((27 \times 1) + 927)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{965} &:= 17 + 2 + 917 + 29 &= ((9^2) \times (7 + ((1 + 9)/2))) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{966} &:= (-1 - 7 + 29) \times (17 + 29) &= (9 - (2 - (71 - 9))) \times ((2 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{967} &:= -1 + (72 + 9 \times 1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (9 - 2) + ((71 + 9) \times (2 \times (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{968} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 + 9 \times (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (927 - 1) + ((9 - 2) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{969} &:= 17 \times (29 + 17 + 2 + 9) &= 9 + ((2 + (71 - 9)) \times ((2 \times 7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{970} &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times (9 + (1 + 7) \times (2 + 9)) &= (9^2) + (7 \times (1 + ((9 \times 2) \times (7 \times 1)))) \\
 \mathbf{971} &:= 1 - 7 + 29 \times 17 \times 2 - 9 &= (927 \times 1) - ((9 \times (2 - 7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{972} &:= 1 + 72 + 917 - 2 \times 9 &= ((927 + 19) + 27) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{973} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times (9 + 1) \times 7 + 2 - 9 &= ((927 + 19) + 27) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{974} &:= -1 + 7 + (2 + 9) \times (1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= ((927 + 19) + 27) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{975} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2) + 9 &= ((9 - 2) \times (7 \times 1)) + (927 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{976} &:= (1 + 7 \times 2 \times (9 + 1)) \times 7 - 2 - 9 &= ((9 + 2) - 7) \times (1 + (9 \times (27 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{977} &:= -1 + 72 + 917 - 2 - 9 &= (927 - (19 + 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{978} &:= (17 - 2 - 9) \times (172 - 9) &= 927 - (((1 + 9) \times 2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{979} &:= (1 \times 72 + 9 + 1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= ((9 \times 27) \times 1) + (92 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{980} &:= (-1 + 7 + 29) \times (17 + 2 + 9) &= ((9^2) \times (7 + ((1 + 9)/2))) + (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{981} &:= (17 + 2 + 91) \times (7 + 2) - 9 &= 9 - (27 \times (1 - (9 + (27 + 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{982} &:= 1 \times 72 + 917 + 2 - 9 &= (927 + ((1 - 9) \times 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{983} &:= 1 + 72 + 917 + 2 - 9 &= (927 \times 1) + ((9 - 2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{984} &:= (1 + 72 + 9) \times (-17 + 29) &= ((92 - 7) + (19 \times 2)) \times (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{985} &:= (-1 + 72) \times (9 \times 1 + 7 - 2) - 9 &= (((92 + 7) \times (1 + 9)) + 2) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{986} &:= 17 \times (-2 \times 9 - 1 + 7 \times (2 + 9)) &= ((927 - 1) - (9 + 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{987} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times (9 + 1) \times 7 - 2 + 9 &= (927 \times 1) - (9 + (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{988} &:= -1 \times 7 + 29 \times 17 \times 2 + 9 &= (927 + 1) - (9 + (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{989} &:= 1 - 7 + 29 \times 17 \times 2 + 9 &= (9 \times ((2^7) - (1 + (9 \times 2)))) + (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{990} &:= (17 + 29 - 1) \times (-7 + 29) &= (927 - 1) - (9 - (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{991} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times (9 + 1) \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= (927 \times 1) - (9 - (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{992} &:= 172 + 91 + 729 &= (927 + (1 - (9 - 2))) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{993} &:= (1 + 72 + 9) \times (-1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 &= (9 \times ((2^7) - 19)) + (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{994} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + 9 \times (1 + 7 \times 2) + 9) &= (927 + ((1 - 9)/2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{995} &:= 17 \times ((-2 + 9) \times (1 + 7) + 2) + 9 &= 927 - ((1^9) + (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{996} &:= 1 \times 72 + 917 - 2 + 9 &= ((927 \times (1^9)) - 2) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{997} &:= 17 + 2 \times (9 + 1) \times 7 \times (-2 + 9) &= 9 - ((2 - 719) - 271) \\
 \mathbf{998} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times (9 + 1) \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) + (((19^2) - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{999} &:= (17 + 2 + 91) \times (7 + 2) + 9 &= (927 + (1^{92})) + 71
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1000} &:= (-1 + 7 - 2) \times (9 + 1) \times (7 + 2 \times 9) &= ((92 + 7) + 1) \times ((9^2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1001} &:= 1 - 729 + 1729 &= (9 + 2) + (719 + 271) \\
 \mathbf{1002} &:= 1 \times 7 + 29 \times 17 \times 2 + 9 &= (92 + (71 \times 9)) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{1003} &:= -17 + 291 + 729 &= (927 - 1) + (((9 + 2) \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1004} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 + (9 - 1) \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 - 2) + (71 + 927)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1005} &:= (1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9) \times (1 + 7) - 2 - 9 &= ((9 - 2) + (71 + 927)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1006} &:= -1 \times 72 + (91 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (927 + 1) + (9 - (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1007} &:= (172 - 9) \times (-1 + 7) + 29 &= (9 \times (((2 \times 7) \times 1) \times 9)) - ((2^7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1008} &:= (1 + 7 \times (2 - 9)) \times (1 + 7 - 29) &= 927 - ((1 - 9) - (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1009} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times (-9 \times 1 + 72 + 9) &= (9 \times (2 + (71 + 9))) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{1010} &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times (9 \times (1 + 7) + 29) &= 92 - ((7 + 1) - (927 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1011} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times 91 - 72 - 9 &= (((927 \times 1) + 92) - 7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1012} &:= (1 + (7 - 2 + 9 - 1) \times 7) \times (2 + 9) &= 92 \times (71 + (9 + (2 - 71))) \\
 \mathbf{1013} &:= -1 \times 7 + 291 + 729 &= ((927 + 1) + 92) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1014} &:= 1 - 7 + 291 + 729 &= 927 - (((1 - 9) \times 2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1015} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 \times 1 \times 7 - 2 + 9 &= 927 + ((19 - 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1016} &:= 1 + (7 + 2 + 9 + 17) \times 29 &= (92 \times (7 + 1)) + (9 + 271)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1017} &:= -1 + 72 + 917 + 29 &= & (((9 + (2 \times 7)) \times 1) + 9)^2 - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1018} &:= 1 + 72 + (91 + 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= & ((9 + 2) + ((7 + 1) \times (9 \times (2 \times 7)))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1019} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 \times 1 \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= & ((927 + 19) + 2) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1020} &:= (1 + 7 \times 2) \times (91 - 7 \times 2 - 9) &= & ((9 + 2) + ((7 + 1) \times (9 \times (2 \times 7)))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1021} &:= -1 + 7 + (2 \times 9 + 17) \times 29 &= & ((9 - (2^7)) \times (1 - 9)) - (2 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1022} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 \times 91 - 7 - 29) &= & (9 - 2) \times ((7 + 1) + ((9 + (2^7)) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1023} &:= 172 \times (-9 + 17 - 2) - 9 &= & 927 - (((1 - 9) \times 2) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1024} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 29 \times 1 \times (7 - 2) + 9 &= & (927 - (1 - (92 + 7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1025} &:= -1 + (7 \times 2 + 91 + 7 + 2) \times 9 &= & (927 - (1 - (92 + 7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1026} &:= (172 - (9 - 1) \times 7 - 2) \times 9 &= & (927 - (1 - (92 + 7))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1027} &:= (1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9) \times (1 + 7) + 2 + 9 &= & (((927 + 1) + 92) + 7) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1028} &:= 1 + 7 + 291 + 729 &= & (((927 + 1) + 92) + 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1029} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 + 9) &= & (9 - 2) \times ((7 \times 19) + (2 \times (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1030} &:= -1 + (7 - 2 + 9) \times (1 + 72) + 9 &= & (9 + ((2 + 71) \times ((9 - 2) + 7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1031} &:= 1 \times (7 - 2 + 9) \times (1 + 72) + 9 &= & 9 + (2 \times ((71 \times 9) - 2^{7 \times 1})) \\
 \mathbf{1032} &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 + 91 + 7 + 29) &= & (9 \times ((2^7) \times 1)) + ((9 - (2^7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1033} &:= ((1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 + 1) \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= & (((9 \times 2) - 7) + 1) \times 92 - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1034} &:= 17 \times 2 \times 9 - 1 + 729 &= & (9 + 2) \times ((7 - ((1 - (9^2)) - 7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1035} &:= 1 \times 729 + 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= & ((9 - (2 \times 7)) - (1 + 9)) \times (2 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1036} &:= 17 \times 2 \times 9 + 1 + 729 &= & (927 - 19) + 2^{7 \times 1} \\
 \mathbf{1037} &:= 17 + 291 + 729 &= & 927 - ((19 - (2^7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1038} &:= (-1 + 7) \times (-29 - 1 + 7 \times 29) &= & ((9 - 2) + (7 - ((1 - 9) \times (2^7)))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1039} &:= -1 \times 7 \times 2 + 9 \times (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= & (9 - 2) + ((7 - ((1 - 9) \times (2^7))) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1040} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 \times (1 + 7) - 2 - 9 &= & (9 + (((2^7) \times 1) - (9 - 2))) \times (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1041} &:= 172 \times (-9 + 17 - 2) + 9 &= & (9 + (2 + 7)) - (((1 - 9) \times (2^7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1042} &:= 1 \times (72 - 9) \times 17 - 29 &= & (9 + 2) + (7 - ((1 - 9) \times 2^{7 \times 1})) \\
 \mathbf{1043} &:= (1 - 7 + 2 + 9 \times 17) \times (-2 + 9) &= & (9 + (2 + 7)) - (((1 - 9) \times (2^7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1044} &:= (1 + 72 - 9 + 1 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= & (9 - (27 - 192)) \times (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1045} &:= (17 + 2) \times (91 - 7 - 29) &= & (((927 - 1) - 9) + (2^7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1046} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + 9 \times 17) - 2 - 9 &= & (((927 - 1) - 9) + (2^7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1047} &:= 1 - 7 + ((-2 + 9) \times 17 - 2) \times 9 &= & ((927 \times 1) - (9 - (2^7))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1048} &:= -1 - 7 + (-2 + 91 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= & 927 + (192 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1049} &:= -1 - 7 + (2 - 9 \times 17) \times (2 - 9) &= & (((9 - 2) \times (71 + 9)) \times 2) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1050} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (29 + 1) \times (7 \times 2 - 9) &= & (9 - 2) \times (((7 - 19)^2) + 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1051} &:= 1 \times 7 + 29 \times 1 \times (7 + 29) &= & 9 + (((2 + (7 \times (19 + 2))) \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1052} &:= (172 + 91) \times (-7 + 2 + 9) &= & (927 - 1) + ((9 \times 2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1053} &:= (17 + 2) \times (9 - 1) \times 7 - 2 - 9 &= & 9 + (((2 + (7 \times (19 + 2))) \times 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1054} &:= 17 \times 2 \times (9 - 1 + 7 \times 2 + 9) &= & ((9 \times ((2^7) - 19)) + 2) + 71
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1055} &:= (1 \times 7 - 2) \times (9 - 1 + 7 \times 29) &= (((9 \times 2) - (7 - 1)) \times ((9^2) + 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1056} &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) \times (-17 + 29) &= ((9 - 2) \times (((7 - 19)^2) + 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1057} &:= (172 + 9) \times (-1 + 7) - 29 &= ((9 - 2) \times (((7 - 19)^2) + 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1058} &:= 1 + 7 \times (-2 + 9 + (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9) &= ((9 - 2) \times (((7 - 19)^2) + 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1059} &:= -1 + 7 + ((-2 + 9) \times 17 - 2) \times 9 &= 927 + (((1 + (9 \times 2)) \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1060} &:= 172 + 917 - 29 &= (9 + 2^{7+1}) \times ((9 + (2 - 7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1061} &:= (17 - 2) \times (9 + 1) \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= (((9 \times ((2 \times 7) \times 1)) \times 9) - 2) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1062} &:= (1 \times 7 + 2) \times (-9 + 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9) &= (9 - 27) \times (1 + ((9 + 2) - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1063} &:= -17 + (29 + 1) \times (7 + 29) &= (927 - 1) + (9 + 2^{7 \times 1}) \\
 \mathbf{1064} &:= 1 + 7 + (-2 + 91 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (((92 - 7) \times 1) - 9) \times (2 \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1065} &:= 1 + (72 - 9) \times 17 + 2 - 9 &= ((927 + 1) + 9) + 2^{7 \times 1} \\
 \mathbf{1066} &:= (-1 + 7 - 2 + 9) \times (1 + 72 + 9) &= (9 - ((2 - 7) + 1)) \times ((9 \times (2 + 7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1067} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9 \times 17) - 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (((2^7) \times 1) - 9)) + ((2 - 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1068} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + 9 \times 17) + 2 + 9 &= ((9 \times 2) - (7 - 1)) \times (((9^2) + 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1069} &:= -1 \times 72 \times (-9 + 1 - 7) - 2 - 9 &= (9 \times (27 - (1 - 92))) + (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1070} &:= -1 + (7 + (-2 + 9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= (927 - 1) + ((9 \times 2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1071} &:= 172 + 917 - 2 \times 9 &= ((9^2) + 719) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{1072} &:= 1 + (7 + (-2 + 9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= 92 + ((7 \times ((1 + 9) \times (2 \times 7))) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1073} &:= 17 + (-2 + 91 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (92 + (7 \times ((1 + 9) \times (2 \times 7)))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1074} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times 91 - 7 - 2 - 9 &= (927 + 19) + 2^{7 \times 1} \\
 \mathbf{1075} &:= (17 + 2) \times (9 - 1) \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= (((9 \times (2^7)) + 1) - (9 - 2)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1076} &:= (-1 + 72) \times (9 - 1 + 7) + 2 + 9 &= ((9 \times (2^7)) - ((1 + (9^2)) - 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1077} &:= (1 + 72 - 9) \times 17 - 2 - 9 &= ((927 - 1) + 9) + (2 \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{1078} &:= (-1 - 7 + 29 + 1) \times 7 \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 + (2 \times 71)) + (927 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1079} &:= 1 - 7 + (2 + 9 \times 17) \times (-2 + 9) &= ((9^2) - ((7 \times 1) - 9)) \times ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1080} &:= (172 + 9 \times (1 - 7) + 2) \times 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) - ((1^{92}) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1081} &:= (1 + 72 - 9) \times 17 + 2 - 9 &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) \times ((19 + 27) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1082} &:= (1 \times 72 - 9) \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= 92 + (719 + 271) \\
 \mathbf{1083} &:= 1 + (72 - 9) \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= (9 + (((2^7) - 1) \times 9) + 2)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1084} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + (91 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= ((9 + (2 \times 7)) - 19) \times 271 \\
 \mathbf{1085} &:= (1 - 72 - 91 + 7) \times (2 - 9) &= (9 \times (((2^7) \times 1) - 9)) + ((2 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1086} &:= (-1 + 7) \times ((29 + 1) \times 7 - 29) &= (9 + ((2 \times 7) \times (1 + (9^2)))) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1087} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times (91 - 7 \times 2) + 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) - ((1 - (9 - 2)) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1088} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times 91 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= (927 + 19) + (2 \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{1089} &:= (17 + 2 \times (9 + 17) \times 2) \times 9 &= 927 - ((1 - 92) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1090} &:= 17 + 2 - 9 \times 17 \times (2 - 9) &= 92 + ((71 + 927) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1091} &:= 1 \times 72 \times (9 - 1 + 7) + 2 + 9 &= 92 + ((71 + 927) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1092} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 91 + 72 - 9) &= (((9 - 2) \times 7) - (1 + 9)) \times (27 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1093} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 + (91 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= 9 - (2 \times (((7 \times 1) - 9) \times 271)) \\
 \mathbf{1094} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 + (91 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (((9 \times 2) - 7) \times (1 + 92)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1095} &:= (17 - 2) \times (-9 + 1 + 72 + 9) &= 927 + ((19 + 2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1096} &:= 172 + 917 - 2 + 9 &= (9 \times ((2^7) \times 1)) - ((9 - 2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1097} &:= 17 + (29 + 1) \times (7 + 29) &= (927 + (19 \times (2 + 7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1098} &:= (1 \times 72 + (9 + 1) \times (7 - 2)) \times 9 &= (927 + (19 \times (2 + 7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1099} &:= (17 + 2 \times (9 + 1) \times 7) \times (-2 + 9) &= (927 + (19 \times (2 + 7))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1100} &:= (1 \times 72 - 9) \times 17 + 29 &= ((9 + 2) - 7) \times (19 + 2^{7+1}) \\
 \mathbf{1101} &:= (17 - 2) \times (9 \times (1 + 7) + 2) - 9 &= (92 + (((7 - 19)^2) \times 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1102} &:= (17 + 2) \times (9 \times 1 - 7) \times 29 &= ((9 \times 2) \times (71 - 9)) - ((2 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1103} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9 \times 17) + 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times (71 - 9))) - ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1104} &:= (-1 + 7) \times (2 + 9 \times 17 + 29) &= (9 \times (2^7)) - ((1 - 9) \times (2 - (7 + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1105} &:= 17 \times (-2 \times (9 - 1) + 72 + 9) &= ((9 + ((2^7) \times 1)) \times 9) - ((2^7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1106} &:= 1 \times 7 \times ((2 + 9) \times 17 - 29) &= (9 \times ((2 \times 7) - (19 - (2^7)))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1107} &:= 172 + 917 + 2 \times 9 &= 9 \times (((2 \times 7) - (19 - (2^7))) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1108} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9 \times 17 + 2) + 9 &= (9 \times ((2 \times 7) - (19 - (2^7)))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1109} &:= 1 \times 72 \times (9 - 1 + 7) + 29 &= (92 - 7) - ((1 - 9) \times 2^{7 \times 1}) \\
 \mathbf{1110} &:= (-1 + 7) \times (2 + 9 - (1 - 7) \times 29) &= ((9 \times (2 \times (71 - 9))) + (2 - 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1111} &:= (1 + 7 + 2 + 91) \times (-7 + 2 \times 9) &= (927 + (192 - 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1112} &:= (-1 + 7^2 + 91) \times 72/9 &= (927 + (192 - 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1113} &:= -1^7 + 2 \times (-91 + 72 \times 9) &= (927 + 192) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1114} &:= 1^7 \times 2 \times (-91 + 72 \times 9) &= 92 + (7 \times ((19 + (2^7)) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1115} &:= -17 \times 2 + 91 \times 7 + 2^9 &= (9 \times ((2^7) + (1 + 9))) - ((2^7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1116} &:= (1 \times 7 + 2) \times (9 \times 17 - 29) &= (9 \times ((2^7) + 1)) + ((9 \times (2 - 7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1117} &:= 1 + (7 + 2) \times (9 \times 17 - 29) &= (((9 \times (2^7)) \times 1) - 9) - (27 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1118} &:= 172 + 917 + 29 &= (9 - ((2 - 7) + 1)) \times (92 - (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1119} &:= -17 + 2 + 9 \times 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 + ((2 \times (7 - 1)) \times 92)) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1120} &:= (1 + 7 + 2 \times (9 + 1)) \times (7^2 - 9) &= ((9 + ((2 \times (7 - 1)) \times 92)) + 7) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1121} &:= 1 + 7^2 + 9 \times 17 \times (-2 + 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 - (19 \times (2 - 7)))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1122} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 \times (91 - 72 \times 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 - (19 \times (2 - 7)))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1123} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 \times (-1 + 72 - 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 - (19 \times (2 - 7)))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1124} &:= -17 + (-2 + 9) \times (172 - 9) &= 92 + ((7 + (1^9)) \times ((2^7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1125} &:= (172 - 91) \times 7 \times 2 - 9 &= (927 + 192) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1126} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 \times (9 \times (-1 + 7) + 2^9) &= (((9 \times (2^7)) - 1) - 9) - (2 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1127} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + 9 \times 1) \times (7 \times 2 + 9) &= 927 + ((192 + 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1128} &:= -1 - 7 + 2 + 9 \times 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times (2^7)) - 19) + (2 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1129} &:= (1 + 7) \times (29 - 1) \times (7 - 2) + 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times (71 - 9))) + ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1130} &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 + 9 \times (1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9) &= (((9 \times (2^7)) - 1) - 9) - (2 \times (7 - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1131} &:= 17 + 2 \times (-91 + 72 \times 9) &= (((9 \times (2 \times 7)) - 1) \times 9) - 2) + (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1132} &:= (-1 - 7 + 291) \times (-7 + 2 + 9) &= (9 - (27 + 1)) + ((9 \times (2^7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1133} &:= -1^7 + 2 \times (-9 \times 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 \times ((27 - 1) + 92)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1134} &:= (-1 + 72 - 9 + 1) \times (7 + 2 + 9) &= ((9 - 2) \times (7 + ((1 + 9) \times 2))) \times (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1135} &:= -17 + 2 \times (-9 + 1 + 72) \times 9 &= ((9 - 27) + 1) + (9 \times ((2^7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1136} &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 \times (9 - 1) + 7 \times 2 \times 9) &= (((9 \times 2) \times (7 - 1)) - 92) \times 71 \\
 \mathbf{1137} &:= (-17 + 2 \times 91) \times 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times ((2^7) \times 1)) - (9 - 2)) - (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1138} &:= 17 \times (-2 + (9 + 1) \times 7) - 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times (2^7)) - 19) - (2 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1139} &:= -(1 + 7)/2 + 9 \times (1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9) &= (9 \times (2^7)) - ((1 + ((9 \times 2) - 7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1140} &:= -(-1 + 7)/2 + 9 \times (1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9) &= (9 + (2 - 71)) \times (9 - (27 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1141} &:= (-1 + 72/9) \times (172 - 9) &= ((9 \times (2^7)) - 1) - (((9 \times 2) - 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1142} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 \times (9 \times 1 - 72) \times 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) - (19 - (2 + (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1143} &:= (172 - 91) \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= ((9^2) \times (7 - 1)) + (9 \times (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1144} &:= 1 + 7 + 2 + 9 \times 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 + 2) \times ((7 - (1 - (92 + 7)))) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1145} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 + 91 \times 7 + 2^9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) + (9 - (2 \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1146} &:= 1 + 72 \times (9 \times 1 + 7) + 2 - 9 &= ((9 \times (2^7)) + (1^{92})) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1147} &:= -1 + 7 + (-2 + 9) \times (172 - 9) &= ((9 \times (2^7)) + (1 + 9)) - ((2 \times 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1148} &:= (172 - 9 \times 1) \times 7 - 2 + 9 &= (((9 \times (2^7)) - 1) - 9) - (2 - (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1149} &:= 17 - 2 + 9 \times 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times (2^7)) \times 1) + (9 - (2 \times (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1150} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 \times 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times ((2^7) + 1)) - ((9 \times 2) - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1151} &:= (-1 + 72) \times 9 + 1^7 \times 2^9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times 71) - (((9 \times 2) \times 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1152} &:= 1 \times 72 \times (9 - 1 + 72/9) &= (9 \times 2) \times (((7 \times 19) + 2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1153} &:= 17 + 2 + 9 \times 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= 9 + (2 + (((71 + 92) \times 7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1154} &:= 1 - 7 + 2^9 \times 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (((9 \times (2^7)) - 1) - 9) + (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1155} &:= (17 - 2) \times (91 - 7 + 2 - 9) &= (9 + 2) \times (((7 \times 1) + 92) + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1156} &:= 17 \times 2 \times (-9 + 17 \times 2 + 9) &= (9 \times (2^7)) + (1 - (9 - (2 \times (7 - 1)))) \\
 \mathbf{1157} &:= -1 + 7 + 2 + 91 \times 7 + 2^9 &= 92 + (((71 + (9^2)) \times 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1158} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 + 91 \times 7 + 2^9 &= (((9 \times (2^7)) - 1) - 9) + (2 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1159} &:= -1 + (7 \times 2 + 9 + 17) \times 29 &= (((9 \times (2^7)) + (1^{92})) + 7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1160} &:= (1 \times 7 \times 2 + 9 + 17) \times 29 &= (((9 \times 2) \times 7) + 19) \times ((2 + 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1161} &:= 1 + (7 \times 2 + 9 + 17) \times 29 &= (9 + ((2^7) + (1 - 9))) \times ((2 + 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1162} &:= 1 + 72 \times 9 + 1^7 + 2^9 &= ((9 \times (2^7)) + (1^9)) + ((2 + 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1163} &:= 1 - 7 + 2^9 + (1 + 72) \times 9 &= (((9 \times 2) - 7) + 1) + ((9 \times (2^7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1164} &:= 1^7 + (2 + 91) \times 7 + 2^9 &= (((9^2) \times 7) + 19) \times 2) - (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1165} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times (91 - 7) - 2 - 9 &= 9 + (((2^7) \times 1) \times 9) - ((2 - 7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1166} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 - 1 + 7 + 2^9 &= (9 \times ((2^7) + 1)) + (9 + (2 - (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1167} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 - 9 &= (9 \times ((2^7) \times 1)) + ((9 - 2) + (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1168} &:= 17 + 2^9 + (-1 + 72) \times 9 &= 927 - (1 - ((9 \times 27) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1169} &:= -1 + 729 + 1 \times 7^2 \times 9 &= (927 \times 1) + ((9 \times 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1170} &:= 1 \times 729 + 1 \times 7^2 \times 9 &= (9 - (2 - (7 + 1))) \times ((9 - 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1171} &:= 1 + 729 + 1 \times 7^2 \times 9 &= 927 + ((1 + (9 \times 27)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1172} &:= 1 \times 7 + (2 \times (9 + 1 + 7))^2 + 9 &= (9 \times (((2^7) + (1^9)) + 2)) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1173} &:= 17 \times (-2 - 9 - 1 + 72 + 9) &= (927 - 1) - (9 - 2^{7+1}) \\
 \mathbf{1174} &:= 17 \times (-2 + (9 + 1) \times 7) + 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times ((2^7) + 1)) + 9) - (2 - (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1175} &:= (1 + 72) \times 9 - 1 + 7 + 2^9 &= (((9 \times 2) - 7) + 1) \times 92 + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1176} &:= (1 - 7) \times (2 - 9) \times (-1^7 + 29) &= ((9 + (2 \times 7)) \times 1) + ((9 \times (2^7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1177} &:= 17^2 + 917 - 29 &= (9 \times ((2^7) \times 1)) + ((9 \times 2) + (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1178} &:= (-1 + 72) \times (9 + 1 + 7) - 29 &= (9 \times (((27 \times 1)/9) + (2^7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1179} &:= (17 + 2) \times 9 \times 1 \times 7 - 2 \times 9 &= (927 - 19) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{1180} &:= -1 + 72 \times (9 \times 1 + 7) + 29 &= (9 \times (27 + 1)) + (927 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1181} &:= -17 \times 2 + 9 \times (17 - 2) \times 9 &= 9 - (2 \times (71 - (9 \times (2 + 71)))) \\
 \mathbf{1182} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 \times (91 - 7) - 2 + 9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times ((7 - 1) \times (9 + 2))) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1183} &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times 91 - 7 - 2 + 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) + (((19 \times 2) - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1184} &:= (-17 + 2 \times 91) \times 7 + 29 &= ((9 \times (2^7)) + 19) + ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1185} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 + 9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= 9 + ((2 \times 7) \times ((1 + (9 + 2)) \times (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1186} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 \times (91 - 7 + 2^9) &= (9 \times (((2^7) + (1^9)) + 2)) + (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1187} &:= -1 - 72 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= 927 + ((1 + 9) \times (27 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1188} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times ((9 + 1) \times 7 + 29) &= 927 - ((1 + 9) - 271) \\
 \mathbf{1189} &:= 1 - 72 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (((9 \times 2) + (7 + 19)) \times 27) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1190} &:= 17 \times (2 + 9 + 1 + 7^2 + 9) &= 927 + (192 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1191} &:= (17 - 2) \times (9 - 1 + 72) - 9 &= (927 - 1) + (9 + 2^{7+1}) \\
 \mathbf{1192} &:= (-1 + 7) \times (291 - 7) - 2^9 &= (9 - (2^7)) - (19 \times (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1193} &:= 1 + (7^2 - 9) \times 17 + 2^9 &= (9 + (((2 \times 7) - (1^9))^2 \times 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1194} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 91 - 72 - 9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times ((7 - 1) \times (9 + 2))) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1195} &:= 17^2 + 917 - 2 - 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) - ((1 + (9 \times (2 - 7))) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1196} &:= (1 + 7 + 2 \times 9) \times (17 + 29) &= (((9 + 27) + 1) + 9) \times (27 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1197} &:= (-1 + 72 - 9 - 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 - 2) \times ((7 + 1) + (92 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1198} &:= 1 + (72 - 9) \times (1 + 7 + 2 + 9) &= (927 \times (1^9)) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{1199} &:= 17^2 + 917 + 2 - 9 &= (((92 \times 7) \times 1) - 9) \times 2 - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1200} &:= -17 - 2^9 + 1729 &= (9 \times (2^7)) + ((1 - 9) \times (2 - (7 + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1201} &:= 172 \times (9 + 1) - 7 - 2^9 &= (92 \times ((7 \times 1) + 9)) - 271 \\
 \mathbf{1202} &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 + 9 \times (17 - 2) \times 9 &= ((9 - 2) \times (7 \times 19)) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{1203} &:= -1 + 7 + (-2 + 9 \times (17 - 2)) \times 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) + (1 + (((9 - 2) \times 7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1204} &:= (-1 \times 7 + 2 + 91) \times (7 - 2 + 9) &= (9 - 2) + ((7 \times 19) \times (2 + (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1205} &:= -1 + 72 \times (9 + 1 + 7) - 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (2 + (7 \times 19))) - ((2 + 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1206} &:= (1 + 7 - 2 \times (9 \times 1 - 72)) \times 9 &= ((927 - 1) + 9) + 271
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1207} &:= 1 + 72 \times (9 + 1 + 7) - 2 \times 9 &= (9 + (271 + 927)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1208} &:= -1 - 7 + 2 \times (91 \times 7 - 29) &= (927 + 1) + (9 + 271) \\
 \mathbf{1209} &:= 1729 - 1 - 7 - 2^9 &= (((9 - ((2 - 7) - 1)) \times (9^2)) - 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1210} &:= (17 + 2 + 91) \times (-7 + 2 \times 9) &= ((9^2) \times ((7 - 1) + 9)) + (2 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1211} &:= 1729 + 1 - 7 - 2^9 &= ((92 \times 7) \times 1) + ((9^2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1212} &:= 1 + 7 \times 29 \times (-1 + 7) + 2 - 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) - ((9 + 2) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1213} &:= (-1 \times 7 + 2 + 91) \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) + (((1 - 9) - 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1214} &:= 1 + (-7 + 2 + 91) \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= ((9 - 2) - 71) + (9 \times (2 \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1215} &:= -1^7 + (29 - 1 + 7)^2 - 9 &= 9 \times ((2 - ((7 - 1) - 9)) \times (27 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1216} &:= (1 + 7)^2 \times (9 - 1 - 7 + 2 \times 9) &= (((9 - 2) - 7) + 19) \times 2^{7-1} \\
 \mathbf{1217} &:= 17^2 + 917 + 2 + 9 &= (927 + 19) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{1218} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times 91 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 + 2) + ((71 \times (9 \times 2)) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1219} &:= 1 + (7^2 + 9) \times (-1 - 7 + 29) &= (((9 + 27) - (1^9))^2) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1220} &:= -1 + 72 + 91 \times 7 + 2^9 &= ((9^2) \times ((7 - 1) + 9)) - (2 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1221} &:= -1 + 729 + 17 \times 29 &= (((9 - 2) + (71 \times 9)) \times 2) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1222} &:= 1 \times 729 + 17 \times 29 &= (92 - ((7 \times 1) - 9)) \times ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1223} &:= 1 + 729 + 17 \times 29 &= ((9 - ((2 - 7) - 1)) \times (9^2)) + (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1224} &:= 1 - (7 + (2 - 91) \times 7) \times 2 - 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) + ((1^{92}) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1225} &:= 1 + 7 - 2^9 + 1729 &= (9 + (((2^7) - 1) \times 9) + 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1226} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 91 + 7 \times (2 - 9) &= 92 - (7 \times (1 - (92 + 71))) \\
 \mathbf{1227} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times (91 + 7 + 2^9) &= (9 \times ((2 \times (7 + 1)) \times 9)) + (2 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1228} &:= (17 \times 2 \times 9 + 1) \times (-7 + 2 + 9) &= (9 + ((2 \times 7) \times (1 + (9^2)))) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1229} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 + 9 \times (17 - 2) \times 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) - ((1 - (9 - 2)) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1230} &:= (1^7 + 29) \times (1 + 7^2 - 9) &= ((9 \times (2^7)) + (1 + ((9 + 2) \times 7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1231} &:= 17 \times (2 + (9 + 1) \times 7) - 2 + 9 &= 927 + ((19 \times 2) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1232} &:= (1 \times 7 - 29) \times (1 + 7) \times (2 - 9) &= (9 - (2 - 7)) \times ((19 - 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1233} &:= 1 + (7 - 29) \times (1 + 7) \times (2 - 9) &= (((9 + 27) - (1^9))^2) + 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1234} &:= 17 - 2^9 + 1729 &= (9 \times ((2^7) + (1^9))) + (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1235} &:= 1 \times 729 + 1 - 7 + 2^9 &= (92 + 7) - ((1 - 9) \times (2 \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1236} &:= 1729 - 17 \times 29 &= (((92 - 7) \times 1) + (9 \times (2^7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1237} &:= -1^7 + 2 \times (91 \times 7 - 2 \times 9) &= (((92 - 7) \times 1) + (9 \times (2^7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1238} &:= 1^7 \times 2 \times (91 \times 7 - 2 \times 9) &= ((9 - (2 \times (7 + (1 - 92)))) \times 7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1239} &:= -1 + 7 + (2 + 9 \times (17 - 2)) \times 9 &= ((9 - (2 \times (7 + (1 - 92)))) \times 7) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1240} &:= (1 + 7) \times (29 + 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9) &= ((9^2) + ((7 + 1) + (9 \times (2^7)))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1241} &:= 17 + 2 \times ((9 + 1) \times 7 - 2) \times 9 &= (9^2) + (((7 + 1) + (9 \times (2^7))) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1242} &:= -17 \times 2 \times 9 + 172 \times 9 &= 9 \times ((271 + 9) - (2 \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1243} &:= 172 + 9 \times 17 \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) - (9 + (27 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1244} &:= -1^7 + 2 \times 91 \times 7 - 29 &= 9 - ((2 - 7) \times (19 \times ((2 \times 7) - 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1245} &:= -17 + 2 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (((9 + (2^7)) \times 1) \times 9) + (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1246} &:= 1 \times 7 \times ((29 - 1) \times 7 - 2 \times 9) &= ((9^2) + (7 + 1)) \times ((9 - 2) + (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1247} &:= 1 \times 729 - 1 + 7 + 2^9 &= ((9 + ((2^7) \times 1)) \times 9) + ((2 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1248} &:= -1 + 7 + 2^9 + 1 + 729 &= (9 \times (((2 \times 7) \times (1 + 9)) - 2)) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1249} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 91 - 7 - 2 \times 9 &= 92 + (((7 - (1 - (9 \times (2^7)))) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1250} &:= 172 \times 9 - 17^2 - 9 &= (((9 - 2) \times 7) + 1) \times ((9 \times 2) + (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1251} &:= 1 + (7 - 2) \times (9 + 1) \times (7 + 2 \times 9) &= 9 - (((27 \times 1) - 9) \times (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1252} &:= 1 - 7 - 2 + (91 + 7^2) \times 9 &= (9 + 2) + (((7 + 1) + 9) \times (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1253} &:= (17 - 2) \times (91 - 7) + 2 - 9 &= (((9 \times 2) \times 71) - (9 \times 2)) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1254} &:= (-1 + 7^2 + 9) \times 1 \times (-7 + 29) &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) - ((9 \times 2) + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1255} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 \times 91 - 7 - 2 - 9 &= 9 - (((2 \times 7) - 192) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1256} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 91 - 7 - 2 - 9 &= ((9 \times (2 \times 7)) \times (1 + 9)) + ((2 - 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1257} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 91 - 7 - 2 - 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) - (92 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1258} &:= 17 + 2^9 + 1 \times 729 &= ((9 + 2) + (7 - 1)) \times (((9^2) - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1259} &:= 17 + 2^9 + 1 + 729 &= 9 - (27 + (1 - ((9 \times 2) \times 71))) \\
 \mathbf{1260} &:= (1 \times 7 + 29 - 1) \times (7 + 29) &= (9 + ((2 + 7) + 192)) \times (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1261} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 91 - 7 + 2 - 9 &= 9 + ((2 \times (71 \times 9)) - (27 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1262} &:= -1 + 7 + 2 \times 91 \times 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times (2^7)) - (19 - (2^7))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1263} &:= 1 + 7 + (-2 + 91) \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) - ((9 - 2) + (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1264} &:= 1 + 7 + 2 \times 91 \times 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) - 1) - (9 \times (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1265} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 \times 91 - 72/9 &= (9 - (271 - 9)) \times (2 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1266} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 91 - 72/9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times 71) - (((9 \times 2) - 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1267} &:= (17 - 2) \times (91 - 7) - 2 + 9 &= (((9 \times 2) \times 71) - (9 \times 2)) + (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1268} &:= -17^2 + 9 + 172 \times 9 &= (((9 \times 2) \times 71) - (9 \times 2)) + (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1269} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 + (91 + 7^2) \times 9 &= ((9^2) \times (7 + 1)) - (9 \times (2 - 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1270} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 + 91 \times (7 - 2 + 9) &= ((9 \times ((2^7) \times 1)) - (9 - (2^7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1271} &:= (17 - 2) \times (91 - 7) + 2 + 9 &= (9 \times ((2^7) \times 1)) - ((9 - (2^7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1272} &:= (1 + (((72 \times 9) - 17) \times 2)) + 9 &= ((9 \times ((2^7) \times 1)) - 9) + ((2^7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1273} &:= -17^2 + 91 \times (7 - 2 + 9) &= (((9 \times (2^7)) + 1) - 9) + ((2^7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1274} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times (91 + 7 + 2 - 9) &= (9 - ((2 \times 7) - 1)) + ((9 \times 2) \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{1275} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) - ((9 + 2) - (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1276} &:= 17 \times (2 + 9 \times (1 + 7)) + 2 \times 9 &= ((92 - 7) \times ((1 + (9 - 2)) + 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1277} &:= -17 - 2 + 9 \times (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times ((2^7) \times 1)) + (((9 \times 2) \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1278} &:= (-1^7 - 29 + 172) \times 9 &= 9 \times ((2 \times (71 \times 9))/(2 + (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1279} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 \times 91 \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= 9 + (((2^7) - 1) \times 9) + ((2^7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1280} &:= -1 \times 7 + (-29 + 172) \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) - (((1 - 92) \times 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1281} &:= 1^7 \times 2 \times 91 \times 7 - 2 + 9 &= ((9 + 2) - 7) - (1 - ((9 \times 2) \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1282} &:= 1^7 + 2 \times 91 \times 7 - 2 + 9 &= (9 + ((2 \times (71 \times 9)) + 2)) - (7 \times 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1283} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 91 + 72/9 &= ((9 + 2) - 7) + (1 + ((9 \times 2) \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1284} &:= 17 + 2 + 91 \times 7 \times 2 - 9 &= ((9 + 2) + (7 \times 192)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1285} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 91 - 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (9 - (2 \times (7 \times 19))) \times ((2 - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1286} &:= (-1 + 72) \times 9 - 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) - ((1 - (92 \times 7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1287} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2^{9-1} \times 7 - 2^9 &= (9 \times ((2^7) + 1)) + ((9 \times 2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1288} &:= (17 + 29) \times (-1^7 + 29) &= (9 \times 2) - (7 + (1 - ((9 \times 2) \times 71))) \\
 \mathbf{1289} &:= (1 + 7^2) \times (9 + 17) - 2 - 9 &= ((92 \times 7) + 1) + ((92 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1290} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 + 91 \times (7 - 2 + 9) &= (9 \times ((2 \times 71) + 9)) + (2 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1291} &:= 1 \times (-7 + 2) + 9 \times (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 - 2) + (71 \times (9 \times 2))) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1292} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 + 91 \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= 9 - (2 - (((71 \times 9) \times 2) + (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1293} &:= 1^7 \times (2 + 91) \times 7 \times 2 - 9 &= (((9 + 2) + (71 \times 9)) \times 2) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1294} &:= 17 \times (29 + 17) + 2^9 &= (92 \times 7) + (((1 + 92) \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1295} &:= -172 + (91 + 72) \times 9 &= 927 + (((19^2) + 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1296} &:= (-1 + 7)^{2-9 \times 1 - 7 + 2 \times 9} &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) - ((9 - 27) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1297} &:= 1 + 72 \times 9 + 1 \times 72 \times 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) + ((9 + 2) + (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1298} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 \times 1 \times 72 + 9 &= ((9 \times (2 - 7)) + (192 \times 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1299} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 91 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) + ((19 + 2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1300} &:= 1 + 7 + 2 \times 91 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= 9 + (((2 \times 7) - 1) + ((9 \times 2) \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1301} &:= -1 - 7 + (2 + 9) \times 17 \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 \times (2 + 71)) + ((92 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1302} &:= (17 - 2) \times 91 - 72 + 9 &= ((9 \times 2) + (7 + 192)) \times (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1303} &:= (1 + 7 + 2 + 91 \times 7) \times 2 + 9 &= ((9 \times (2 \times 71)) + 9) + (2 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1304} &:= (-1^{72} + 9) \times (172 - 9) &= ((9^2) + 71) + ((9 \times (2^7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1305} &:= 1 \times 72 \times 9 + (1 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 - (2 \times 7)) \times ((1 + 9) - 271) \\
 \mathbf{1306} &:= 172 + 9 \times 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 + 2) - ((7 - 192) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1307} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 \times ((1 + 7)^2 + 9) &= (((9 + 2) + (71 \times 9)) \times 2) + (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1308} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 \times (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= 92 + ((7 + 1) \times ((9^2) + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1309} &:= 1 \times 7 + (2 + 91) \times (7 - 2 + 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 1)) \times (9 + ((2 + 7) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1310} &:= 1 + 7^2 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 - 271) \times ((9 - (2 \times 7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1311} &:= (1 + 7^2) \times (9 + 17) + 2 + 9 &= 9 - (2 - ((7 + 1) \times (92 + 71))) \\
 \mathbf{1312} &:= (172 - 9 + 1) \times 72/9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times (71 + 9)) - 2^{7 \times 1} \\
 \mathbf{1313} &:= -1 + (72 + 9 - 1 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 + 2) + (7 \times ((192 - 7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1314} &:= 1 \times 7^2 + 91 \times 7 \times 2 - 9 &= 9 + ((2 - 7) \times ((1 + 9) - 271)) \\
 \mathbf{1315} &:= -1 + 7 + (-2 + 9) \times 17 \times (2 + 9) &= (9 + 27) + (1 + ((9 \times 2) \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1316} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + 9 + 172 + 9) &= (((92 - 7) \times 1) + 9) \times (2 \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1317} &:= 17 \times 2 + 91 \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= 9 + (((2^7) - 19) \times (2 \times (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1318} &:= 1 \times 7 + (2 + 91) \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= 9 + ((2 - (7 - 192)) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1319} &:= (17 + 2) \times (9 + 1) \times 7 - 2 - 9 &= (9 + (2 \times 719)) - 2^{7 \times 1} \\
 \mathbf{1320} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times (9 + 1) \times (-7 + 2 \times 9) &= (((9^2) + 7) \times 1) \times (9 - (2 - (7 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1321} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 \times ((1 + 7)^2 + 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times (71 + ((9 - 2) \times 7))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1322} &:= 1 + 7 + (2 \times 9 \times (1 + 7) + 2) \times 9 &= (9 \times 2) + ((71 + 92) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1323} &:= (-1 \times 7 + (2 + 9) \times 1 \times 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times 71) - (9 \times (2 - (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1324} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 91 + 7 \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 \times (2^7)) + ((19 \times (2 + 7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1325} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 \times (91 \times 7 + 29) &= (9 \times ((2 \times 71) - 9)) + ((2^7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1326} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times (91 - 7) - 2 \times 9 &= (9 - 27) + (192 \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1327} &:= 17 \times (2 + 9) \times 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (9 - 27) + ((192 \times 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1328} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times (91 - 72/9) &= ((9 \times 2) \times 71) + (((9 - 2) \times 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1329} &:= (1 + 7)^2 + 91 \times 7 \times 2 - 9 &= ((9 - 2) \times ((71 - 9) + (2^7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1330} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 \times 91 + 72/9) &= (9 - 2) \times ((71 - 9) + ((2^7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1331} &:= -1 + 72 + (9 + 1) \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + (2 \times 71)) \times 9) - (27 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1332} &:= (-1 + 72 + 9 + 1 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + (2 + 7)) \times 1) \times (((9^2) - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1333} &:= -1 + (7^2 + 9) \times (1 - 7 + 29) &= (9 \times (2 + (7 \times (19 + 2)))) - (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1334} &:= 1 \times (7^2 + 9) \times (1 - 7 + 29) &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) \times (((1 - 9)^2) - (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1335} &:= 1 + (7^2 + 9) \times (1 - 7 + 29) &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 19)) - ((2^7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1336} &:= (1 + 7) \times ((29 - 1) \times 7 - 29) &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 19)) - ((2^7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1337} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 91 + 72 - 9 &= (9 \times (2^7)) + ((192 - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1338} &:= 1 + 7 + 2 \times (9 \times 17 + 2^9) &= ((9 \times (2^7)) + 192) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1339} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times (91 \times 7 + 29) &= 9 + ((271 - (9^2)) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1340} &:= 17 + 2 \times 9 \times (1 + 72) + 9 &= (((9^2) - (7 \times 1)) \times (9 \times 2)) + 7 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1341} &:= (-1 \times 7 \times 2 + 91 + 72) \times 9 &= 9 \times ((2 \times (7 - 1)) + ((9 + (2^7)) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1342} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 \times (91 + 7) - 29 &= 9 + ((2 \times ((71 \times 9) + 27)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1343} &:= -1 \times 7 + (29 + 1) \times (7 - 2) \times 9 &= 9 + (2 \times (((71 \times 9) + 27) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1344} &:= (1 \times 7 - 2 + 91) \times (7 - 2 + 9) &= (9/(2 + 7)) \times (192 \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1345} &:= 17 \times (-2 + 9 \times 1) \times 7 + 2^9 &= (9/(2 + 7)) + (192 \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1346} &:= 1 + 7^2 + 9 \times (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times ((2 \times 71) + 9)) - ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1347} &:= -1 + 7 + (-2 + 9 \times 17 - 2) \times 9 &= (9 + 2) - ((7 - (192 \times 7)) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1348} &:= 17 + (2 + 9)^{-1-7+2+9} &= (9 + 2) + (((7 \times 192) - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1349} &:= (-1 + 72) \times (-9 + 17 + 2 + 9) &= (((9 + 2) + 7) + (1^{92})) \times 71 \\
 \mathbf{1350} &:= -1 + 7 \times (2^{9-1} - 72 + 9) &= (9 - (2 \times 7)) \times ((1^9) - 271) \\
 \mathbf{1351} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2^{9-1} - 72 + 9) &= ((9^2) - 7) - (1 - ((9 \times 2) \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1352} &:= (1 + 7) \times (-2 + 9 \times 17 + 2 \times 9) &= (9 - ((2 - 7) \times 19)) \times ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1353} &:= (-1 + 72 + 9) \times 17 + 2 - 9 &= 9 - ((2 \times (7 + (1 - 92))) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1354} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 \times 91 + 72 + 9 &= (((9^2) + 71) \times 9) - (2 \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1355} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 + (9 \times 17 - 2) \times 9 &= ((9 - ((2 \times 7) - 1)) + 9) \times 271 \\
 \mathbf{1356} &:= 1 + 72 + 91 \times 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (((9 \times 27) - 19) + 2) \times (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1357} &:= (17 - 2) \times 91 - 72/9 &= ((9 - (2 - 7)) + (192 \times 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1358} &:= -17 + (2 + 9) \times (-1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9) &= ((9 - (2 - 7)) + (192 \times 7)) \times 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1359} &:= (1 + 7 - 29 + 172) \times 9 &= 927 + ((19^2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1360} &:= (-1 + 72 + 9) \times (-1 + 7 + 2 + 9) &= 9 - (((2^7) \times ((1 - 9) - 2)) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1361} &:= (17 - 2) \times 91 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= (9 + 2) + ((7 + (192 \times 7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1362} &:= 1^7 + 2 + (9 \times 17 - 2) \times 9 &= ((9 + 2) + 7) + ((192 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1363} &:= 1^7 \times (29 - 1) \times 7^2 - 9 &= (((9 - 2) + (71 \times 9)) \times 2) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1364} &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 + (9 \times 17 - 2) \times 9 &= 9 + (((2 - 7) + (1 + 9)) \times 271) \\
 \mathbf{1365} &:= (17 - 2) \times 91/7 \times (-2 + 9) &= 92 - (7 - (((1 + 9) \times (2^7)) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1366} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times (91 + 7) + 2 - 9 &= (((9 + (2^7)) \times (1 + 9)) + 2) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1367} &:= (-1 + 72) \times 9 - 1 + 729 &= (9 \times ((271 + 9) - (2^7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1368} &:= 1 \times 72 \times (9 + 1) + 72 \times 9 &= (9 \times ((271 + 9) - (2^7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1369} &:= 17 \times 2 \times (9 - 1) \times (7 - 2) + 9 &= (9 \times ((271 + 9) - (2^7))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1370} &:= 1 + (7^2 - 9) \times 17 \times 2 + 9 &= ((9 \times ((2^7) + (1 + 9))) + (2^7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1371} &:= -1 + 7^2 \times (-9 + 1 + 7 + 29) &= (((9 + (2 + 7)) - 1) \times (9^2)) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1372} &:= 1 \times 7^2 \times (-9 + 1 + 7 + 29) &= (9 + (2 \times (719 - 2))) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1373} &:= 1 + 7^2 \times (-9 + 1 + 7 + 29) &= ((9 - (2 - 7)) \times (1 + 92)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1374} &:= (1 - 7) \times 29 + 172 \times 9 &= 9 + (((2 \times 719) - 2) - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1375} &:= (-1 + 7 + (-2 + 9) \times 17) \times (2 + 9) &= (9^2) - (((7 - 192) \times 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1376} &:= 172 \times (9 - 1^{729}) &= ((92 + 7) - 1) + (9 \times (2 \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1377} &:= 1 \times 729 \times 1 + 72 \times 9 &= ((92 + 7) \times 1) + (9 \times (2 \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1378} &:= 1 \times 729 + 1 + 72 \times 9 &= (((9 + (2^7)) \times (1 + 9)) + 2) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1379} &:= 1 + 729 + 1 + 72 \times 9 &= ((92 \times 7) - 1) + (92 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1380} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times (91 + 7) - 2 + 9 &= ((92 \times 7) \times 1) + (92 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1381} &:= 172 \times (9 - 1) + 7 \times 2 - 9 &= ((9 - (2 - 719)) \times 2) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1382} &:= -1^7 + 29 \times (-1 + 7^2) - 9 &= (9 + ((2 \times 7) \times (1 + 92))) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1383} &:= -1 + 7 + (2 \times 9 + 1) \times 72 + 9 &= (((92 \times (7 + 1)) - 9) \times 2) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1384} &:= 1 \times 7 + (2 \times 9 + 1) \times 72 + 9 &= ((9 \times (27 + (1 - 9))) + 2) \times (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1385} &:= -1 + (7 + 2) \times (91 + 72 - 9) &= ((9 + (((2 + 7) + 1) \times 9)) \times (2 \times 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1386} &:= (1 + 7 - 29) \times (1 - 7) \times (2 + 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times 7) \times ((1 + (9 + 2)) + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1387} &:= 17 \times (-2 + 91) - 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + (2 \times 71)) \times 9) + (27 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1388} &:= 1 \times (7 + 2) \times 9 \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= (9 - (((2 - 7) - 192) \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1389} &:= 1 + (72 + 9) \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= 9 - (((2 - 7) - 192) \times 7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1390} &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 \times (91 + 7 + 2) - 9 &= (((9 + 2) \times 7) \times 19) - (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1391} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times (91 + 7) + 2 \times 9 &= 9 + (2 \times ((719 - 27) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1392} &:= (-1 - 7 + 2 \times 91) \times 72/9 &= ((92 + 71) + (9 + 2)) \times (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1393} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 \times 9 + 172 + 9) &= (9 + (271 - (9^2))) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1394} &:= -1 \times 7 + 29 \times (-1 + 7^2) + 9 &= 9 + (((2 + 71) \times (9 \times 2)) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1395} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 \times (-1 + 7 \times 2) - 9 &= 9 \times ((2 + 71) + (9 + (2 + 71))) \\
 \mathbf{1396} &:= (1 + 72) \times (91 - 72) + 9 &= ((9 \times 27) \times 1) + ((9 \times (2^7)) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1397} &:= (1 \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 + 1^7) \times (2 + 9) &= (9 + 2) \times (7 + (((1 + 9) \times 2) \times (7 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1398} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 91 - 7^2 - 9 &= (((9 - 2) + 71) \times (9 \times 2)) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1399} &:= 172 \times (9 - 1) + 7 \times 2 + 9 &= (92 \times ((7 \times 1) + 9)) - (2 + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1400} &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 + (9 \times 17 + 2) \times 9 &= (((9 - 2) \times 7) + (1^9)) \times (27 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1401} &:= 172 \times (9 - 1) + 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (9 - 2) + (7 + (19 \times (2 + 71))) \\
 \mathbf{1402} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times (91 + 7) + 29 &= (9 - 27) + (((1 + 9) \times 2) \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{1403} &:= 17 + (2 + 9 \times 1) \times 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= (((9 \times 2) \times 7) - 1) + ((9 \times 2) \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{1404} &:= (17^2 - 9 - 1) \times (7 - 2) + 9 &= (9 + 2) + (7 \times ((192 + 7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1405} &:= 172 \times (-9 + 17) + 29 &= ((9 \times 2) \times 71) + (((9 \times 2) \times 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1406} &:= 1 - 7 + 29 \times 1 \times 7^2 - 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 7)) + (((1 + 9) \times (2^7)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1407} &:= -1 + (72 + (9 - 1) \times 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (((9 + (2 + 7)) + 1) \times ((9^2) - 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1408} &:= 1 \times (72 + (9 - 1) \times 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (92 + (7 \times (1 + (9 + 2)))) \times (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1409} &:= 1 + (72 + (9 - 1) \times 7) \times (2 + 9) &= (((9^2) - 7) \times ((1 + 9) \times 2)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1410} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times (91 + 7 + 2) + 9 &= (((9 - 2) + 71) \times (9 \times 2)) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1411} &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 \times (1 + 7 \times (2 + 9)) &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) - (9 - (2 \times 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1412} &:= 172 \times (9 - 1) + 7 + 29 &= (927 - 1) + ((9^2) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1413} &:= (-1 + 729 - 17) \times 2 - 9 &= 9 \times ((2 - (7 + 1)) + (92 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1414} &:= (-1 + 7 \times 29 + 1) \times 7 + 2 - 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 71)) + ((9 + (2^7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1415} &:= -1 + 7 \times (29 + 172) + 9 &= 9 + (((2 + 7) + 192) \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1416} &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 91 - 7^2 + 9 &= 9 + (((2 + 7) + 192) \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1417} &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times (91 + 7 + 2 + 9) &= (((9^2) - 7) + (192 \times 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1418} &:= -1 \times 7^2 + (91 + 72) \times 9 &= (9^2) + (((7 \times 192) - 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1419} &:= -1 + 7 + (2 + 9 \times 17 + 2) \times 9 &= (9^2) - ((7 - (192 \times 7)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1420} &:= (-1 + 72) \times (-9 \times 1^7 + 29) &= 9 + (((2 \times 719) - 27) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1421} &:= (17 - 2 - 9 + 1) \times 7 \times 29 &= 9 + (((2 \times 719) - 27) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1422} &:= 1 + 7 \times 29 \times (-1 + 72/9) &= (92 \times (7 + (1 + 9))) - (2 \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{1423} &:= 1729 - 17 \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 + 27) + (19 \times (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1424} &:= (1 + 7) \times ((29 - 1) \times 7 - 2 \times 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times 71) + ((92 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1425} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 + 917 + 2^9 &= ((9 + (2 + 7)) + 1) \times (((9^2) - 7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1426} &:= -1^7 - 2 + 917 + 2^9 &= ((9 + 2) + (7 \times 192)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1427} &:= -1^7 \times 2 + 917 + 2^9 &= (9 \times (2 \times (71 + 9))) - ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1428} &:= (17 - 2) \times 91 + 72 - 9 &= (92 + (7 \times 192)) - (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1429} &:= 1^{72} \times 917 + 2^9 &= ((92 + (7 \times 192)) - 7) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1430} &:= -1 - 7 + 2 \times (-9 - 1 + 729) &= ((92 + (7 \times 192)) - 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1431} &:= (-1 + 729 - 17) \times 2 + 9 &= (9 + (2 \times 719)) - (2 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1432} &:= (-1 + 7 \times 29 + 1) \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= (9 + 271) + (9 \times 2^{7 \times 1}) \\
 \mathbf{1433} &:= 1 + 7 \times 29 \times 1 \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= (((9^2) - 7) \times 19) + 27) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1434} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 \times (-9 \times 1 + 729) &= (((9^2) - 7) \times 19) + 27) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1435} &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 917 + 2^9 &= (9 + (2 \times 719)) - (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1436} &:= 1 + 7 + (-2 + 9) \times (1 + 7 \times 29) &= (9 \times (2 \times (71 + 9))) + (2 - (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1437} &:= 1 \times 7 + 29 \times 1 \times 7^2 + 9 &= 9 - (((2 \times 7) \times (1 - (9 \times 2))) \times (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1438} &:= -1 + 7 \times 29 \times 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= 9 + ((2 \times 719) - (2 + (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1439} &:= 1 \times 7 \times 29 \times 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 &= 927 + ((19 \times 27) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1440} &:= 1^7 \times 2 \times (9 - 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 + 27) \times ((1 - 9) \times (2 - (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1441} &:= 1^7 + 2 \times (9 - 1 + 72) \times 9 &= 92 + ((71 \times (9 \times 2)) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1442} &:= 1^7 \times 2 \times (-9 + 1 + 729) &= ((92 + 7) + (192 \times 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1443} &:= 1^7 + 2 \times (-9 + 1 + 729) &= ((92 + 7) + (192 \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1444} &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 + 917 + 2^9 &= ((92 + 7) + (192 \times 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1445} &:= 17 \times (2 + 9 \times (1 + 7) + 2 + 9) &= (92 \times ((7 \times 1) + 9)) - (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1446} &:= 1^7 \times 291 \times (7 - 2) - 9 &= (((9 \times 27) \times (1^9)) - 2) \times (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1447} &:= -1 + 72/9 \times (172 + 9) &= (((92 \times (7 + 1)) - 9) \times 2) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1448} &:= 1 \times 72/9 \times (172 + 9) &= ((9 \times 2) \times (71 + 9)) + (2 + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1449} &:= 1729 - 17^2 + 9 &= 9 \times (((27 - 1) \times 9) - 2) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1450} &:= 17 \times (-2 + 91) - 72 + 9 &= (9 \times (((2 + 7) \times 19) - 2)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1451} &:= -(1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 \times (172 - 9) &= (9 - 2) + ((719 \times 2) + (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1452} &:= -1 - 7 \times 2 + (91 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 - (2 - (719 \times 2))) + (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1453} &:= 1 \times 7 + 291 \times (7 - 2) - 9 &= 9 + ((2 \times 719) - ((2 - 7) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1454} &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 + (91 + 72) \times 9 &= (((92 + (71 \times 9)) \times 2) - 7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1455} &:= 17 + 2 \times (-9 - 1 + 729) &= (9 + (2 + (719 \times 2))) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1456} &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 + (9 + 1) \times (7 + 2 + 9)) &= (9 + (2 \times 719)) + (2 + (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1457} &:= 1 \times 729 - 1 + 729 &= (((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 19)) + 2) - (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1458} &:= (1 \times 7 + 2) \times 9 \times 1 \times (7 + 2 + 9) &= 9 + (((2 + 719) \times 2) + (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1459} &:= 1 \times 729 + 1 + 729 &= 927 + (19 \times (27 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1460} &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times (9 \times 17 + 2 - 9) &= (9 + (((2 \times 7) + 1) \times 92)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1461} &:= (1 + 72) \times 91/7 + 2^9 &= ((9^2) - 7) + (19 \times (2 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1462} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + (91 + 72) \times 9 &= (((92 \times ((7 \times 1) + 9)) - 2) - 7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1463} &:= 17 + 291 \times (7 - 2) - 9 &= (92 \times ((7 \times 1) + 9)) - (2 + (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1464} &:= 17 \times (-2 + 91) + 7 \times (2 - 9) &= ((9^{27 \times 1/9}) \times 2) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1465} &:= 1^7 \times (2^{9+1} + 7^2 \times 9) &= 9 + (2 \times ((7 + 19) \times (27 + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1466} &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 - 72 - 9 &= (9 - ((2 - (7 + 1)) \times (9 \times 27))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1467} &:= 1^{72} \times (91 + 72) \times 9 &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 19)) - (2 - (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1468} &:= -1^7 + 2 + (91 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 \times ((2 \times 71) - 9)) + 271 \\
 \mathbf{1469} &:= -1 + 7^2 \times (9 - 1 - 7 + 29) &= (9 \times (2 \times 7)) + ((192 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1470} &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 - 7 \times (2 + 9) &= (9 \times (2 \times 7)) + (192 \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1471} &:= (1 + 729 + 1^7) \times 2 + 9 &= (((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 19)) + 2) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1472} &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 + (91 + 72) \times 9 &= 92 \times (((7 - 19) + 27) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1473 &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + (91 + 72) \times 9 &= (((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 19)) + 2) + (7 + 1) \\
 1474 &:= 1^7 \times 2 \times (9 - 1 + 729) &= (9^2) + ((7 + 192) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 1475 &:= -1^7 + (-2 + 91 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 19)) + (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 1476 &:= 1^7 \times 2 \times (9 + 1 + 72) \times 9 &= (9 \times 2) + (((7 - 1) \times 9) \times 27) \times 1 \\
 1477 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 + 9 + 1 + 7 \times 29) &= (9 \times 2) + (((7 - 1) \times 9) \times 27) + 1 \\
 1478 &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 91 + 7 \times 29 &= 92 + (7 \times (192 + (7 - 1))) \\
 1479 &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 \times (172 - 9) &= ((9 + (2 + 7)) - 1) \times ((9^2) + (7 - 1)) \\
 1480 &:= -1 + 7 \times 2 + (91 + 72) \times 9 &= (927 + 1) + (92 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 1481 &:= 17 + 291 \times (7 - 2) + 9 &= (92 \times ((7 \times 1) + 9)) + (2 + (7 \times 1)) \\
 1482 &:= (1 - 7) \times ((2 - 9) \times 17 \times 2 - 9) &= ((9 + (2 + 7)) \times (1 + (9^2))) + (7 - 1) \\
 1483 &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 \times (172 - 9) &= ((9 + (2 + 7)) \times (1 + (9^2))) + (7 \times 1) \\
 1484 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 - 72 + 9 &= 92 + ((7 \times (192 + 7)) - 1) \\
 1485 &:= -1 \times 72 + 9 \times 172 + 9 &= 92 + (7 \times (192 + (7 \times 1))) \\
 1486 &:= 1 - 72 + 9 \times 172 + 9 &= ((9^2) \times (7 - (1 - 9))) + 271 \\
 1487 &:= 17 \times (2 + 9) \times (-1 + 7 + 2) - 9 &= (9 \times ((2 \times 71) + 9)) + ((2^7) \times 1) \\
 1488 &:= (-1 + 7 + 2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 72 - 9) &= (927 - ((1 - (9^2)) \times 7)) + 1 \\
 1489 &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) \times 17 + 2 - 9 &= (((9^2) + 7) \times (19 - 2)) - (7 \times 1) \\
 1490 &:= 17 \times (-2 + 91) - 7 \times 2 - 9 &= (9 + (2 \times (7 \times (1 + 9)))) \times ((2 + 7) + 1) \\
 1491 &:= -1 + (7^2 + 91) \times 7 + 2^9 &= (9 + (2 - (7 + 1))) \times ((9 - 2) \times 71) \\
 1492 &:= 1 \times (7^2 + 91) \times 7 + 2^9 &= 92 + (7 \times ((192 + 7) + 1)) \\
 1493 &:= 17 + 2 \times 9 \times (1 + 72 + 9) &= ((9 \times ((2 + 71) + 92)) + 7) + 1 \\
 1494 &:= (1 + 72 + 9 + 1) \times (7 + 2 + 9) &= ((92 + 71) \times 9) + (27 \times 1) \\
 1495 &:= 1^7 + (2 \times (91 - 7) - 2) \times 9 &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) \times ((1 - 9) + (2 + 71)) \\
 1496 &:= 17 \times (291 - 7 \times 29) &= (9^2) + ((7 \times 192) + 71) \\
 1497 &:= 1729 - (1 + 7) \times 29 &= (((9^2) + 71) \times 9) + ((2^7) + 1) \\
 1498 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (-2 \times 9 + (1 + 7) \times 29) &= 9 - (2 - (71 \times (92 - 71))) \\
 1499 &:= 1 + 7 \times (-2 \times 9 + (1 + 7) \times 29) &= (92 \times ((7 \times 1) + 9)) + (27 \times 1) \\
 1500 &:= 17 \times (2 + 91) - 72 - 9 &= ((9 \times (2 \times 7)) - 1) \times ((9 \times 2) - (7 - 1)) \\
 1501 &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times 9 \times 17 - 29 &= 927 + (((1 + (9^2)) \times 7) \times 1) \\
 1502 &:= -17 - 29 + 172 \times 9 &= (9 + 2) + (71 \times (92 - 71)) \\
 1503 &:= (-1 + 7)^2 + 9 \times (172 - 9) &= (927 \times 1) + (9 \times 2^{7-1}) \\
 1504 &:= (1 + 7) \times (-2 + 9 + 172 + 9) &= (9 \times (((2^7) \times 1) + 9)) + 271 \\
 1505 &:= 172 \times 9 - 17 \times 2 - 9 &= (92 - 7) + ((1 + 9) \times (2 \times 71)) \\
 1506 &:= (1^7 + 2) \times (9 + 17 \times 29) &= (9 \times (2^7)) + ((19^2) - (7 \times 1)) \\
 1507 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 - 7^2 + 9 &= 92 + ((7 \times 192) + 71) \\
 1508 &:= -1 \times 7^2 + 9 + 172 \times 9 &= (((9 \times (2 \times 7)) - 1) - 9) \times ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 1509 &:= -1^7 - 2 + (91 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 + 2) + (7 + ((19 + 2) \times 71)) \\
 1510 &:= 1^7 \times (-2 + (91 - 7) \times 2 \times 9) &= ((9 \times 2) - (7 + 1)) \times (9 + (2 \times 71))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1511 &:= 1^7 - 2 + (91 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (((9 \times (2 + 7)) - 1) \times 9) \times 2 + 71 \\
 1512 &:= (1 \times 7 + 2 \times 91) \times 72/9 &= ((9 \times (2 + 7)) \times 19) - (27 \times 1) \\
 1513 &:= 17 \times (-2 + 91) - 7 - 2 + 9 &= ((9 + 2) + (7 - 1)) \times ((9 \times 2) + 71) \\
 1514 &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times 91 + 7^2 + 9 &= (9 + (2 \times (719 - 2))) + 71 \\
 1515 &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times (9 + 17) \times 29 &= ((9 \times (((2 \times 7) - (1^9))^2)) - 7) + 1 \\
 1516 &:= 1 \times 7^2 + (91 + 72) \times 9 &= ((9 \times 2) + 7) + ((19 + 2) \times 71) \\
 1517 &:= 1 + 7^2 + (-9 + 172) \times 9 &= (((9 \times 2) - 7) \times ((1 + 9) + (2^7))) - 1 \\
 1518 &:= 17 \times (2 + 91) - 72 + 9 &= (9 - 27) + (192 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 1519 &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times 9 \times 17 - 2 - 9 &= ((9 \times 2) + (7 + 192)) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 1520 &:= 172 \times 9 - 17 - 2 - 9 &= (9 + (2 \times 719)) + (2 + 71) \\
 1521 &:= (-1 \times 7 + 29 - 1) \times 72 + 9 &= (((9 \times 2) \times 71) + (9 \times 27)) \times 1 \\
 1522 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 - 7 - 2 \times 9 &= (92 + (719 \times 2)) - (7 + 1) \\
 1523 &:= -17 \times 2 + 9 + 172 \times 9 &= ((9 - (2 - 719)) \times 2) + 71 \\
 1524 &:= -17 + 2 + 9 \times (17 + 2) \times 9 &= 92 + ((719 \times 2) - (7 - 1)) \\
 1525 &:= 1729 - 1 - 7 \times 29 &= (((92 \times (7 + 1)) - 9) \times 2) + 71 \\
 1526 &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times (91 + 7 + 2 + 9) &= (((9 + (2^7)) + 1) \times (9 + 2)) + 7 + 1 \\
 1527 &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 \times (91 + 7 + 2 + 9) &= (9 \times 2) + ((719 \times 2) + 71) \\
 1528 &:= 1^7 + 2^9 \times (1^7 + 2) - 9 &= ((9 \times (((2 \times 7) - (1^9))^2)) + 7) \times 1 \\
 1529 &:= -1 + (7 - 2) \times (9 + 1 + 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= ((9 \times 2) - 7) \times (((1 + 9) + (2^7)) + 1) \\
 1530 &:= 17 \times (2 + 9 - 17^2) \times 9 &= ((92 + 71) + 92) \times (7 - 1) \\
 1531 &:= 172 \times 9 + 1 - 7 - 2 - 9 &= (((9 + 2) + 719) \times 2) + 71 \\
 1532 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 + (9 + 1 - 7) \times 2^9 &= (((9 + 2) \times 7) \times 19) - 2 + 71 \\
 1533 &:= (1 + 72) \times (9 - 17 + 29) &= (((9 \times 2) - (7 - 1)) + 9) \times (2 + 71) \\
 1534 &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times (-9 + 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9) &= (9 + ((2^7) - 19)) \times ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 1535 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 - 9 + 172 \times 9 &= (((92 - 71) - 9) \times (2^7)) - 1 \\
 1536 &:= 172 \times 9 + 17 - 29 &= ((92 + 7) + (1 + 92)) \times (7 + 1) \\
 1537 &:= -1^7 \times 2 + 9 \times (17 + 2) \times 9 &= ((92 \times ((7 + 1) + 9)) - 27) \times 1 \\
 1538 &:= 172 \times 9 - 17 - 2 + 9 &= (92 + (719 \times 2)) + (7 + 1) \\
 1539 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 - 72/9 &= (9^2) \times (7 + (((1 + 9) \times 2) - (7 + 1))) \\
 1540 &:= (17 + 291) \times (7 \times 2 - 9) &= (9 + 2) \times (((7 \times (19 + 2)) - 7) \times 1) \\
 1541 &:= (1 + 7 + 2) \times 9 \times 17 + 2 + 9 &= (((92 - 7) + 1) \times 9) \times 2 - (7 \times 1) \\
 1542 &:= (-1 - 7 + 29) \times (1 + 72) + 9 &= 9 + ((27 + 192) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 1543 &:= (-1 + 7) \times 291 - 7 \times 29 &= ((9 \times (2 \times 71)) + 9) + 2^{7+1} \\
 1544 &:= -1^7 + 2^9 \times (-1 + 7)/2 + 9 &= 92 + ((7 - 1) \times ((9 \times 27) - 1)) \\
 1545 &:= 1 + 7 - 2 - 9 + 172 \times 9 &= (92 \times ((7 \times 1) + 9)) + (2 + 71) \\
 1546 &:= 17 \times 2 + (91 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (2 \times 7)) + (((1 + 9) \times 2) \times 71) \\
 1547 &:= (1 - 7 + 2 - 9) \times 17 \times (2 - 9) &= (927 - 1) - (9 \times (2 - 71)) \\
 1548 &:= 1729 - 172 - 9 &= ((92 + 71) + 9) \times (2 + (7 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1549 &:= 1 + 7 + 2 + 9 \times 172 - 9 &= 927 + (1 - (9 \times (2 - 71))) \\
 1550 &:= (-1 + 72 - 9) \times (17 \times 2 - 9) &= 92 + (((7 - 1) \times 9) \times (27 \times 1)) \\
 1551 &:= (1 + 7 \times 2 \times (9 + 1)) \times (-7 + 2 \times 9) &= ((92 - 7) \times 19) - 2^{7-1} \\
 1552 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2^9 - 17^2) - 9 &= (9 + ((2 \times (7 + 1)) \times 92)) + 71 \\
 1553 &:= 172 \times 9 + 1 - 7 + 2 + 9 &= ((92 - 71) \times ((9^2) - 7)) - 1 \\
 1554 &:= 17 - 2 + 9 \times (17 + 2) \times 9 &= (9 - 2) \times ((71 + 9) + (2 \times 71)) \\
 1555 &:= 1729 + (1 - 7) \times 29 &= ((92 - 71) \times ((9^2) - 7)) + 1 \\
 1556 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1^{72} + 9 &= ((9 + 2) \times ((7 \times 19) + 2)) + 71 \\
 1557 &:= -1 \times 72 + 9 \times (172 + 9) &= 9 \times (((271 - 92) - 7) + 1) \\
 1558 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 - 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (9 + 271) + ((9 \times 2) \times 71) \\
 1559 &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 + 172 \times 9 &= ((9 \times 2) \times ((7 - 1) + (9^2))) - (7 \times 1) \\
 1560 &:= 1 - 7 + 2 \times 9 + 172 \times 9 &= (((((9^2) + 7) - 1) \times 9) \times 2) - (7 - 1) \\
 1561 &:= 1 \times 7^2 + (91 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times 2) + (7 + (192 \times (7 + 1))) \\
 1562 &:= 17 \times (-2 + 91) + 7 \times (-2 + 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times 71) + ((9 + 2) \times 71) \\
 1563 &:= 1 + 7 - 2 + 9 \times 172 + 9 &= (927 - ((1 - 92) \times 7)) - 1 \\
 1564 &:= (-1 + 7^2 \times (9 - 1)) \times (-7 + 2 + 9) &= (927 - ((1 - 92) \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 1565 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 + 7 + 2 + 9 &= (927 - ((1 - 92) \times 7)) + 1 \\
 1566 &:= 1729 - 172 + 9 &= ((9 \times (2 + 7)) \times 19) + (27 \times 1) \\
 1567 &:= 1 + 7 + 2 + 9 + 172 \times 9 &= 927 + ((1 + 9) \times 2^{7-1}) \\
 1568 &:= 1 \times 7 \times 2 \times (9 - 1) \times (7 - 2 + 9) &= ((9 + 2) \times 7) + ((19 + 2) \times 71) \\
 1569 &:= -1 - 7 + 29 + 172 \times 9 &= 9 - ((27 - 1) \times ((9 + 2) - 71)) \\
 1570 &:= -1 \times 7 + 29 + 172 \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) - (1 - (927 \times 1)) \\
 1571 &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 + 9 \times (-1 + 7) \times 29 &= 9 - (((2 - 7) - (19 - 2)) \times 71) \\
 1572 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 + 7 + 2 \times 9 &= 9 + (27 + (192 \times (7 + 1))) \\
 1573 &:= 1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 + 172 \times 9 &= (92 \times 7) + (1 + (927 + 1)) \\
 1574 &:= 172 \times 9 + 1 + 7 + 2 \times 9 &= (((9^2) \times (7 + 1)) + 927) - 1 \\
 1575 &:= (17 - 2) \times (91 + 7 - 2 + 9) &= (((9^2) \times (7 + 1)) + 927) \times 1 \\
 1576 &:= 17 + 2 + 9 + 172 \times 9 &= (((9^2) \times (7 + 1)) + 927) + 1 \\
 1577 &:= 1^7 \times (29 + 172 \times 9) &= (927 + ((1 + 92) \times 7)) - 1 \\
 1578 &:= (17 + 2) \times (91 - 7) - 2 \times 9 &= (927 + ((1 + 92) \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 1579 &:= -1 - 7^2 + 9 \times (172 + 9) &= (927 + ((1 + 92) \times 7)) + 1 \\
 1580 &:= -1 \times 7^2 + 9 \times (172 + 9) &= (9 \times 2) + (71 \times (9 + ((2 \times 7) - 1))) \\
 1581 &:= 1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 \times (-1 + 7) \times 29 &= (((9 \times 27) - 19) + 2) \times 7 - 1 \\
 1582 &:= (1 + 7 \times 2 \times (9 - 1)) \times (7 - 2 + 9) &= (((9 \times 27) - 19) + 2) \times 7 \times 1 \\
 1583 &:= -1 + 7 + 29 + 172 \times 9 &= 92 - ((71 - 92) \times 71) \\
 1584 &:= 1 \times 7 + 29 + 172 \times 9 &= (9 \times 2) \times (((7 - 1) + 9) + (2 + 71)) \\
 1585 &:= 172 \times 9 + 1 + 7 + 29 &= (9 \times (2 + 71)) + (927 + 1) \\
 1586 &:= 1 + 7^2 + (9 + 1 - 7) \times 2^9 &= (9 \times 27) + ((192 \times 7) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1587 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 + 7^2 - 9 &= (9 - (2 \times ((7 \times 1) + 9))) \times (2 - 71) \\
 1588 &:= 1 \times 7^2 + 9 \times 172 - 9 &= ((9 \times 27) + (192 \times 7)) + 1 \\
 1589 &:= 17 \times (2 + 91) + 72/9 &= (((9 \times ((2 \times 7) + 1)) + 92) \times 7) \times 1 \\
 1590 &:= -17 \times 2 + (9 - 1) \times 7 \times 29 &= (9^2) + ((719 \times 2) + 71) \\
 1591 &:= 17 \times 2 + 9 + 172 \times 9 &= (92 \times ((7 + 1) + 9)) + (27 \times 1) \\
 1592 &:= -1 + (-7 + 29 \times 1) \times 72 + 9 &= ((9^2) \times 7) - (((1 - 9) \times (2^7)) - 1) \\
 1593 &:= (-1 \times 7 + 29 \times 1) \times 72 + 9 &= 9 + ((2 \times ((7 \times 1) + 92)) \times (7 + 1)) \\
 1594 &:= ((172 \times 9) + 17) + 29 &= (9 \times (2 \times (71 + (9 \times 2)))) - (7 + 1) \\
 1595 &:= (17 \times (2 + 91)) + 7 - 2 + 9 &= (((9 + 27) + 192) \times 7) - 1 \\
 1596 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 + 7 \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 + (2 \times (71 - 9))) \times (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 1597 &:= (1 + 7) \times 2 \times (91 + 7) + 29 &= (((9 + 27) + 192) \times 7) + 1 \\
 1598 &:= 17 \times (2 \times 9 - 1 + 7 \times (2 + 9)) &= (9 + ((2 + (((7 - 1) + 9)^2)) \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 1599 &:= 17 \times (2 + 91) + 7 + 2 + 9 &= ((92 - 7) \times 19) - (2 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 1600 &:= (1 + 7^2) \times (9 \times 1 + 7 \times 2 + 9) &= ((92 - 7) \times 19) - ((2 \times 7) + 1) \\
 1601 &:= -1^7 + (-2 + 91) \times (7 + 2 + 9) &= 92 + ((719 \times 2) + 71) \\
 1602 &:= (-1^7 - 2 + 9 + 172) \times 9 &= 9 \times (((2^7) - 19) - 2) + 71 \\
 1603 &:= (1 + 7)^2 + 9 \times 172 - 9 &= ((92 - 7) \times 19) - (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 1604 &:= -17 \times 2 + 91 \times (7 + 2 + 9) &= (9 \times (271 - 92)) - (7 \times 1) \\
 1605 &:= -1 + 7 \times 29 \times (1 + 7) - 2 \times 9 &= (((9^2) + 7) + 19) \times ((2 \times 7) + 1) \\
 1606 &:= 1 \times 7^2 + 9 + 172 \times 9 &= (((92 - 7) \times 19) - (2 + 7)) \times 1 \\
 1607 &:= -17 + 29 \times (1 + 7) \times (-2 + 9) &= ((92 - 7) \times 19) - (2 + (7 - 1)) \\
 1608 &:= 1 \times 72 + (9 + 1 - 7) \times 2^9 &= (((9 \times (2 \times 7)) - 1) + 9) \times (2 \times (7 - 1)) \\
 1609 &:= -17 + 2 + (9 - 1) \times 7 \times 29 &= (((92 - 7) \times 19) + 2) - (7 + 1) \\
 1610 &:= 17 \times (2 - 9) + 1729 &= ((92 - 7) \times 19) + ((2 - 7) \times 1) \\
 1611 &:= 1 - 7 \times 2 + (9 - 1) \times 7 \times 29 &= 9 \times ((2 \times 71) + (9 + (27 + 1))) \\
 1612 &:= 172 \times 9 + 1 + 72 - 9 &= (9 \times (2^{7+1} - ((9 + 2) \times 7))) + 1 \\
 1613 &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 \times 9 \times (1 + 7 + 2) \times 9 &= ((9 \times ((2 + 7) + 1)) \times (9 \times 2)) - (7 \times 1) \\
 1614 &:= (-1 + 7) \times (291 + 7 - 29) &= ((9 + (271 - 9)) - 2) \times (7 - 1) \\
 1615 &:= 17 \times (2 \times (9 + 17) \times 2 - 9) &= ((9 + (2 + 7)) + 1) \times (92 - (7 \times 1)) \\
 1616 &:= -1 - 7 + (29 - 1) \times (7^2 + 9) &= ((92 + 719) \times 2) - (7 - 1) \\
 1617 &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2 + 9 - 1) \times 7 \times (2 + 9) &= (92 - 71) \times ((9 + 2) \times (7 \times 1)) \\
 1618 &:= 1 + 7 \times 29 \times (1 + 7) + 2 - 9 &= (9 \times (271 - 92)) + (7 \times 1) \\
 1619 &:= 17 + (-2 + 91) \times (7 + 2 + 9) &= ((92 - 7) \times 19) - ((2 - 7) + 1) \\
 1620 &:= (17 + (2 \times 9 + 1)) \times (7 - 2) \times 9 &= (9 + 27) \times ((19 + 27) - 1) \\
 1621 &:= 1 - 7 - 2 + 9 \times (172 + 9) &= 9 + ((2 \times (71 - 9)) \times ((2 \times 7) - 1)) \\
 1622 &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 \times 91 \times (7 + 2) - 9 &= (((92 - 7) \times (1 + (9 \times 2))) + 7) \times 1 \\
 1623 &:= -1 - 7 + 2 + 9 \times (172 + 9) &= ((92 - 7) \times 19) + (2 + (7 - 1)) \\
 1624 &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 + 7 \times (2 + 9) &= (((9 - 2) \times 7) \times 1) + 9 \times (27 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1625} &:= -(1+7)/2 + (9+172) \times 9 &= (((92-7) \times 19) + 2) + (7+1) \\
 \mathbf{1626} &:= 1^7 \times 2 + (9-1) \times 7 \times 29 &= (((9 \times 2) + 7) - 19) \times 271 \\
 \mathbf{1627} &:= -1^7 \times 2 + (9+172) \times 9 &= ((92-7) \times 19) + (2 \times (7-1)) \\
 \mathbf{1628} &:= 172 \times 9 - 1 + 72 + 9 &= ((92-7) \times 19) + ((2 \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1629} &:= 1^{72} \times 9 \times (172+9) &= ((9^2) \times (7-1)) + (9 \times ((2^7) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1630} &:= 1^{72} + 9 \times (172+9) &= ((92-71) \times (9^2)) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1631} &:= 1 \times 7 \times (2 \times (9-1) \times 7 \times 2 + 9) &= ((92-7) \times 19) + (2 \times (7+1)) \\
 \mathbf{1632} &:= 1 \times 72/9 \times (1+7 \times 29) &= (((9 \times 27) + ((1-9) - 2)) \times 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1633} &:= (1+7)/2 + (9+172) \times 9 &= 9 + (((((27-1) \times 9) - 2) \times (7 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1634} &:= -1 \times 7^2 + 9 \times 17 \times (2+9) &= (((9+2) + 7) + 1) \times ((92-7) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1635} &:= (-1+7) \times (-2 \times 9 + 17^2) + 9 &= (92+7) + (192 \times (7+1)) \\
 \mathbf{1636} &:= 1 + 7 \times 29 \times (1+7) + 2 + 9 &= (((9 + (2^7)) \times ((1+9) + 2)) - 7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1637} &:= -1 + 7 + 2 + 9 \times (172+9) &= ((9 + (2^7)) \times ((1+9) + 2)) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1638} &:= (1 \times 72 - 9) \times (1+7+2 \times 9) &= (9-2) \times (71 + (92+71)) \\
 \mathbf{1639} &:= 172 + (91+72) \times 9 &= (9+2) \times (((71+9) - 2) + 71) \\
 \mathbf{1640} &:= 1^7 \times 2 \times (91+729) &= (9 \times ((2^7) - 1)) + ((9-2) \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{1641} &:= 1^7 + 2 \times (91+729) &= ((92-7) \times 19) + (27-1) \\
 \mathbf{1642} &:= ((1+7) \times 29 + 1) \times 7 + 2 + 9 &= ((92-7) \times 19) + (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1643} &:= 17 \times (-2 + 91 + 7) + 2 + 9 &= (9^2) + (71 \times (9 + ((2 \times 7) - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1644} &:= (-1+7) \times (2^{9-1} + 7 + 2 + 9) &= (9 + (2^7)) \times ((1 + (9 \times 2)) - (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1645} &:= -1 - 7 + 29 \times (-1 + 7^2 + 9) &= (((9 \times 27) - (1 + (9-2))) \times 7) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1646} &:= (-1 + 72 + 91) \times 7 + 2^9 &= (((9 \times 27) - (1 + (9-2))) \times 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1647} &:= (1 + (7-2+9-1) \times 7 \times 2) \times 9 &= 9 - ((2 \times 7) \times (1 + (9 - ((2^7) - 1)))) \\
 \mathbf{1648} &:= -1 \times 72 - 9 + 1729 &= ((9 \times (2^7)) - 1) + ((9-2) \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{1649} &:= 1729 + 1 - 72 - 9 &= (((9-2) \times 71) + (9 \times (2^7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1650} &:= (1+7^2) \times (9-1+7+2 \times 9) &= (((((9 \times 2) + 7) \times 1) \times (9+2)) \times (7-1)) \\
 \mathbf{1651} &:= 1729 - 1 - 7 \times (2+9) &= ((9 + ((2^7) - 19)) \times (2 \times 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1652} &:= (17+2+9) \times (1+7^2+9) &= ((9 + ((2^7) - 19)) \times (2 \times 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1653} &:= 1729 + 1 - 7 \times (2+9) &= ((9 + ((2^7) - 19)) \times (2 \times 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1654} &:= -1 \times 7 + (-2+9 \times 17) \times (2+9) &= (9 + ((2 \times (7-1)) \times (9 + (2^7)))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1655} &:= -17 + 2^{9+1} + 72 \times 9 &= 927 - ((1-92) \times (7+1)) \\
 \mathbf{1656} &:= ((1-7)^2 + 9+1) \times (7+29) &= 92 \times ((71 \times (9 \times 2))/71) \\
 \mathbf{1657} &:= 17 + 2 \times (91+729) &= (9 \times ((2^7) + ((1-9)^2))) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1658} &:= 17 \times 2 + (9-1) \times 7 \times 29 &= ((9-2) \times 71) + (9 \times ((2^7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1659} &:= (-1+7 \times 2 \times (9+1+7)) \times (-2+9) &= ((9 + (2^7)) + ((1+9)^2)) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1660} &:= -1^7 + (-2+9 \times 17) \times (2+9) &= (92 \times 7) - ((1-9) \times ((2^7) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1661} &:= 1^7 \times (-2+9 \times 17) \times (2+9) &= 9 + ((2 \times 7) \times (((19-2) \times 7) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1662} &:= (-1+7) \times (291-7+2-9) &= 927 - (1 - (92 \times (7+1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1663} &:= 1729 + ((1 - 7) \times (2 + 9)) &= (((9 - 2) + 7) - (1^9)) \times (2^7) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1664} &:= (-1 + 7 \times 2) \times (9 \times 1 - 7)^{-2+9} &= 92 - ((7 - 1) \times (9 - 271)) \\
 \mathbf{1665} &:= 1729 - 1 - 72 + 9 &= (((9 - 2) + 7) - (1^9)) \times (2^7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1666} &:= 1729 \times 1 - 72 + 9 &= (9 - (2^7)) \times ((1 - 9) + (2 - (7 + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1667} &:= 1 - 72 + 9 + 1729 &= ((92 \times 7) - ((1 - 9) \times (2^7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1668} &:= -1 - 7 \times 2 + 9 \times 17 \times (2 + 9) &= ((92 \times 7) - ((1 - 9) \times (2^7))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1669} &:= (17^2 - 9) \times (-1 + 7) - 2 - 9 &= ((92 \times 7) - ((1 - 9) \times (2^7))) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1670} &:= (1 - 7 + 29) \times (1 + 72) - 9 &= 9 + (2 - (7 \times (19 - 2^{7+1}))) \\
 \mathbf{1671} &:= 172 \times (9 + 1) + 7 \times (2 - 9) &= (((9^2) + 7) \times (1 - (9 - 27))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1672} &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 + 9 + 1 + 7) \times (2 + 9) &= ((9 + ((2 + 7) + 1)) \times (9 + 2)) \times (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1673} &:= (1 \times 7 + 29 \times (1 + 7)) \times (-2 + 9) &= (9 + (2^7)) + (192 \times (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1674} &:= (1 \times 7 - 2 + 9 + 172) \times 9 &= ((9 \times (2 + 7)) - 19) \times (27 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1675} &:= 172 \times 9 + 1 + 7 \times 2 \times 9 &= 9 + ((2 \times 7) \times (((19 - 2) \times 7) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1676} &:= 1 + 7 \times (-2 + 9) \times 17 \times 2 + 9 &= (92 \times 7) - ((1 - 9) \times ((2^7) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1677} &:= (17 \times 2 + 9) \times (-1 + 7^2 - 9) &= ((92 + 7) \times (19 - 2)) - (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1678} &:= -1 \times 7 + 2 + 9 \times 17 \times (2 + 9) &= (((9^2) + 71) \times (9 + 2)) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1679} &:= 1 - 7 + 2 + 9 \times 17 \times (2 + 9) &= (9 + (2 \times 7)) \times (1 + (9 \times ((2 + 7) - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1680} &:= -1^7 - 2 + 9 \times 17 \times (2 + 9) &= (9 + ((2 + 7) + 192)) \times (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1681} &:= -1^7 \times 2 + 9 \times 17 \times (2 + 9) &= ((9 - 2) + ((71 - 9) \times 27)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1682} &:= 1^7 - 2 + 9 \times 17 \times (2 + 9) &= 9 - (2 - (((71 - 9) \times 27) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1683} &:= 1729 - 17 - 29 &= (9 + (2 + (7 - 1))) \times (92 + (7 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1684} &:= 1729 - (-1 + 7)^2 - 9 &= ((9 + 2) + ((71 - 9) \times 27)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1685} &:= 1 - (7 - 2) \times 9 + 1729 &= ((9 + 2) + ((71 - 9) \times 27)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1686} &:= -17 \times 2 - 9 + 1729 &= ((9 + 2) + ((71 - 9) \times 27)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1687} &:= 1729 + (-1 + 7) \times (2 - 9) &= (((9 \times 27) \times (1^9)) - 2) \times 7 \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1688} &:= (1 - 7 + 29) \times (1 + 72) + 9 &= (((9 \times 27) \times (1^9)) - 2) \times 7 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1689} &:= -1 + 7 + (2 \times 91 + 7 - 2) \times 9 &= (((92 - (7 \times 19))^2) + 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1690} &:= 1729 + 1 - 7^2 + 9 &= (((9 - 2) \times (7 + 1)) + 9) \times (27 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1691} &:= (17 + 2) \times (9 - 1 + 72 + 9) &= ((9^2) + (7 + 1)) \times ((9 + 2) + (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1692} &:= (1 + 7 + 2 + 91 - 7) \times 2 \times 9 &= ((92 - 7) \times ((1 + 9) \times 2)) - (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1693} &:= 1729 \times 1 - 7 - 29 &= ((9 - ((2 \times 7) \times (1 - 9))) \times (2 \times 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1694} &:= 1729 + 1 - 7 - 29 &= (9 - ((2 \times 7) \times (1 - 9))) \times ((2 \times 7) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1695} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 2 + 9 \times 17 \times (2 + 9) &= ((9 - ((2 \times 7) \times (1 - 9))) \times (2 \times 7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1696} &:= (-1 + 7 + 2) \times (9 \times 1 + 7 \times 29) &= 9 + (((27 \times 1) \times 9) - 2) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1697} &:= (-1 + 7) \times 291 + 7 \times (2 - 9) &= (9 + (((27 \times 1) \times 9) - 2) \times 7) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1698} &:= 172 \times (9 + 1) + 7 - 29 &= (((9 + 2) - 7) - 1) \times (((9^2) \times 7) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1699} &:= -1^7 - 29 + 1729 &= 9 - (2 \times (7 - (((1 + 9) + 2) \times 71))) \\
 \mathbf{1700} &:= -1^7 \times 29 + 1729 &= (((92 - 71) \times 9) \times (2 + 7)) - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1701} &:= 1729 - 17 - 2 - 9 &= (((92 - 71) \times 9) \times (2 + 7)) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1702} &:= 1729 - (-1 + 7)^2 + 9 &= (9 \times (271 - (9^2))) - (7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1703} &:= 1729 - 1 - 7 - 2 \times 9 &= (9 \times (271 - (9^2))) - (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1704} &:= (-1 + 7) \times (-2 + (9 + 17) \times (2 + 9)) &= ((9 + 27) - ((1 + 9) + 2)) \times 71 \\
 \mathbf{1705} &:= 1729 - 17 + 2 - 9 &= 9 + (2 \times (719 + ((2^7) + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1706} &:= -1 + 7 - 29 + 1729 &= (92 \times (7 + (1 + 9))) + (2 \times 71) \\
 \mathbf{1707} &:= 1 \times 7 - 29 + 1729 &= ((92 - 7) \times ((1 + 9) \times 2)) + (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1708} &:= 1729 + 1 + 7 - 29 &= (((9^2) + 71) + 92) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1709} &:= 172 \times (9 + 1) + 7 - 2 \times 9 &= ((9 - 27) \times (19 \times (2 - 7))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1710} &:= (17 + 2) \times (9 \times 1 + 72 + 9) &= 9 \times ((27 \times 1) + (92 + 71)) \\
 \mathbf{1711} &:= -1 \times 7 - 2 - 9 + 1729 &= (((92 + (7 \times 1)) \times 9) \times 2) - 71 \\
 \mathbf{1712} &:= (1 + 7) \times (2 + 9 \times 1 + 7 \times 29) &= ((9 + 2) + ((7 \times 1) \times (9 \times 27))) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1713} &:= 172 \times (9 + 1^7) + 2 - 9 &= 9 + (2 \times (71 \times ((9 \times 2) - (7 - 1)))) \\
 \mathbf{1714} &:= -1 - 7 + 2 - 9 + 1729 &= ((9 - 2) + (7 \times (1 + (9 \times 27)))) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1715} &:= 1729 \times 1 - 7 + 2 - 9 &= ((9 + (2^7)) \times ((1 + 9) + 2)) + 71 \\
 \mathbf{1716} &:= 1729 + 1 - 7 + 2 - 9 &= (9 \times (271 - (9^2))) + (7 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1717} &:= 1729 + 17 - 29 &= (9 \times (2^7)) - (1 - (((9^2) \times 7) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1718} &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 \times 9 + 1729 &= 9 + ((2 \times 719) + 271) \\
 \mathbf{1719} &:= -17 - 2 + 9 + 1729 &= (9 + 2) + (7 \times (1 + ((9 \times 27) \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1720} &:= 1729 - 1 - 72/9 &= ((92 + 71) + 9) \times (2 + (7 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1721} &:= 172 \times (9 + 1) + 7/(-2 + 9) &= 9 - (2 \times (71 - (927 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1722} &:= (1 + 7 \times (29 - 1 + 7)) \times (-2 + 9) &= (((9 \times 27) + (1^9)) + 2) \times (7 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{1723} &:= 1729 - 17 + 2 + 9 &= (((9 \times 27) + (1^9)) + 2) \times 7 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1724} &:= 1729 \times 1 - 7 \times 2 + 9 &= ((9 + (2 \times 7)) \times ((1 + (9^2)) - 7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1725} &:= 1 \times 7 - 2 - 9 + 1729 &= (9 - (2 \times (7 + (1 + 9)))) \times (2 - 71) \\
 \mathbf{1726} &:= 1729 + 1 + 7 - 2 - 9 &= (9 + 2) + (7 \times (1 + ((9 \times 27) + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1727} &:= 172 \times (9 + 1^7) - 2 + 9 &= (9 + 2) \times ((71 + 92) - (7 - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1728} &:= 1729 - 1^{729} &= (9 \times 2) \times ((7 \times 1) + ((9^2) + (7 + 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1729} &:= 1729 \times 1^{729} &= (9 + (2 \times (71 - 9))) \times ((2 \times 7) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

References

- [1] **Inder J. Taneja**, 2019 In Numbers, **Zenodo**, December 31, 2019, pp. 1-27, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2529103>.
- [2] **Inder J. Taneja**, 2020 In Numbers: Mathematical Style, **Zenodo**, December 31, 2019, pp. 1-37, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3596193>.

- [3] **Inder J. Taneja**, 21 Mathematical Highlights for 2021, **Zenodo**, December 26, 2020, pp. 1-75, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4394408>.
- [4] **Inder J. Taneja**, Geometrical, Numerical, and Symmetrical Representations for the Days of 2020, **Zenodo**, October 04, 2020, pp. 1-201, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4065069>.
Also see the link: Geometrical, Numerical, and Symmetrical Representations for the Days of 2020 <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2020/10/07/geometrical-numerical-and-symmetrical-representations-for-the-days-of-2020/>
- [5] **Inder J. Taneja**, Hardy-Ramanujan Number - 1729, **Zenodo**, December 22, 2021, pp. 1-106, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799640>. Also see site link: Hardy-Ramanujan Number - 1729, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=149>.
- [6] **Inder J. Taneja**, Mathematical Beauty of 2022, **Zenodo**, December 26, 2021, pp. 1-78, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5805264>.
- [7] **Inder J. Taneja**, 23 and 2023 in Numbers and Patterns, **Zenodo**, December 22, 2022, pp. 1-51, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7473340>.
- [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Mathematical Representations of the Last Day of the Year 23 Written American Style: 12.31.23 (123123), **Zenodo**, December 19, 2023, pp. 1-13, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10405771>
- [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Mathematical Aspects of 24 and 2024, **Zenodo**, December 19, 2023, pp. 1-40, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10406530>.
- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, Zenodo, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. Zenodo, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>
- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, Zenodo, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.
- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares with Order Square Magic Sums, Zenodo, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.
- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 108, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8230214>.
- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 81, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8231157>.
- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Striped Magic Squares of Even Orders 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14, Zenodo, November 10, 2023, pp. 1-34, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10107355>.

- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Orders 6, 10, 12, 14 and 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, Zenodo, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-31, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377674>.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Generating Pythagorean Triples and Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 31, Zenodo, May 28, 2021, pp. 1-153, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4837491>.
- [19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Inder J. Taneja, Sequential Pythagorean Triples and Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares, Zenodo, June 21, 2021, pp. 1-595, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5009204>.
- [20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 19, **Zenodo**, July 25, pp. 1-31, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8180919>.
- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Numbers and Magic Squares Representations of Hardy-Ramanujan Number-1729, **Zenodo**, December 20, 2024, pp. 1-127, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14538297>.
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